

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D7.3 Analysis: Communication and information

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is the third output of the COVINFORM project's WP7, which focuses on inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation. It builds on two previous reports, namely *D7.1 Baseline report: Communication and information* and *D7.2 Research design: Communication and information*. The present report assesses and critiques COVID-19 communication practices on key dimensions of impact. This deliverable contains seven research chapters, each focusing on a specific aspect of COVID-19 communication. The first two chapters analyse visual data of COVID-19 public health campaigns and COVID-19 memes using a content analysis. In more detail, the first chapter engages with government communication (strategies) and the second with a particular form of communication by residents, namely memes. The following five chapters focus on government communication and use *D7.1. Baseline report: Communication and information* as a base for analysing dimensions of impact of COVID-19 communication. These dimensions are: 1.) Good and bad practices in COVID-19 communication strategies, 2.) Communication to influence behaviour change, 3.) Digital communication and exclusion, 4.) Fighting malinformation, disinformation and misinformation, 5.) Representation and justice in media.

In line with the objectives of WP7, the task on which this deliverable reports has focused on two main research questions:

- RQ1: How have different actors designed, delivered and evaluated inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation?
- RQ2: What impact have COVID-19 communication strategies and practices had on individuals from the majority population and vulnerable groups?

Answers to these questions can be found in the seven chapters, each shedding light on a different aspect. Regarding RQ1 we have found that information campaigns have, at least initially, been addressed to the general public, before more targeted campaigns were launched. While there are some efforts to design campaigns inclusively, we could still observe a focus on the (white) majority population. We have further identified good and bad practices of COVID-19 crisis communication. With regards to addressing mis- and disinformation, we have found that while all countries under research have implemented some measures, they differ substantially between countries.

Regarding RQ2 we found that memes are a way to cope with the pandemic situation, particularly as a way to comment and critique measures, as well as the behaviour of members of society. Further, the shift towards digital communication, as described in chapter 6, as well as the pre-existing digital divide, increased digital inequalities. This shift towards digital communicating unveiled a need to improve policies and access to digital media. Finally, we found that the way media provide information about the crisis influences how members of the public make sense of the pandemic, including which groups are perceived as vulnerable.

The analyses conducted for this deliverable unveiled some gaps that will be investigated further. These include, on the one hand, the effect of information campaigns and media representation on residents, particularly on groups defined as vulnerable. On the other hand, the impact of COVID-19 communication on behaviour change needs to be explored further as well as what is considered to be good communication from a resident perspective.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
D	Deliverable
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
PM	Prime Minister
RQ	Research Question
WHO	World Health Organisation
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

This deliverable assesses and critiques COVID-19 communication practices on key dimensions of impact. This deliverable contains seven research chapters, each focusing on a specific aspect of COVID-19 communication. The first two chapters analyse visual data of COVID-19 public health campaigns and COVID-19 memes using a content analysis. In more detail, the first chapter engages with government communication (strategies) and the second with a particular form of communication by residents, namely memes. The following five chapters focus on government communication and use D7.1. 'Baseline report: Communication and information as a base for analysing dimensions of impact of COVID-19 communication. These dimensions are: 1.) Good and bad practices in COVID-19 communication strategies, 2.) Communication to influence behaviour change, 3.) Digital communication and exclusion, 4.) Fighting malinformation, disinformation and misinformation, 5.) Representation and justice in media.

The overarching research questions (RQs) for WP7 are:

- RQ1: How have different actors designed, delivered and evaluated inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation?
- RQ2: What impact have COVID-19 communication strategies and practices had on individuals from the majority population and vulnerable groups?

Aim of this deliverable is to provide findings which, together with the outcomes of the empirical research for WP7, the baseline report (D7.1) and the second iteration of this deliverable, help to answer the overarching research question of the work package. These will be synthesised in *D7.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on communication, information and misinformation*, due in month 18 of the project. Additionally, the deliverable will be guiding the empirical research for WP7. Beside the new insights gained, the contribution of this deliverable is crucial for WP7 in two ways: 1.) D7.3 is highlighting important issues which should be further investigated in the empirical research. 2.) It shows the partnership where crucial information is still missing in order to be able to answer the overarching research questions in D7.4 and its second iteration. This information can then be generated in the empirical research and the second iteration of this deliverable. Further, D7.3 relates to the other tasks in WP7 in so far as it builds on the findings generated in *D7.1 Baseline report: Communication and information* and the research design developed in D7.2. D7.3 will also be of help for WP6, which focuses on questions of community responses, and the respective resident interviews as this deliverable highlights best practice community examples. It also shows how some groups are at risk 1.) of being negatively impacted by digital inequality, 2.) of exclusion through media representation and, 3.) of exclusion through a lack of representation in public health campaigns.

Communication about public health recommendations was a crucial measure particularly at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, when hygiene guidelines and public health recommendations were the only measure to fight the spread of the disease. Chapter 2, led by SYNYO, presents the outcomes of an analysis of information campaigns aiming at influencing behaviour through communication activities (Atkin & Rice 2013). The analysis was guided by the following questions: 1.) What is the dominant topic of the communication? 2.) What narratives (i.e. stories) are created? 3.) How are they trying to influence perceptions? 4.) What groups are represented and how were certain groups (not) represented? 5.) How is humour used in these campaigns as a means to change/influence behaviour? What other elements or emotive strategies were used? A sample of 93 images containing

images of public health campaigns from ten EU countries +UK from March 2020 until November 2021 was analysed through a content analysis, following the logic of Panofsky's (1962) iconology (see also Müller 2011). Themes and topics were coded inductively.

During the pandemic, researchers could observe the production and sharing of COVID-19 related memes (Kuipers 2020). Indeed, memes are often used to comment on current issues; they “facilitate discursive exchanges about events within society and criticism of these events” (Pauliks 2020, 47). Led by SYNYO, chapter 3 presents the outcomes of an explorative analysis of memes aiming to gain an understanding of how humour was used to cope with the events of the pandemic and communicate with others. The guiding questions for the analysis were: 1.) What were the dominant narratives in the memes? 2.) On what (e.g., COVID-19 measures or impacts) and who (e.g., politicians, services, residents) do memes in the different countries under research focus? 3.) How are aspects of vulnerability discussed within memes (e.g., mental health issues, loneliness)? A sample of 668 memes collected between the beginning of 2020 and autumn 2021 within the ten countries of analysis (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, the UK) was coded inductively, creating categories through identifying themes within the data set.

The following five chapters and their analysis of dimension of impact are based on findings from D7.1 'Baseline report: Communication and information. The data was collected through desk research conducted for the time period of March 2020 until March 2021. The data collected reached from public health campaigns, government statements, strategy papers, grey literature, academic publications, newspaper articles, evaluations to social media posts. As such, the data presented here does not claim to be comprehensive. Rather, it constitutes the openly available information in the presented timeframe. Most of the dimensions used additional data to complement their analysis. This deliverable includes ten 10 EU countries + UK (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden & the UK). Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, England and Wales are the countries within which the COVINFORM project will be conducting empirical research. As England and Wales will both be field site in the empirical research data for the UK focuses on those two countries. Romania, which is part of this deliverable, will not be a field site for empirical research in the COVINFORM project. However, due to their status as practitioner partner in this project and their 'on ground' expertise and insights, Romania is included in this report. The analysis of each of these chapters was led by a different consortium partner.

In chapter four, the Austrian Red Cross provides a short overview of good and bad practices in COVID-19 communication strategies across the ten EU countries + UK. The guiding research question is: What good practices of COVID-19 communication as well as challenges can be identified? The chapter particularly focuses on the communicators, communication strategies and channels as well as communication targeting vulnerable groups. Through the analysis of these practices several categories of relevance for good communication could be identified. Finally, the chapter provides a library summarizing the identified good and bad practices.

TRI engaged with communication for behaviour change in chapter 5. Encouraging residents to change behaviour and engage in protective measures such as mask wearing and regular hand washing; physically distancing; avoiding mass gathering; staying at home; working/schooling from home; public testing; and vaccinating is still crucial for the successful fight of COVID-19. The guiding research questions of this chapter are: 1.) Did communication (strategies) from the countries under research follow recommendations for effective communication? 2.) Were these strategies able to encourage

people to change their behaviour? As there is limited research assessing the effectiveness of the communication strategies of the eleven countries, compliance with COVID-19 measures was chosen as the main indicator for successful/unsuccessful communication for behaviour change.

The next chapter focuses on digital communication and exclusion. Within the COVID-19 crisis, there was a shift towards digital communication. Digital communication is a great way of reaching broad audiences as it is easy to upscale. However, digital communication effectively excluded several groups from communication and relevant information. The COVINFORM practitioner partner MDI presents a comprehensive literature review on the topics of digital inequality asking questions on which groups are impacted by it and how can the risks of digital inequality be mitigated. Although digital inequality was not explicitly explored in D7.1 the chapter highlights what initiatives mitigating the effects of the digital divide could be identified in D7.1

The pandemic has been shaped by what is called an 'infodemic'. Particularly negative effects of this are the rapid spread of dis- and misinformation. Chapter 7 which is led by SYNNO analyses how countries are fighting the spread of dis- and misinformation in times of COVID-19. The two research questions explored in this chapter are: what measures and initiatives have been implemented by (national) governments to fight and cope with mis- and disinformation during the COVID-19 pandemic? What best practices can be found amongst those measures and initiatives? The measures and initiatives taken can broadly be divided in 12 categories. The chapter also presents some good and best practices examples on national and local government level. The initiatives discussed are targeted at groups at risk of communication vulnerability.

The final chapter, led by UGOT, focuses on the topic of representations and justice in media. Media content affects what issues and which groups and individuals in society the public considers being important. Additionally, media content also affects how issues, groups and individuals are presented and perceived by the public (Entman, 1993). This comes with many issues such as misrepresentation or underrepresentation/ overrepresentation of certain social groups or problems. This chapter explores the three following questions: 1.) Which groups are represented in the media? 2.) How are different concerns and threats addressed? 3.) How might certain fears and threat perceptions be connected to prejudice, discrimination and hate speech? To answer these questions the UGOT team draws on findings from the EU 10+ UK countries and elaborates more in-depth on these issues in a Sweden specific case study.

This deliverable provides important findings on the COVID-19 communication in Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, and the UK. The findings of this report will highlight interesting and/or contradictory phenomena and draw attention to which data that is not yet generated but still needed. As such, the findings presented will shape the direction of the empirical research.

2 COVID-19 public health campaigns

Communication about public health recommendations was a crucial measure particularly at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, when hygiene guidelines and public health recommendations were the only measure to fight the spread of the disease. Later, with the availability of the vaccines, vaccination campaigns also became fundamental. In this chapter, we look at information campaigns as “purposive attempts to inform or influence behaviors in large audiences within a specified time period using an organized set of communication activities and featuring an array of mediated messages in multiple channels generally to produce non-commercial benefits to individuals and society” (Atkin & Rice 2013). What makes public health information campaigns around COVID-19 interesting is the fact that everyone is affected by the pandemic. This affects the way campaigns are targeted at specific groups. Furthermore, due to the duration of the (still ongoing) pandemic, keeping the audiences’ attention, particularly when repeating information, is a challenge.

Narratives – or storytelling – are an effective way of communicating public health information (Patel & Patel 2017). As Gubrium and Gubrium (2021) point out, the narratives about safety communicated in public health campaigns (e.g., distancing, wearing of face masks, etc.) need to be socially and contextually informed by lived experiences. The concept of safety may differ between social groups; the ability to follow public health advice is connected to multiple and intersection social categories such as socio-economic status, gender, *race*/ethnicity, age, and others. As such, public health responses aimed at reducing risk need to consider these contexts and their influence on individual decision making (ibid.).

Behavioural and social sciences have defined key principles for public health campaigns to be effective (particularly in the context of epidemics or pandemics), such as providing clear and specific guidance, ‘protect each other’ messages of solidarity, addressing social norms, avoiding messages of fear or disgust in relation to other persons, and avoiding authoritarian messages. Messages should also be possible to follow (i.e., actionable) and be communicated in a professional style (Bonell et al. 2020).

In the following, we first describe the methodology and key research questions of our analysis of public health campaigns. We then present key insights per country, focusing on ten target countries: Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden and the UK. Then, we describe insights of our cross-country analysis, before closing with some conclusions.

2.1 Methodology

To analyse public health campaigns in ten selected European countries / areas, we have followed an explorative approach. Our main research questions (RQs) are:

- RQ1: What is the dominant topic of the communication?
- RQ2: What narratives (i.e. stories) are created? How are they trying to influence perceptions?
- RQ3: What groups are represented and how were certain groups (not) represented?
- RQ4: How is humour used in these campaigns as a means to change/influence behaviour? What other elements or emotive strategies were used?

Partners have selected at least one image of a public health campaign per quarter since the widely acknowledged beginning of the pandemic in February/March of 2020 until Q3 of 2021, resulting in a sample of a total of 93 pictures. The campaigns included focus on different areas; furthermore, both

national-level and local-level campaigns were subject of this analysis. Partners were advised to focus on national-level campaigns where local campaigns were not available.

In our analysis, we have identified themes and topics used in the information campaigns through manual inductive coding in conducting a content analysis. The analysis followed the logic of Panofsky's (1962) iconographic-iconological method (see also Müller 2011), identifying and categorising themes per country as well as overarching themes and stylistic elements. Panofsky's iconographic-iconological method consists of three steps, the pre-iconographic description, the iconography, and the iconology. In our analysis, we conducted the first two steps: first, in the pre-iconographic description, the factual (or primary) image content was described, thus enabling the researchers to grasp every aspect of the image. In the second step, the iconography, context was added, thus seeking the conventional meaning of the image while providing the social and cultural context needed to understand the signs, symbols and images. The third step, the iconology, which aims to uncover the intrinsic meaning and underlying principles, was not yet conducted. The reason for this is to align the analysis further with the upcoming fieldwork in the context of WP7: semi-structured interviews with communication experts and residents will provide us with relevant context and indicators to then carry out the third step of analysis. This way, insights will be aligned and an overall analysis can be conducted.

Notably, our analysis does not reflect experiences of these campaigns, nor their effectiveness. This will be explored in the upcoming research activities including residents in the selected sub-national geographic areas, and reported in *D7.7 Analysis: Communication and information – update M34*.

In the following, we present a summary of the main findings per country, as well as a cross-country analysis of overarching themes and similarities. It is important to add that neither the selection of the campaigns, nor the analysis we conducted, are representative and claim any generalisability. Rather, we explore the themes and topics, stylistic elements, narratives, and representativity of these campaigns.

2.2 Country analysis

2.2.1 Austria

Context and included campaigns

The collection of Austrian information campaigns provided ten images. Out of those, two are national-level information campaigns published by the Austrian federal government (March and May 2020), the subsequent campaigns were all distributed by the City of Vienna.

Insights

The first two campaigns by the Austrian Federal Government are very simple and clear, using big letters on a single-coloured background with simple drawings. The message is clear and simple: keep a distance. Both images contain the slogan "look after yourself, look after others".

Figure 1. Austrian public health campaign | 24.05.2020

While the campaigns launched by the Austrian government at the beginning of the pandemic are rather plain and simple, with a straightforward message, the (later published) campaigns by the City of Vienna make use of humour and more colourful stylistic language. These campaigns communicate simple messages – for example, keep a distance, wash your hands, stay at home, wear a mask, or: get vaccinated – but make use of humorous elements to do so: either in the form of the image (a pantomime miming the correct distance), in the form of dialect words, pop-cultural references, puns, or rhymes. Most of the campaigns used photos, contrary to the very simple images used by the info campaigns by the Austrian government, with one exception. Since summer 2021, the vaccination campaign came to a halt and the vaccination progress

slowed down (Eberl, Partheymüller & Paul 2021).

The dominant topics of the public health campaigns are (in chronological order/aligned with the evolution of the pandemic): providing behavioural guidelines (e.g., ‘keep a distance’), and motivating persons to get vaccinated. The latter includes information about the prioritisation of the vaccination campaigns.

We can observe a narrative of solidarity, focused on the protection of oneself and others (“schau auf dich, schau auf mich” – “look after yourself, look after others”), in the national information campaign. This is later repeated in the local campaign in Vienna with the slogan “us against the virus”. There is also a narrative of freedom, connected to the vaccines: in getting vaccinated, persons can free themselves of the virus.

With regards to inclusivity, initially, the public health campaigns make only use of text and simple drawings, i.e. there were no specific groups represented (or not represented). Those campaigns using of photos (by the City of Vienna) show white people. Campaigns are directed at different audiences: while some target young people and reference partying / going out, others are directed at older people. The majority of the campaigns, however, are directed at the general public.

Particularly the campaigns launched by the City of Vienna are humorous, making use of different stylistic and rhetoric devices: puns, rhymes, pop-cultural references, funny pictures, and dialect. One example is the campaign that states ‘The OIDA rules’. It uses both dialect and funny pictures; ‘OIDA’ is both an acronym for the measures (**O**bstand **H**oiten (which in Viennese dialect means ‘keep your distance’), **I**mmers d’**H**änd’ **w**oschn (which in Viennese dialect means ‘Always wash your hands’), **D**aham **b**leibn’ which in Viennese Dialect means ‘Stay at home’, and **A** Maskn **a**ufsetzen’, which means ‘Wear a mask’). The word ‘Oida’ is widely used in Viennese dialect particularly by youth and young adults. It has countless meanings and applications. Its meaning often only changes through the tonality. With the ‘baby elephant’, we can also observe a very simplistic style.

2.2.2 Belgium

Context and included campaigns

While the aim was to include examples of public health campaigns specific to the City of Antwerp, there were not many such campaigns available. Therefore, most of the included example were used in all of Flanders (i.e. the Dutch-speaking region in Belgium) and two examples of national-level campaigns. A total of ten images were included in the analysis.

Insights

The first public health campaigns are very clear and simple, focusing on the most important rules and measures. Using alerting and bright colours, they transport key messages in a simple way. With the evolution of the pandemic, the initially very serious messages become more light-hearted and humorous. The dominant topic of communication across almost all of the analysed public health campaigns are simple and easy-to-follow rules such as ‘stay at home’, ‘wash your hands’, ‘keep distance’, ‘protect older people’. One campaign also reminds people to take care of themselves. As the pandemic evolves, the same messages are repeated, reminding the audiences that there is still a pandemic ongoing and measures are still needed. Campaigns focused on both public health measures (such as hygiene recommendations) and the vaccination.

The narratives created are predominantly ones of civic responsibility and solidarity, asking for compliance with the rules to protect others. They communicate positive messages (‘together, we can beat the pandemic’), focussing on unity and cohesiveness; and the collective nature of the pandemic is underlined. Positive messages of self-confidence and solidarity are also communicated. Later on, there is a focus on ‘restarting life’ (with/due to the vaccination), and to have fun with common sense (i.e., while still keeping the rules of distancing and wearing masks in mind). Figure 2 below shows to women, eating in a restaurant. The slogan reminds them to enjoy with moderation, to have ‘fun with common sense’. Messages to ‘keep distance’ are repeated, reminding the population to continue to be careful so numbers will not rise again and stricter measures can be avoided.

The majority of the campaigns use text and simple drawings only; as such, no specific groups are represented or excluded. One campaign also focuses on the 11 million Belgians together in the crisis, i.e. on sending a message of unity. Contrary to that, the first vaccination campaign uses testimonials of people from different ethnicities, all in the same posture: showing off their left arm (after being vaccinated), wearing a mask. In general, the focus shifted over time: in the beginning, the posters featured health care workers and elderly people (because they had vaccine priority), and later the campaigns broadened in scope. However, the majority of the posters/campaigns showed white persons.

The initial campaigns (by the Flemish government) are of a rather serious nature and transport the most important rules. However, already the second one by the Flemish government makes use of

Figure 2. Belgian public health campaign | 04.06.2021

humorous images, i.e., cute and relaxed-looking (baby) animals, being more playful and caring. There is also a connection to a well-known public health slogan ('drink with moderation'), a play on words (see Figure 2).

2.2.3 Germany

Context and included campaigns

For Germany, all included examples of public health campaigns are published by the city of Berlin and thus focus on a sub-national level. A total of seven images were included in the analysis.

Insights

The majority of the info campaigns by the City of Berlin uses text only, few make use of photos or drawn images as well. They all communicate simple and clear messages, sometimes using metaphors or references to sports or pop culture. The campaigns use bright colours, predominantly red, white and/or black. The main messages that are communicated are public health recommendations ('stay at home', 'keep a distance', 'protect others'), messages of solidarity, and hygiene guidelines. At a later stage of the pandemic, also the fight against mis- and disinformation ("fake news") is emphasised.

The most present narrative is one of solidarity, fighting the pandemic together by complying with the regulations, thus demonstrating solidarity. This is also summarised in the hashtag #BerlinGegenCorona. There is also a focus on positive aspects, such as the increase in solidarity. A common goal – fighting the pandemic – is further emphasised. One example is Figure 3 below: the

Figure 3. Germany public health campaign | 12.04.2020

image is minimalistic, consisting of white text against a bright red background. The first bold sentence says: "Die gute Nachricht: Auch Solidarität ist ansteckend" ("Good news: solidarity is also contagious"). The second phrase states: "Danke an alle, die sich auch an Feiertagen solidarisch zeigen und damit Menschenleben schützen" ("Thank you to all who show solidarity even on holidays and thus protect human lives"). The image emphasises

the positive side-effects of the pandemic (increased social solidarity) by reframing the red-hot pandemic vocabulary "contagious" in a positive context.

With regards to the representation of specific groups, the majority of the campaigns are designed in a rather minimalistic format, with text on a single-coloured background. Those that do make use of photos or drawings are designed in an inclusive way; and visual puns like rainbow lights can be an allusion to the LGBTQ movement which is an important part of popular culture in Berlin.

The campaigns are designed in a light-hearted way, making use of humoristic element such as puns and references to pop culture. Figure 3 is one example, stating that solidarity may be contagious like the virus. We can also observe several references to pop culture and the 'do-it-yourself' culture in Berlin as a famous party and festival city. Metaphors from sport (football) are also used ("Abstand ist die beste Verteidigung. Macht jetzt mit und schützt Euer Team!" – "Distance is the best defense. Join now and protect your team!"), as well as repetition of well-known public health slogans.

2.2.4 Greece

Context and included campaigns

For Greece, a total of sixteen images were included in the analysis. The majority of these images were published by the Ministry of Health, with some local examples included (e.g., Municipality of Chalkida).

Insights

All of the Greek campaigns analysed follow the same style of simple infographics, aimed to inform the public about the most important rules such as washing hands, keeping distance, wearing masks, avoiding meeting people when feeling sick, trusting experts, throwing out tissues, etc. They make use of bright colours, simple images, and communicate simple and clear messages. Addressed are mainly the general population, with specific audiences are addressed, it is schools/students and the unvaccinated.

We can observe focus on three key messages: public health recommendations and measures (staying at home), following the hygiene practices (e.g., washing hands), and information about vaccinations. At the beginning of the pandemic, the message is focused on staying at home and establishing hygiene practices; with the development of the pandemic, more emphasis was put on hygiene guidelines and particularly on wearing masks (how to wear them correctly, not to forget them, etc.). One example is Figure 4 below: the illustration demonstrates the bad hygiene practices that are relevant to the use of masks. Specifically, the image shows what people should not do whilst wearing a mask in five informative pictures which can be seen in an orange-font background. The first shows a torn mask and the text can be translated as: “We do not use torn/ripped masks”. The second shows the woman touching the mask and the text can be translated as: “We do not touch our mask when we wear it”. The third depicts the woman wearing the mask on her chin and the text can be translated as: “We do not lower our mask to our chin”. The fourth depicts the woman wearing the mask under her nose, leaving her more exposed and the text can be translated as: “We do not wear the mask under our nose”. Concluding the last illustration depicts a mask with smaller icons of what can be interpreted as virus-particles and the text can be translated as: “We do not re-use masks of one-use-only”.

Figure 4. Greek public health campaign | 22.07.2020

With the availability of the vaccine, focus was put on providing information about the vaccines and countering misinformation (stressing that the vaccines are safe), and to communicate the prioritisation of the vaccines. Hygiene guidelines are nevertheless still repeated, even once vaccines are available.

The Greek information campaigns show a strong emphasis on the ‘we’ – with slogans like “we stay at home” communicate that we are all in this together. This strengthens solidarity but sounds paternalistic at times (“we do not touch our mask when we wear it”). There is also an emphasis of the individual’s responsibility in following the guidelines (e.g. “wear a mask – save a life”). With the availability of vaccines, there is also a focus on ‘get liberated, enjoy life’, to encourage people to get vaccinated.

As mentioned above, all campaigns use text and simple drawings only; as such, no groups represented (or not represented). In terms of stylistic devices, we can observe repetition of campaigns and the use of similar images to reinforce the message. The campaigns use bright colours and simple images, sometimes infographics or line drawings. This style did not change throughout the duration of the pandemic observed (Q1-2020 until Q3-2021). In a later stage of the pandemic, we can observe the use of fear, providing information about the numbers of unvaccinated persons in intensive care.

2.2.5 Italy

Context and included campaigns

In the Italian context, a total of nine images were included in the analysis. These images were published on both national and regional level.

Insights

The most prominent and observable aspect of the Italian public health campaigns is that they make use of emotion, which is also reflected in the use of photos for the campaigns, portraying e.g. doctors in protective gear. Messages are similarly emotional rather than short and simple, yet still coherent and intelligible.

The Italian public health campaigns focus on measures ('stay at home') and guidelines/measures ('wear a mask') in the initial phase of the pandemic, aiming to keep people alert. In the second phase, the dominant topic are the vaccinations, including countering misinformation and addressing uncertainty ('all vaccines are effective'). This also includes the safety measures installed to travel again (EU Green Pass).

In the first phase of the pandemic, the Italian campaigns build their narrative around fear, guilt, and thankfulness to the doctors that lost their lives. One example is Figure 5 below: the image shows the tired smile of a doctor, whose figure is covered by a full-body suit and a professional mask that does not allow her to be recognised. The doctor's figure stands out against the background of the Italian flag.

Figure 5. Italian public health campaign | 30.06.2020

A white label "Io medico giuro che avrò cura di te, in ogni emergenza" ("I, the doctor, swear that I will take care of you in every emergency") covers the left-hand side of the image with a subtitle "Emergenza Covid-19. 170 medici hanno dato la vita. Non dimentichiamolo" ("Covid-19 emergency. 170 doctors gave their lives. Let us not forget."). As such, the campaigns focus on the negative consequences and the fear evoked by the pandemic.

With the availability of the vaccines, the campaigns become more positive, following a narrative of rebirth, re-starting life. Getting vaccinated means to beat the virus – "Let's take back the taste of the future".

The persons portrayed on photos are predominantly white; the focus is put on displaying healthcare workers. There is one campaign with two non-white persons, focused on informing migrants on the importance of getting vaccinated. Another campaign includes celebrities. Mainly, the campaigns address the general public, with one campaign directed at migrants specifically.

As mentioned above, we can observe that some of the Italian information campaigns use fear, blame, and/or guilt to evoke emotions and thus compliance. For example, one image contains a caption that reads “La scelta è tua ma le conseguenze riguardano tutti noi” (“The choice is yours but the consequences affect us all”), as well as “Aiutaci a contenere la diffusione del coronavirus, prima che sia troppo tardi” (“Help us contain the spread of the coronavirus, before it’s too late”). Another one reminds of the 170 doctors who died during the first wave of the pandemic, which evokes emotions of sadness and thankfulness.

We can also observe a slight religious connotation: with the availability of the vaccination, Italy is ‘reborn’, which is symbolised by the primrose, the first flower to bloom after winter. As such, the campaign communicates serenity and regeneration, after a dark ‘winter’ Italy is reborn through the vaccine. Other stylistic devices are the inclusion of celebrities, and the use of the V-sign for ‘victory’ but also for ‘vaccine’.

2.2.6 Portugal

Context and included campaigns

For Portugal, the focus was put on sub-national public health campaigns. The Portuguese Ministry of Health provided campaign templates to be shared by the counties on their platforms throughout the pandemic. Few local authorities held public health campaigns that deviated from the government’s general messages. A total of seven images were included in the analysis.

Insights

Overall, the analysed Portuguese campaigns use simple messages, they are clear and coherent in image and content. They address the general public, as well as young people, for the latter the message is to keep safe and patient. With regards to the dominant topic of communication, we have identified three key messages or topics: first, the focus lies on the implemented measures (‘stay at home’). Second, the focus lies on the message of keeping alert and continue to follow the measures (e.g., washing hands, staying at home, keeping a distance). With the availability of vaccinations, campaigns aim to motivate people to get vaccinated.

The Portuguese campaigns create a narrative of solidarity – follow the measures for yourself and for your own protection – as well as one of fear and guilt. One example is shown in Figure 6. Two images are displayed side by side: the one on the left shows a young woman looking at the camera, smiling with a mask on and gesturing with a thumbs-up; the image on the right portrays another young woman laying on a hospital bed with a venturi mask delivering oxygen. The top text says “COVID-19/The decision is yours”. Going across both images, the phrase “Wear mask or wear mask”, each “wear mask” on an image, and the disjunctive “or” split in each image. In the bottom, the different organizations supporting this message: the Portuguese Republic’s Department of Health, the National Health Service, the General Directorate of Health, and the “We are ON” government website (a Portuguese initiative that gives relevant information about COVID-19 guidelines. This campaign was launched in January 2021, when Portugal experienced the highest death rates since the beginning of the pandemic.

Figure 6. Portuguese public health campaign | 28.01.2021

With regards to representation and inclusivity, about half of the campaigns make use of photos; these all portray white people. In terms of groups addressed, as described above, the majority of the campaigns address the general public, with two focused on young people specifically.

While there is a use of emotive strategies, particularly addressing the emotions of fear and guilt, we can also observe the use of humour in some of the campaigns: use of puns or popular proverbs, as well as pop culture references (video games) and an analogy to football.

2.2.7 Romania

Context and included campaigns

For Romania, the majority of the included images are part of campaigns launched on the national level, either by the Ministry of Health, WHO Romania, or the Romanian Red Cross. A total of seven images were included in the analysis.

Insights

The Romanian information campaigns communicate simple and clear messages, predominantly through infographics and comic-style drawn images, using bright colours. All campaigns analysed are addressed to the general public; the dominant topics of communication changed with the development of the pandemic: first, focus was put on communicating measures and hygiene guidelines (through infographics), aiming to raise awareness (even before the outbreak in Romania) on the correct (and incorrect) way of following hygiene guidelines. Next, focus was put on keeping the population alert, communicating that the pandemic is not yet over. This also includes protective measures for the start of the school year.

With the availability of the vaccines, messages turned to vaccination, including fighting of misinformation (e.g., the rumour that mRNA vaccines alter the DNA). The message was that one by one, the Romanian population can stop the pandemic. Finally, there are campaigns tackling the physical and mental well-being of the population, promoting self-care. One example is Figure 7 below: the image shows a comic-style male individual jogging, driving a bike, drinking water and eating healthy food (i.e., vegetables and fruits). As such, the image promotes a healthy lifestyle; it was part of a call to action to “make a priority out of your physical and mental health”. It was published in Summer 2021, when infection rates went down, but also the progress of the vaccination rates were low.

Figure 7. Romanian public health campaign | 24.09.2021

In the Romanian public health campaigns, we can observe a subtle narrative of solidarity and togetherness in the fight against the pandemic; predominantly, the focus is put on providing clear and simple information. With the availability of the vaccine, there is also a message of hope.

None of the Romanian information campaigns used photos; the majority of the used drawings were designed in an inclusive way, portraying persons of different gender and ethnicity. However, we could observe gendered stereotypes in one of the infographics, showing female figures conducting typical household activities (cleaning, caring for a child), whereas male figures are shown taking care for themselves (e.g., showering).

The campaigns were all designed in a rather straightforward and serious way, without making use of humour or any appeal to emotions.

2.2.8 Spain

Context and included campaigns

For Spain, the images selected and analysed were published by a variety of actors, from the Spanish government to local-level actors such as Madrid City Hall or Madrid Metro. A total of ten images were included in the analysis.

Insights

The Spanish public health campaigns we have analysed are simple and direct, with clear messages. The majority addresses the general public, one is directed at schools (teachers, children, parents). The main topics of communication are to follow regulations and hygiene guidelines (e.g., wear masks), as well as to take care of oneself (e.g. in terms of physical health, avoiding smoking, etc.). Further communicated are good and bad practices of hygiene. With the development of the pandemic, there is also a focus on prevention of the next wave, aiming to keep people alert and continue to follow the measures; as well as a focus on the vaccines.

The main narratives observed are those of solidarity and unity – together, the virus can be stopped, ‘I protect you, you protect me’, ‘we will fight the virus together’ – as well as hope (‘building a better and healthier world’). There is also a focus on cooperation. However, we can also observe a narrative of fear and guilt (see below). The majority of the campaigns make use of comic-style drawings; where photos are used, the portrayed persons are white.

With regards to the use of emotive content, there is a use of fear and guilt: to skip quarantine means to intubate the best friend, or an unprotected family reunion equals burying one’s grandmother, as shown in Figure 8: the image is part of a set of images published in a communication campaign of the community of Madrid before Christmas 2020. At this time, restrictions were relaxed, which meant that recommendations and warnings were repeated in the campaign to avoid any increase in infections. The campaign resorted to powerful images that alluded to the primal feelings, in this case of the youngest.

Figure 8. Spanish public health campaigns | 16.11.2020

We can also observe the use of puns / play on words: the vaccination campaign #YOME VACUNO SEGURO says “I get vaccinated for sure” but also means that the vaccine is completely safe.

2.2.9 Sweden

Context and included campaigns

In accordance with the Swedish constitutional model, the responsibility for health care is on the regional authorities. All nursing of covid-infected patients, testing and vaccination are coordinated and

performed by the country's 21 regions. In the following, the focus was put on images used in public communication campaigns from Västra Götandsregionen (VGR), which is the second largest Swedish region with 1,734,443 inhabitants (2020). The regional capital is Gothenburg, Sweden's second largest city. The search strategy included images, i.e. photos or illustrations that have been part of a communication activity. In cases where the most disseminated image is a video, the video's initial image is presented. It is this image the public first sees; communication activities, i.e. packaged communication with the Västra Götaland Region as sender and with residents as target group. For example, ads, social media posts and campaigns; and communication activity about COVID-19, where the topic was COVID-19 but the campaign included, for example, the spread of infection, sampling, hand hygiene, vaccination, etc. A total of seven images were included in the analysis.

Insights

The Swedish information campaigns are rather straightforward and simple, yet we still can observe the use of emotive content. Focus is put on simple messages, addressing the general public, as well as persons older than 50 and younger people (both target groups regarding vaccinations). There is also one campaign directed at immigrants (with different languages).

The dominant topics of communication change along with the development of the pandemic. In the beginning, there is a call for help to reduce pressure on the health information system: the population is asked to only call when it is necessary. There is also information about hygiene guidelines, which is a reoccurring topic in the next campaigns – recommendations such as avoid crowds, keep distance, avoid travelling by public transport. To address raising numbers, the spread of the pandemic is illustrated by statistics (bar diagrams), and the repetition of advice, with the message to keep alert. One example is shown in Figure 9:

Figure 9. Swedish public health campaign | 26.05.2021

With the availability of the vaccinations, campaigns focus on information about the prioritisation (who can get vaccinated) as well as about the vaccines (where to get it, where to find further information, how many doses are needed). Finally, information about the booster shot is provided. One example is Figure 9, which shows a middle-aged smiling woman. In the left part of the image a text is displayed, announcing the start of vaccination of persons 50 years or older: “Vaccination of 50 years and older. It is now possible for people born 1971 or earlier to book an appointment for vaccination against COVID-19. The demand for vaccines is still

higher than the supply and therefore there is currently a shortage of available appointments. New times for appointments are added as the vaccination centre receives the vaccine. On 1177.se there is a page that shows available time slots and there you can book an appointment. Together we stop the spread of infection! Read more about vaccine against covid-19 at 1177.se”

The main narrative we could observe in the campaigns is one of solidarity: the population is asked to keep the curve down collectively, and to continue following the recommended measures (mainly, distancing).

described. It also emphasises the importance of wearing a mask, as a sensible preventative measure, ‘use your head, stop the spread’.

In the majority of the campaigns, no specific groups are represented; those which include persons are designed inclusively, showing persons of different genders, ages and ethnicity.

With regards to humour and stylistic elements we could identify, we can see that local elements are used: as described above, the local monument ‘the Bull’ is a recurring element in the campaigns. The sculpture was commissioned as a sign of Birmingham’s regeneration, and to represent its history (i.e., the bullring). This is combined with play on words: the symbol of the bull is not only used to represent the seriousness of the public health advice, as described in the phrase, ‘No Bull’, a shortened form of the English phrase, ‘bullshit’ meaning ‘complete nonsense or something that is not true’.

With regards to emotive strategies, we can observe serious and warning messages; the use of capital letters aims at touching upon emotions and fears about the COVID-19. These emotive elements are also reflected by the use of colours, mainly black and yellow or black and red, which are traditional colours of danger and alarm. This changes with the development of the pandemic, the use of colours is softer and less alerting in the campaigns on “Healthy Brum” contrary to the “Keep Brum safe” and “It’s no Bull” campaigns. The use of hashtags such as #BrumTogether gives a sense of community and empathy.

2.3 Cross-country analysis

In the following, we present an overview of overarching themes and stylistic element identified across the public health campaigns described above. As there are differences in the levels (national vs. sub-national campaigns) of the campaigns included, we want to stress that this is neither a complete nor representative analysis. Rather, we aimed to explore the use of specific themes and stylistic elements.

In the following, we split the analysis into two main parts: the messages communicated (including narratives) on the one hand, and the stylistic elements on the other hand.

2.3.1 Messages & narratives in public health campaigns across countries

One narrative observable in public health campaigns across national borders is one of *solidarity and unity*, creating a sense of togetherness and unity against the virus. According to Bonell et al. 2020, messages of ‘protect each other’ are effective and valuable particularly when promoting collective identity and supportive social norms. Figure 11 shows such messages of unity and solidarity; they use slogans (“Wir statt Virus” – “Us instead of Virus”), hashtags (#BerlinGegenCorona, #viseuficaemcasa), and messages of unity (“1 TEAM. 11 MILLION. All together we can beat the coronavirus.”). There are also messages addressing loneliness and isolation (“Are you self-isolating? You are not alone.”). Some campaigns also use national colours to communicate this message of unity. Such ‘stand together’ messages emphasise a sense of belonging to a specific community (e.g., Berlin) or nation, linked to a sense of duty, solidarity and inclusion (Bonell et al. 2020).

Figure 11. Messages of solidarity and unity in public health campaigns

Another narrative we can observe is that of ‘rebirth’ or ‘restarting life’. These campaigns focus on a positive message of hope that, with the availability of the vaccine, the pandemic will be over and life

Figure 12. ‘Restarting life’ narrative in public health campaigns (ex. Belgium, 12.01.2021)

can go back to normal. These narratives make use of visual puns (like a ‘play button’ that symbolises the ‘restarting’) or religious connotations (‘rebirth’), as well as metaphors (‘rebirth’ after a ‘long dark winter’). One example is the Belgian campaign launched in January 2021 by the Flemish government (see Figure 12). The standard format of all the posters is an individual holding up their sleeve and showing their right upper arm, in which they have received the vaccine. At the spot where they have received the injection, there is a play button. The posters are available with pictures of lots of different individuals. The focus shifted over time: in the beginning, the posters featured more health care workers and elderly people (because they had vaccine priority), and later the campaign broadened in scope. The bottom line of this campaign is that vaccination will allow normal life to re-start. The pause and play buttons are used to visualize this. The campaign aims to convince people that getting vaccinated corresponds to pressing the play button. The slogan is short and catchy, especially because it rhymes. Closely connected to this narrative of ‘rebirth’ are the stylistic elements using ‘esprit’ to communicate the new possibilities and ‘going back to normal’ offered by the vaccines (see below). These narratives could be categorised under what Bonell et al. (2020) call ‘make it possible messages’, i.e. messages that focus on rewards, incentives and enablement rather than punishment, disincentives, or castigation.

Another message we can observe across borders are *public health recommendations and hygiene guidelines*, simply and clearly communicated through straightforward designs and infographics (more detail on the stylistic elements below). These messages are straightforward and usually focus on one or only a few aspects, for example, keep a distance, wear a mask, stay at home.

2.3.2 Stylistic elements in public health campaigns across countries

Across countries, we can observe that – especially at the beginning of the pandemic – messages have been designed in a simple and straightforward way, using simple (often single) messages. Text messages with a single-colour background are an often-used format, sometimes including pictograms. Some examples are included in Figure 13 below. While some of these contain more text and some less, the messages overall are fairly simple and mainly focused on one key message. Some of the images use bright and alerting colours, like the black-and-yellow images used in Belgium, Romania, Sweden, and the UK. Others, like the Austrian and Greek campaigns, use pastel or milder colours, less alerting and more calming.

Figure 13. Simple messages, use of text and colour in public health campaigns across countries

We can also observe the use of infographics to communicate simple hygiene guidelines or other public health recommendations. Some examples are provided in Figure 14 below: often using comic-style drawings or infographics, these images provide varying amount of information: while some of the Greek campaigns simply remind to wash hands, keep a distance, and wear masks, the Romanian campaigns provide very detailed guidance in text and images. These messages are straightforward, simple, yet informative.

Figure 14. Infographics in public health campaigns across countries

With regards to *emotive strategies*, there are several different stylistic strategies applied throughout the campaigns. One example is the use of photos in medical settings, e.g. of healthcare workers. The images included in Figure 15 show vaccinations (Italian vaccination campaigns), as well as a person (most likely a healthcare worker) holding the hands of an older patient.

Figure 15. Use of photos in medical settings in public health campaigns

This is closely related to those campaigns making use of fear and/or guilt as emotive strategies; they depict the consequences of non-compliance with the measures, partially in a medical setting. For example, the image on the left in Figure 16 below shows an Italian campaign, portraying a young girl's face without a mask. The main label stands out on the right-hand side of the image: "Indossare la mascherina o indossare il respiratore?" ("Wearing a mask or wearing a respirator?"). At the bottom, a caption reads "La scelta è tua ma le conseguenze riguardano tutti noi" ("The choice is yours but the consequences affect us all"); the subtitle says "Aiutaci a contenere la diffusione del coronavirus, prima che sia troppo tardi" ("Help us contain the spread of the coronavirus, before it's too late"). The logo of Lombardia region, the email contact and the hashtag of the campaign "TheCovidDilemma" are also indicated. This is exemplary for the use of fear and guilt; the campaigns give an impression of the choice, as well as the consequences of that choice – doing A (e.g., not wearing a mask) equals B (e.g., killing your grandmother).

Figure 16. Use of fear and/or guilt in public health campaigns

While fear appeals have been used frequently in public health campaigns, they are not effective in the long-term process of behaviour change that is usually the goal of public health campaigns (Cho & Salmon 2006).

On the other hand, there is the *use of humour* in information campaigns. We have identified several different approaches. The use of *puns and play on words* is one example. In Figure 17 we can see three examples: the first picture, a campaign by the City of Vienna, shows a woman sitting in a public transport bus. She is wearing a mask and holding a form in her hands. She is getting a vaccination administered by a female Health Care Worker. The text, which is written in white on purple background reads: 'Our joyride continuous. Get vaccinated in the vaccination bus without appointment'. This is a

word play, as the German word for joyride includes parts of the German word for syringe. The second example is the public health campaign by the City of Birmingham: it depicts the local monument, the Bull, and as a play on word, it includes the phrase “It’s no bull!”. ‘Bull’ is short for ‘bullshit’, meaning ‘complete nonsense or something that is not true’. The last picture is another play on words: #YOME VACUNO SEGURO says “I get vaccinated for sure” but also means that the vaccine is completely safe.

Figure 17. Use of puns in public health campaigns

Another element are *rhymes* to design catchy messages (“Use your head, stop the spread”, Birmingham campaign 22.06.2021). Two examples are provided below; both are information campaigns launched by the City of Vienna. The image on the left, showing an upper arm with a band-aid on it, is part of the City of Vienna’s vaccination campaign. It references the previous information campaign, launched by the Austrian federal government, regarding physical distancing rules implemented since the beginning of the pandemic. One of the main messages of public health campaigns was that grandchildren should also keep their distance to their grandparents as these are often those most vulnerable to the virus. Not being able to see older or vulnerable family members for the sake of protecting them became a key message and was also widely discussed and contested. The vaccination campaign suggest that once vaccinated families can come together again and even hug vulnerable and older family members again.

Figure 18. Use of rhymes in public health campaigns

The image on the right is also part of the vaccination campaign, but directed at a younger audience. The shows two hands on a turntable, indicating a DJ at a party. The light is colourful. In red letters, it is written “Alle gehen in den Club” (“everyone goes to the club”). Below, in white letters, there is written “Nur nicht Linus, der glaubt den Fake News” (“Except Linus, he believes in Fake News.”). In German, it is a rhyme following a rhyme scheme typically used by children. This image is part of several similar ones as part of the City of Vienna’s vaccination campaign. This particular image is focused on the misinformation around the vaccines. Context is the “2G” rule established for clubs: only vaccinated or

recovered persons are allowed to visit clubs, tests are not valid. The rhymes used in these two examples, as well as in other campaigns, ensure that messages are light-hearted, fun, and catchy. Other campaigns make use of *dialect words*, thus addressing a specific audience (with the risk of excluding some), creating a sense of belonging.

References to *pop culture* is another approach used in some campaigns. Four distinct examples are shown in Figure 19 below: the first one (from left to right) is part of the City of Vienna's vaccination campaign; it shows a comic-style drawing of a young woman and man dancing next to a mirror light. During the summer months in 2021, the City of Vienna organised parties for young people between 18 and 30 where they could get vaccinated. During these parties, the Johnson & Johnson vaccine was offered due to the fact that only one shot is needed. The text on the image references a popular Austrian song called 'Kabinenparty'.

The second image is part of Berlin's information campaign; it encourages to dance with "nobody" instead of with "somebody" – it is an appeal to celebrate at home alone in order to protect one's own and others. Dancing alone as a cool act of solidarity shown as something fun emphasized by the neon lights in all colours which stand for an inclusive nightlife. The image and text refer to the creative aspects of the Do-it-yourself culture which has a long tradition in Berlin as a famous Party and Festival city as if it were saying: we want you to have fun however for now in a safe way. As the introductory text suggest as some kind of personalized message to people who miss going out: make the best out of it, small changes can help to adjust. Visual puns like the rainbow lights can be an allusion to the LGBTQ movement which is an important part of popular culture in Berlin.

The third image is part of the Portuguese vaccination campaign. This campaign uses the popular video game "Among Us" as a theme. It is possible to see its different characters in space, with the commonly used imagery to represent the COVID-19 virus beside them. The main message reads "The virus is the IMPOSTOR". Below it says "Task: use mask". From top to bottom, left to right, the corners of the image have the Cascais Youth symbol, a department of the City Council responsible for addressing the problems of its younger population; the hashtag #letseliminatecovid; the city's website; and one of the city's symbols. It is a targeted campaign to appeal to a younger demographic; it was part of a face-to-face initiative in middle and high schools in the municipality to address health security measures and promote mental health awareness due to videogames and cyberbullying. The youth's mental health was a concern, after months without social interaction. Acknowledging the dangers of online dependency, these campaigns began with the reopening of schools after easter festivities.

The last image was part of the Swedish vaccination campaign. It was posted on FB and partly communicates using emojis to illustrate that two shots of vaccine makes give a stronger protection. Under the emojis the text goes: "Don't forget! Two doses of vaccine are needed for an efficient and long-lasting protection against covid-19". In the lower right corner of the image, the logo of the VGR is displayed. The text posted on FB together with the image says: "Vaccinate yourself - that's the most important thing you do this summer! Two doses are needed for effective and long-lasting protection against covid-19. Together we stop the pandemic!"

Figure 19. Use of pop cultural references in public health campaigns

Besides these pop culture references, we could also observe references to football, including metaphors (“Abstand ist die beste Verteidigung” (“Distance is the best form of defence”) as a variation of a well-known football metaphor “Angriff ist die beste Verteidigung” (“offence is the best form of defence”) and references to team spirit (“Tu estás em jogo”, a play on words that can mean “You are at stake”, or a football terminology that translates to “You are onside/playing”).

Finally, we have identified the use of *joie de vivre*, particularly (but not exclusively) combined with messages of hope and ‘rebirth’/‘restarting life’. Four examples are provided below (from left to right): the first image is part of the Belgian information campaign launched in September 2021, entitled ‘enjoy your freedom’. The campaign shows people to be having fun in different settings – at a fairground in the image below, and at weddings and dinners with friends in other posters. The two main messages of the campaign are (i) to continue to keep distance, and (ii) to ensure good ventilation. The promise of the campaign is that people live up to these rules, the COVID numbers will stay low and restrictive measures won’t be necessary. This is referred to as a ‘win-win’ scenario.

The second image is part of a Portuguese campaign, showing happy young people wearing masks, in a celebration. The text on the image reads “It is not yet time for parties! Have fun in safety”. In the blue box, one can read “Give it time! Follow DGS’s (the government health authority) recommendations.”. Launched in summer 2020, there were still restrictions and measures in place to prevent the spread of the infection; including rules in beaches, summer festivals cancelled, the recommendation to stay in the country for the holidays, etc. One demographic that was subject to preoccupation was the youth. Targeted in campaigns such as this one, teenagers and young adults were alerted to follow the rules and avoid large gatherings.

The third image is part of a campaign connected to the World Health Day in April 2021. It claims that ‘another world is possible’; that those most affected by COVID-19 have been the people with the lowest living conditions and worst working conditions. The text on the image reads: “building a better and healthier world”.

The fourth image is an example from Greece; it shows four joyful individuals, two male and two female citizens in an orange-coloured background. The caption reads as: “Get Vaccinated, get liberated, enjoy LIFE”.

Figure 20. Use of *joie de vivre* in public health campaigns

2.3.3 Representation in public health campaigns across countries

Overall, we can observe that, particularly at the beginning of the pandemic, campaigns were focused on communicating clear messages to a broad audience, targeting the general public rather than specific groups. These messages were designed inclusively in the sense that the majority of the campaigns used text rather than potentially exclusive images or photos.

We can also observe inclusive design in the sense of including persons of different age, gender, and ethnicity in several campaigns, both in the use of photos and in the use of infographics. Some examples are provided in Figure 21 below.

Figure 21. Inclusive design in public health campaigns

Particularly at a later stage of the pandemic, we can observe that campaigns become more targeted, addressing, for example, older persons (as a group that was prioritised across Europe to get vaccinated) as well as young people (as a group that was heavily impacted due to school closings), or migrants.

2.4 Conclusions

Regarding RQ1, we have found that there are two main topics of communication: (i) public health recommendations and hygiene guidelines, including both personal preventive measures and general advice, and (ii) (motivating) information about vaccines and the vaccination campaigns. While the former is mainly addressed at the general public, with some exceptions where campaigns are targeted at younger audiences, the latter are more targeted, following the logic of prioritisation. Within the limited sample of public health campaigns analysed in this chapter, we could observe only individual campaigns tailoring messages to specific sub-groups based on gender, age, regional, ethnic or cultural affiliations, as recommended by Bonell et al. (2020). Such tailored campaigns usually address either older persons or young persons, the former as the most vulnerable group, as well as the group prioritised for vaccinations, the latter as a group that has been impacted drastically and whose cooperation was needed to keep numbers low. We have also identified individual campaigns addressing migrants.

To answer RQ2, we can observe the use of certain narratives, first and foremost one of unity and solidarity. Rooted in the psychology of social identity, social influence, and moral behaviour, such narratives of solidarity stress desired behaviour and how they benefit the most vulnerable members of society (Bonell et al. 2020). At times, these messages are enforced by using emotive strategies addressing fear and guilt, others focus on positive messages. There is also a narrative of hope, of rebirth and restarting life, that accompanies some of the vaccination campaigns.

In terms of their design, answering RQ3, we can observe inclusive design in some campaigns regarding representation of persons of different age, gender, and ethnicity, yet we still can observe a focus on the (white) majority population. We have to point out, however, that certain campaigns, launched in languages other than the national language, were not included in this analysis.

Regarding RQ4, we have identified the use of several stylistic elements. While at the beginning of the pandemic, messages were communicated in a serious and straightforward way, at a later stage of the pandemic humour was used, for example in the form of puns and play on words, rhymes, or dialect words. References to pop culture can also be observed, as well as addressing *joie de vivre*. We can also observe the use of emotive strategies, particularly leveraging fear and guilt. These usually include images of healthcare workers or some sort of medical setting. Interestingly, within our sample, this kind of images were not widely used; other research has shown greater engagement with such images (Malik, Khan & Quan-Haase 2021).

3 Humour as a coping mechanism: memes

This chapter presents outcomes of an analysis of memes which had the aim to gain an understanding how humour was used to cope with the events of the pandemic and communicate with others. Following Shifman (2014), memes can be defined as “(a) a group of digital items sharing common characteristics of content, form, and/or stance, which (b) were created with awareness of each other, and (c) were circulated, imitated and/or transformed via the Internet y many users.” (p. 41) The term is commonly used to describe the propagation of jokes, rumours, videos and the like via the internet, thus being closely connected to Darwin’s initial idea of describing small units of culture spreading from person to person by copying or imitation (ibid.).

We analyse internet memes because humour is a powerful coping mechanism and can give valuable insights into the situation of members within a society. During the pandemic, researchers could observe the production and sharing of COVID-19 related memes (Kuipers 2020). Humour can lower the degree of negative emotions such as stress and hopelessness surrounding the pandemic (Olah & Ford 2021). Memes are often used to comment on current issues; they “facilitate discursive exchanges about events within society and criticism of these events” (Pauliks 2020, 47).

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused several domains of stress: bodily (such as physical health concerns), interpersonal (such as isolation, concerns for family members), cognitive (processing frightening information), behavioural, economic, and politics (Olah & Ford 2021; Schimmenti et al. 2020).

We have analysed memes, focusing on aspects such as ideology, misinformation, humour as a coping mechanism, etc. The main research questions (RQs) are:

- RQ1: What were the dominant narratives in the memes?
- RQ2: On what (e.g., COVID-19 measures or impacts) and who (e.g., politicians, services, residents) do memes in the different countries under research focus? What situations are captured?
- RQ3: How are aspects of vulnerability discussed within memes (e.g., mental health issues, loneliness)?

3.1 Methodology

The task of collecting and analysing memes was organised in an explorative way. While the task leader provided general recommendations for search strategies and regularly discussed the search with partners, partners individually decided which keywords and channels to use, due to the country-specific nature of the search. The majority of the partners made use of a combination of search via keywords and identification of specific channels (e.g., country-specific sub-Reddits¹, Facebook, Instagram or Twitter pages with many followers, meme-sharing sites such as Imgur or 9gag, etc.). This resulted in a sample of 668 memes collected between the beginning of 2020 and autumn 2021 within the ten countries of analysis, as can be seen in Table 1 below.

¹ i.e., dedicated national channels of the social media platform Reddit.

Table 1. Overview of number of memes collected per country

Austria	Belgium	Germany	Greece	Italy	Portugal	Romania	Spain	Sweden	UK	Total
275	36	38	11	62	76	10	70	35	55	668

The images were coded inductively, according to the explorative approach, creating categories through identifying themes within the data set. Partners provided a translation where applicable, as well as a description of the context of each image, following the logic of Panofsky's iconographic-iconological method.

Due to the diversity of the sample, as well as the differences in numbers of memes collected per country, we conducted a high-level analysis that does not claim representability. The type of images included may not only be caused by country-specific characteristics but also by the search strategies applied. As such, while providing some insights in how humour was used to cope with the pandemic situation, this analysis provides an exploration of the topic.

3.2 Country analyses

The following chapter provides insights per country under analysis.

3.2.1 Austria

The Austrian sample included a total of 275 images between the beginning of the pandemic and December 2021. We have coded the following categories: *Everyday life during the pandemic*, *Commentary / criticism of measures*, *social criticism*, *Criticism of politicians / the government*, *Gallows humour / fatalism / defeatism*, *Commentary on vaccination strategy*, *Social tensions*, *Everyday political news*, *Anti anti-vax movement*, and *Anti-vax movement / fighting measures*. Within this sample, by far the biggest category of memes *commented or criticised the Austrian federal government*, as well as individual politicians. This commentary or criticism is multifaceted; for example, some memes comment on a perceived skewed prioritisation of measures (for example, how tourism/keeping ski resorts open or the economy seemingly were prioritised over stricter measures), while others commented on the crisis communication of the government, particularly the tendency to hold press

Österreich: Können wir bitte endlich ein
gscheites Krisenmanagement haben!

Die Bundesregierung:

Figure 22. Criticism of government 1 | Austria

conferences. One example is Figure 22 below: the text above the image says: "Austria: could we please just have a proper crisis management! – the federal government: best I can do is press conferences". The faces of minister of health (at the time), Rudolf Anschober, and chancellor (at the time) Sebastian Kurz are photoshopped onto the two persons portrayed in the image. Similarly, the (at times) overly complicated communication of measures, and the tendency to announce measures in press conferences are commented (and criticised), as well as a lack of dialogue with the general public. There are also memes commenting on the inadequate communication to migrants and other vulnerable groups. Furthermore, similar to commenting the

overabundance of press conferences, there are memes commenting on ‘self-praise’ of individual politicians, particularly former chancellor Sebastian Kurz.

One example is Figure 23: in a well-known meme format using the ‘Drake meme’, i.e. screenshots of the Drake song ‘Hotline Bling’, Sebastian Kurz is portrayed on two pictures. In the first he holds up his hand in a gesture of rejection next to the text “spend more than €200 Mio to have enough vaccines”, in the second he smiles, accompanied by the text “spend more than €200 Mio for self-promotion and PR”. This is one among several memes commenting on a perceived self-promotion that seemed to be more important than ‘proper’ crisis management. Indeed, there are several memes commenting on the governments’ poor crisis management, addressing difficulties or the overall performance of the federal government.

Figure 23. Criticism of government 2 | Austria

As can be seen in Figure 24, the crisis management of the government is symbolised by a stairway that seemingly leads nowhere; the text above the image says “the corona strategy of the Austrian government (illustrated)”. Besides the overall crisis management, the slow development of some measures (such as the ‘Green Pass’), or the slow reaction times until measures were defined (perceived as the government waiting and observing the situation rather than acting), are commented

Figure 24. Criticism of government 3 | Austria

in several memes. Perceived incompetence of individual politicians, the federal government, or local governments are also addressed in some memes; for example, minister of education (at the time) Heinz Fassmann, whose lack of addressing urgent issues regarding schools and universities was commented regularly through memes. Indeed, several memes address a perceived failure of taking into account school and university students’ situations. Furthermore, some memes address some politician’s or the whole government’s perceived lack of taking responsibility, e.g. for hick-ups in the organisation of the vaccination programme. Others comment on the non-compliance of some politicians with the measures, and the bad example they are setting. Inner-governmental conflicts and their impact on the crisis management, as well as the lack of trustworthiness for announced measures (that may be changed or modified) are also commented.

In addition, we identified memes *commenting or criticising measures*, particularly measures perceived as absurd, contradicting, or irrational such as the exception of gun shops allowed to open during a ‘soft lockdown’, or the change of the safety distance from 2 to 1 meter and the consequent ‘shrinking’ of the ‘baby elephant’ as symbol for the distance. This also included commentary on the unfairness of some measures, and the impossibility to follow some measure in specific jobs. Further commented are confusing measures, often caused by the modification of previous policies, and overly complicated measures. One example is provided in Figure 25: in three screenshots of a scene in *The Lord of the Rings. The Fellowship of the Ring*, the text captions state Pippin saying: “Do you already know the new corona rules for new years?” to which Aragon says: “They are known already for a week.” Pippin replies: “These are the old new rules. I mean the new new rules.” This kind of criticism is also connected to the federal system of Austria, which means that local governments implemented varying measures and regulations at times. Several memes commented on this issue. Similarly, the uncertainty of upcoming measures, often caused by their late announcement, was addressed in several memes, as was the unexpectedness of some measures (particularly the announcement of further lockdowns in winter 2020/2021). Further, the government’s tendency to announce measures bit by bit was included. Neologisms like ‘easter rest’ instead of ‘lockdown’ were also addressed.

Figure 25. Criticism of measures 1 | Austria

Figure 26. Criticism of measures 2 | Austria

Two measures in particular, the corona traffic light and the Green Pass are commented regularly. One example is Figure 26: the image lists the four colours of the corona traffic light, which was planned as an indicator for specific measures, depending on the epidemiological situation. Due to a lot of exceptions and changes, the system initially caused more confusion than clarity. This is reflected in the image: the measures commented next to the colours are described as follows: (green) take care a little bit, (yellow) well, take care a bit more, (orange) ?????, (red) lockdown. Not only these but also other measures’ perceived ineffectiveness is addressed through memes in the Austrian sample.

Besides this commentary on measures, we could also observe *social criticism*, i.e. commentary on the behaviour of other members of society. This ranged from hoarding of toilet paper and other goods, widely observe before the first lockdown – not only in Austria but across the world – to a lack of compliance with measures (e.g., wearing masks) and other unreasonable or even antisocial behaviour. The carelessness of some persons during the pandemic as also addressed. Further discussed was the fact that some politicians ‘cut the line’ in getting vaccinated, not following the order of prioritisation. Skiing and the overall situation in Ischgl, one of the hotspots of the pandemic in Europe both in 2020 and 2021, was addressed with several memes. Further, the motivation for getting vaccinated – to be able to go to bars rather than to protect others – was a topic in several memes. The anti-vax movement was addressed in particular, including the recommendations by one Austrian politician to use an anthelmintic drug to fight infections with COVID-19, as well as gleeful comments on this politician’s COVID-19 infection. One example is Figure 27, showing a man with a smug smiley. The text says (in dialect): “You can’t catch corona if you die from taking horse anthelmintic”. Similar to this is the category of *social tensions*, addressing the tensions within a family or between friends if there are differentiating opinions on the vaccination.

Figure 27. Social criticism | Austria

Opposed to this are memes that criticise the vaccines; very often, these include comparisons to the holocaust and Nazi Germany. Particularly with the announcement of compulsory COVID-19 vaccinations (foreseen for February 2022), this kind of memes were used to criticise the government measures, addressing the feeling of exclusion and oppression.

We also identified memes falling under the category *gallows humour*; these memes jokingly comment on the fears due to an uncertain outlook of the pandemic or the implemented measures. This may include the uncertainty of the duration of the pandemic, new variants/mutations of the virus, or the ineffectiveness of measures, as demonstrated in Figure 28: a man, titled “5 days of easter rest” throws a bucket of water on a roaring fire, clearly without any effect. The fire is titled “raising infection numbers”.

Figure 28. Gallows humour | Austria

Finally, the vaccination was addressed in several memes, including the lack of available vaccines in the beginning of 2021, and the slow progress of the vaccination programme, as well as the prioritisation of vaccines (particularly, the bad press the AstraZeneca vaccine received).

3.2.2 Belgium

The Belgian sample included a total of 36 images collected between the beginning of the pandemic and autumn 2021. We have coded the following categories: *Compliance with measures*, *Societal behaviour / social criticism*, *Behaviour changes during the pandemic / due to the measures*, *Feeling of uncertainty & isolation*, *Unfamiliarity of measures / coping mechanism*, *Conspiracy*, *Defeatism / fatalism / gallows humour*, *Social tensions*, *Economic aspects*, *Hopefulness*, *Restrictions*, and *Criticism of measures*. The memes analysed in the context of Belgium address various different aspects. Several memes tackle the issue of *compliance with regulations* such as staying at home or physical distancing. We also observe discussions of everyday life during the pandemic. An example is provided in Figure 29: the text says ‘When your hairdresser is closed, but the dog groomer who is working from home is still available’, with a picture of a young man with a peculiar (poodle-like) hairstyle. This refers to the closure of hairdressers (and other services) during lockdown, and alternative ways to get a haircut.

Figure 29. Everyday life during the pandemic | Belgium

Such memes may be used as a coping mechanism, addressing difficulties, other even address the impossibility to comply for some professions: for example, physical distancing is not possible for services that require physical contact. Others comment the luxury of owning a garden during times of lockdown, i.e. the social inequalities in the availability of space.

Other memes within this category point at options to ‘escape’ or find a way out of restrictions; for example, holding an empty coffee cup so to avoid wearing a mask for a while, or going for a walk with a turtle (instead of a dog, which was one of the exceptions for going outside during lockdown in Belgium).

Another category of memes address behaviour of people during the pandemic in the form of *social criticism*. On the one hand, this tackles the issue of non-compliance (by other members of society). One example is Figure 30: using screenshots of the TV sitcom ‘Friends’, Phoebe says ‘stay at home’, while Joey repeats ‘go to the coast’. This refers to the first lockdown in March 2020, when many Belgians went to the coast or other outdoor/nature areas, despite stay-at-home orders, and these places often became very crowded. Another example are memes addressing hoarding (e.g., of toilet paper), which were mainly shared at the beginning of the pandemic.

Figure 30. Social criticism | Belgium

As part of a coping strategy to deal with the unfamiliar situation, some memes address the *behavioural changes* during the pandemic, particularly the increase in people (suddenly) getting engaged in sportive activities, particularly sports that can be carried out in the own home (e.g., yoga). Others address the *unfamiliarity of the measures*, such as wearing masks or physical distancing.

The *feeling of uncertainty and isolation* is also addressed in memes, for example in commenting on the

Figure 31. Feeling of uncertainty | Belgium

(unknown) duration of the pandemic and the implemented measures, as well as the uncertainties of possible upcoming measures, and the unpredictability of the situation. One example is provided in Figure 31 below: the image shows child, an older couple (most likely grandparents) and a mom 'after the quarantine'. The grandmother says: 'Lovely that we finally could come for a post-natal visit. How old is he now?'. The mom replies: '122 months'. The meme refers to how visits, especially by older people, are being discouraged during the lockdown. It suggests that the lockdown might continue for a long time (i.e., addressing a feeling of uncertainty when the lockdown might end), and children will grow up before seeing their grandparents.

A similar category of memes addresses *social tensions*, either caused by the measures such as lockdowns (e.g., between spouses confined in a small apartment, particularly when working from home), by the pandemic itself (e.g., how sneezing and coughing in public suddenly became an issue), or by the worsening of social tensions that existed before the pandemic (e.g., between family members).

Defeatism and gallows humour are another coping strategy to address the unfamiliar and frightening situation. Memes in this category address the situation with exaggeration, as can be seen in Figure 32: the image says 'Highlight the disastrous part of 2020', written above an image of someone who is highlighting entire pages. 2020 has been perceived as a disastrous year for many, with few positive periods. Another example is an image showing a dinosaur with short arms and reads 'couldn't wash his hands, now he's gone extinct', exaggerating the consequences of non-compliance in a fatalist way. Another meme comments the appearance of new mutations or variants of the virus.

Figure 32. Gallows humour | Belgium

Contrary to this, there are memes transporting a *message of hopefulness*, e.g. when the hospitality sector reopened in Belgium, while other comment on the current situation, e.g. restrictions, and even *criticise measures* such as the restriction that four people were allowed to meet in the garden, but only one contact (the knuffelcontact, i.e. 'cuddle contact' or close contact) was allowed to go to the toilet.

There is also a commentary on the *economic situation*, addressing the closing of shops and consequent shift to online shopping. On the other side of the coin, the re-opening of the hospitality sector may 'bankrupt' persons and put them in need for support measures due to overspending in restaurants.

Within the sample, there was also a meme addressing the suspected origin of the virus in Wuhan.

3.2.3 Germany

The German sample of 38 memes contained a variety of topics that were addressed. We have coded the following categories: *Anti-vax movement*, *Opposition to measures*, *Commenting / criticising politicians / the government*, *Commenting / criticising measures*, *Compliance with measures*, *Defeatism / fatalism / gallows humour*, *Social criticism* and *Comment on everyday political events*. One important category is that of *anti-vaccination memes*. This can be communicated in the form of heroization of unvaccinated persons, as well as in addressing the experienced peer pressure of getting vaccinated, particularly due to measures that restrict access to services and facilities. There are also memes containing criticism of the scientific community and doctors. Others draw comparisons to Nazi Germany and the ‘corona dictatorship’, particularly in the context of compulsory vaccinations. In this context, victimisation is also used. Finally, the effectiveness of the vaccines is questioned, as shown in Figure 33: it depicts a conversation between a patient and a doctor, as follows:

Figure 33. Anti-vaccination memes | Germany

Patient: I am finally immune against corona. Great!

Doctor: No, no, you can still get infected.

Patient: What?! But I am allowed to take off my mask!

Doctor: NO!

Patient: Oh. My family is also getting vaccinated. Do the manufacturers take responsibility if I suffer from side effects such as facial paralysis or if my child or my mother dies from it?

Doctor: No.

Patient: Then why are we doing this?

Doctor: I don't know. The media wants this and the government says we should show solidarity. I'm just doing my job. I'm not here to think, ok? Keep calm.

This meme reflects the ongoing discussion about the vaccination rates, while at the same time repeating misinformation about the vaccines regarding its side effects, as well as its supposed ineffectiveness.

Similar to these anti-vaccination memes are those *opposing the measures*, criticising masks and the “2G”² measures. Within this category, we also summarised memes opposing the so-called ‘corona dictatorship’, as well as those downplaying or denying the pandemic. Memes within this category express superiority above those following measures; they further create a sense of ‘us against ‘others. One example is provided in Figure 34: the image depicts Daenerys Targaryen, a character from the TV show “Game of Thrones”. She is holding a cigarette in her hand and

Figure 34. Opposing measures | Germany

² 2G means that only persons who are vaccinated (“geimpft”) and recovered (“geheilt”) are allowed to enter certain areas (e.g., bars, restaurants); it is a stricter measure than the initially implemented “3G” rule, which included tested (“getestet”).

laughing; the text reads “Just exclude us. We do not want to be members of such a totalitarian society. We are becoming more and more.” There is also a meme addressing measures that are seen as exaggerated.

Distinct from this category are memes that *comment or criticise measures*, for example a lack of proper infrastructure for vaccinations, the failure to address the needs of young people, or the exaggeration of some measures. Similar to this are memes that *comment or criticise individual politicians or the government*, particularly the poor corona management as well as shortages of vaccines and masks. One example is provided in Figure 35: a man, labelled “German politician” is staring at a woman’s chest. The woman’s face is labelled “Come up with proper measures”, while the woman’s chest is labelled “lockdown no. 24”. Incompetence, either of public health organisations like the Robert Koch Institute, as well as of individual politicians, are also addressed.

Figure 35. Criticism of politicians | Germany

Finally, we have identified memes that *criticise social behaviour*, such as hoarding of toilet paper.

3.2.4 Greece

The Greek sample was rather limited and included eleven images. We have coded the following categories: *Social tensions*, *Criticism of measures*, *Societal behaviour / social criticism*, *Compliance with measures*, and *Feeling of relief*. Within this sample, there are memes *criticising measures* such as the

Figure 36. Social criticism 1 | Greece

effectiveness of masks, as well as their costs (“When you have paid 35€ for two masks and find out that they do not protect you”). Others can be interpreted as *social criticism*, addressing various issues – from toilet paper shortage to following everyday measures such as mask mandates to the anti-vaxx movement. One example is Figure 36: the image shows a pack of toilet paper and a building owned by Amazon. The text above those pictures says “BREAKING NEWS Softex buys Amazon”. This is a comment on the (worldwide) behaviour of hoarding toilet paper in the initial phase of the pandemic. The meme also comments on the increase of prices (and subsequent economic success of the

companies providing these goods). Another example is provided in Figure 37, which is a comment on the differentiation between vaccinated and unvaccinated persons, making fun of the unvaccinated who were prohibited from going to the shops. The text on the image says “Unvaccinated people during winter outside stores”, above a picture of a woman pressing her hands against a window. In the window, we can see the reflection of a smiling woman. This meme is a reaction to the attempts of the Greek government to increase vaccination rates by prohibiting certain activities for

Figure 37. Social criticism 2 | Greece

unvaccinated persons. Another meme comments on the restrictions that prevent people from celebrating Easter, and the attempts to spend this important holiday in one's village.

Similarly, another meme comments on the *social tensions* caused by the pandemic, particularly the

Figure 38. Everyday life with the measures | Greece

fear of coughing in public and the feeling of insecurity. A commentary on the everyday life with the measures is shown in Figure 38: a man with a smug smile, tipping his finger to his head, is accompanied by a text that reads "Wearing double mask at the gym is not bothering if you are not going to the gym". Posted in May 2021, when first restrictions were lifted, this image reacts to the government's recommendation to wear double masks at the gym.

The sample also included a meme commenting on the *feeling of relief* when a test turned out negative.

3.2.5 Italy

The Italian sample contained a total of 62 individual images, commenting on several aspects of the pandemic situation, including: *Societal behaviour / social criticism*, *Criticism of measures*, *Defeatism / fatalism / gallows humour*, *Compliance with measures*, *Criticism of politics / the government*, and *Hopefulness*. As one of the most coded categories, we can see memes addressing the behaviour of other members of society in the form of *social criticism*. These comment on a variety of aspects; for

example, unreasonable behaviour by the population (e.g., going to the supermarket at 23.31, against the recommendation by the government) as well as non-compliance with measures, including excuses and loopholes for non-compliance. One example is Figure 39: the image shows Paris Hilton, Britney Spears and Lindsey Lohan smiling at each other, all located in a car. Britney asks "But where are we going?", to which Paris replies "to a private family party".

Posted in April 2020, this meme addresses the restrictions around Easter, and the non-compliance by the public,

Figure 39. Social criticism | Italy

symbolised by Paris Hilton, Britney Spears and Lindsey Lohan who were famous for partying in the early 2000. Besides non-compliance with measures and restrictions, other memes within this category address shortages (e.g., due to toilet paper hoarding), as well as vaccinations. For the latter, memes comment both the reasons to get vaccinated (e.g., to visit bars and restaurants, instead of to protect others), as well as the anti-vaxx ('novax') movement, including the restriction unvaccinated persons have to face.

Other memes *comment or criticise measures* and restrictions. The auto-certification required during the first lockdown – a certificate that declared the reasons for movement – was commented by several memes, particularly the regular updates and modifications of the document. This comment on

Figure 40. Criticism of measures | Italy

modification is also commented on the level of decrees, causing confusion and doubts about constantly changing rules. One example is Figure 40: the image shows the former Head of Government, Giuseppe Conte, saying: “I see you bored, I almost make you print a new self-certification”. Posted on 2 April 2020, this meme reflects on a time where the entire country was in quarantine. During this time, the government limited any kind of movement; the abovementioned self-certification justifying the reason of movement was mandatory and modified regularly. The difficulty to distinguish between these auto-certification documents, as well as measures or ‘phases’ of measures is commented in several memes. There is also commentary on the strictness of measures, considered exaggerated at times, as well as the absurdity of some measures

(e.g., compulsory masks outdoors between 6 pm and 6 am, or the impossibility to leaving ones how without violating containment measures). Others comment the monitoring of compliance by the police and other members of society, as well as the restrictions imposed by restrictions such as curfews.

A similar, yet distinct category are memes *commenting or criticising politicians or the government*. This includes comments on the Italian government’s crisis communication and overload of press conferences (comparing them to a soap opera), as well as a certain detachment from reality (with a meme using screenshots from the film “Marie Antoinette”).

We can also observe memes that fall under the category *fatalism / gallows humour*, commenting either the current situation or address the uncertainty of the future. As such, memes under this category are posted throughout the pandemic due to its long duration and reoccurring waves. Figure 41 provides a good example of this category: the image shows a map of the ancient Roman Empire, with the caption “if we continue to cough, we will get back the whole Roman Empire”. Posted in the beginning of March 2020, the pandemic was spreading fast in Italy. Within this category, we can also find memes that portray *defeatism*, portraying how people have giving up on excitement during the lockdowns, particularly referencing the long duration of the pandemic. One meme jokingly foresees new disasters – under the caption “In April, everything will be better”, an image of Godzilla leaving the ocean is portrayed.

Se avanziamo a colpi di tosse
ci riprendiamo tutto l’Impero
Romano

Figure 41. Gallows humour | Italy

3.2.6 Portugal

The Portuguese sample included 77 memes. The memes cover the following categories: *Novelty of the virus*, *Compliance with measures*, *Public health advise*, *Societal behaviour / social criticism*, *Defeatism / gallus humour*, *Solidarity*, *Criticism of measures*, *Criticism of politics / politicians*, *Economic dimensions*, *Social tension*, *Hopefulness*. The most used categories were *Compliance with measures* and *societal behaviour*. In the categories *Compliance with measures* the main themes were coping with the reality of life under COVID-19, the struggles of life under lockdown and restrictions, ways to get around complying with measures, and making fun of unreasonable behaviour. For example, Figure 42 shows a man at home during lockdown who pretends his bathtub is the public transport he uses for his daily commute. This meme is a comment on how residents are advised to follow the lockdown order but also keep up their daily routines.

Figure 42. Compliance with measures | Portugal

In the category *Societal behaviour / social criticism* we have found memes commenting on supply shortages, non-compliances with measures, unreasonable or unsocial behaviour as well as anti-vaxxer sentiments. The meme exemplified here is specific to the Portuguese context. It shows the Portuguese football player Cristiano Ronaldo. The texts

Figure 43. Social criticism | Portugal

says, “So what about me, I can’t play football just because there are people dying”. The meme critiques Ronaldo’s reaction to testing positive for COVID-19 in October 2020. While addressing the media, he described the PCR test as “uma treta”, a softer version in Portuguese of the expression “bullshit”. People reacted with concern to his demeanour towards his diagnosis, criticizing his possible misinformation attempt.

The third most used category in Portugal is *Defeatism and gallows humour*. The themes here are: the current situation in Portugal as well as other countries, vaccine and new variants. Figure 44 shows an image of “Correio da Manhã” (a Portuguese cable news channel) news report. The prime minister, António Costa, is seen speaking in parliament. The footer information spells “Hairdressers will reopen”. Costa has his head photoshopped, making his hair look unkempt. The meme plays on the government order to reopen some services, such as hair dressers, in the beginning of May 2020. The prime minister’s unkempt and longish hair indicate that hair dressers were allowed to open because the prime minister needed a haircut.

Figure 44. Gallows humour | Portugal

Figure 45. Novelty of the virus | Portugal

There are more country specific memes. For example, in the category *Novelty of the virus* is a meme drawing parallels between the COVID-19 coverage and the coverage of the bushfires in summer 2021 and how both were heavily reported over. The description on the boat says: “Journalists without wildfires to talk about”.

3.2.7 Romania

The Romanian partners submitted 10 memes for analysis. In Romania we identified three categories overall. These are: *Compliance with measures*, *Criticism of measures* as well as *Conspiracy theories*. The majority of memes were coded to *Compliance with measures*. Within this category the themes discussed are coping mechanisms, everyday life and struggles with everyday life during the pandemic as well as ways to get around complying with measures.

The following meme (Figure 46) shows the Romanian national football team. The text on top of the picture saying “Respect for the boys, they stay home since 1996. This is prevention!” On the picture there is a question – European or World series? And on the bottom the call for action “We stay home!”. The meme is mocking the lack of success of the national team as they did not qualify for the final tournaments and as a consequence had to stay at home just like the rest of the country during lockdown and quarantine.

Figure 46. Compliance with measures 1 | Romania

Another example within the same category is less country specific. Figure 47 shows a dog opening a door and talking to its owner. The dog says: ‘Do you want me to walk you out?’.

Figure 47. Compliance with measures 2 | Romania

The image is a parody of the lockdown exemptions to leave your house as one of these was walking your dog.

One example for a meme found in the category *Criticism of measures* shows a famous Romanian journalist and politics specialist – Cristian Tudor Popescu. The text says: “This is a microscope image of the Coronavirus jumping on you when you leave the house”. Cristian Tudor Popescu is heavily involved in the COVID-19 media coverage and a continuous observer of the current situation.

The category *Conspiracy theory* contains, for example, the following meme (figure x) displaying several people transmitting ultrasounds and the text says – “when 5G towers infect you with COVID-19 you start spreading your own wifi”.

One of the myths spread by conspiracy theorist is that the electromagnetic waves emitted by the 5G towers are making the public more vulnerable to the virus. Signals coming from these towers were believed to cause transmission of COVID-19. This would lead to the implantation of a ‘Body Area Network’.

Figure 48. Conspiracy theory | Romania

3.2.8 Spain

Spain submitted 70 memes. The main categories we coded are: *Societal behaviour / social criticism*, *Anti anti-vaxxer sentiments*, *Societal behaviour / social criticism*, *Defeatism / fatalism*, *Public health advise*, *Criticism of measures*, *Compliance with measures*, *Criticism of politics / politicians / the government*, *Criticism of doctors / medical diagnoses*, *Addressing misinformation*, *Anti-vaxxer sentiments*, *Economic aspects*, *Social tensions*, *Origin of the virus / conspiracy*. The categories we most coded to were *Anti-vaxxer movement*, *Compliance with measures*, *Criticism of politics/ politicians/ government and Societal behaviour / social criticism*

In the category *Anti anti-vaxxer sentiments* we found critical comments as well as mockery of the anti-vaxxer movement. The meme shows a person dressed for a party sitting in a cab. Their face shows annoyance and discontent. The text reads: “Antivaccine people going home at 22:00 because they can’t get in anywhere”. The meme comments on the mandatory vaccination to be able to enter entertainment venues, discos or bars in Spain.

Figure 49. Anti-vaxxer sentiments | Spain

In *Compliance with measures* the themes we could identify were coping mechanism / making fun of the current situation, (struggles of the)

Figure 50. Compliance with measures | Spain

everyday life during the pandemic, unreasonable or inconsequent measures and vaccination. Figure 50 shows Mafalda, a famous Argentinian comic figure. The character is looking sad and bored. Mafalda says: “Weekend Cruise! I cross to the kitchen, cross to the living room, cross to my room, and so on...” The joke refers to the period of lockdown and house confinement, which was strict and long in Spain. People, unable to go out, wandered around the house, trying to walk around and entertain themselves in some way.

In the category *Criticism of politics/ politicians/ government* we could identify some reoccurring themes. These are: unreasonable / unsocial measures, incompetence, government communication, anti-government. For example, the following meme shows a Chinese “fortune cookie”. The message says: “You do not have coronavirus.” But it is written with the spoken accent of a Chinese pronouncing Spanish, where the R’s are pronounced like L’s. That is, instead of “having” (to have) it is written “tenel”, and instead of “coronavirus”, it is written “colonavilus”. At the top the text says: “The Chinese tests that the government bought arrived”. This meme insinuates that antigen tests produced in China are not effective in identifying infections. The debate was triggered by the government’s decision to introduce rapid COVID-19 tests and expresses scientism over the usefulness of anti-gen rapid testing in general.

Figure 51. Criticism of politics & the government | Spain

In the category *Societal behaviour / social criticism* we could

Figure 52. Social criticism | Spain

identified the following themes:

hoarding, unreasonable or unsocial behaviour, polarization, non-compliance with measures. The meme below mocking hoarding behaviour. Hoarding was a phenomenon that occurred particularly often at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic. Figure 52 shows a woman queuing at the supermarket to pay for her groceries. She has bought a huge volume of groceries. The text of the image reads: “Today in Mega-structures: this woman’s refrigerator” (text not visible in the picture). Mega-structures is the title of a well-known TV program in Spain in which they talk about big engineering works and big buildings. The joke refers to the size of the fridge that would be needed to store the amount of food the women purchased.

3.2.9 Sweden

We received and analysed 35 memes from the Swedish context. The categories we identified for the Swedish memes are: *Compliance with measures*, *Criticism of politics / politicians / the government*, *Criticism of measures & strategy*, *Societal behaviour / social criticism*, *Criticism of experts*, *Social criticism in relation to the anti-vaxxer movement*, *Criticism of vaccination campaign* and *Anti- vaxxer sentiments*. The most memes were coded to *Criticism of politics/politicians/ government*, *Criticism of measures & strategy* as well as *Compliance with measures*. Interesting is that many of the memes are very specific to the Swedish context and the so-called ‘Swedish solution’.

We identified the following themes within the category *Criticism of politics / politicians / the government*: commentary on the effectiveness of measures & communication, the (lack of) crisis communication, a feeling of uncertainty, as well as perceived incompetence

Figure 53. Criticism of politics | Sweden

of politicians or the government, and a failure to follow measures / recommendations by politicians. The following meme speaks to multiple of these themes. In the meme a child is sitting in the back of a car saying to chief epidemiologist Anders Tegnell, who is driving, “Put the safety belt on” and he replies “The answer is no. Studies have shown that they only make a difference when you actually are in a car crash – which we are not. This conclusion might be re-evaluated”. The meme hints on the Swedish authorities’ lack of recommendation to use face mask. The government waited until the middle of the second wave to introduce mask wearing. Their handling of this was widely discussed and criticised.

Folkhälsomyndigheten making face masks optional in Sweden

Figure 54. Criticism of measures | Sweden

this meme uses a picture from the Simpsons. Principal Skinner first says “Are we acting so irresponsibly?” and in the next picture he says “No, it is Europe that is wrong”. The headline says “Folkhälsomyndigheten making face masks optional in Sweden”. Folkhälsomyndigheten is the Swedish Health Agency. The context to the meme is substantial critique on the so-called Swedish strategy. In particular, Sweden was at the time one of the few countries in the world who did not recommend face masks.

Finally, the category *Compliance with measures* contains the following themes: memes are used as a coping mechanism in making fun of the current situation, others comment on the (struggles of the) everyday life during the pandemic, and others are coded under the category self-mockery. Many of the memes in this category are a mockery on the stereotypes that Swedes are shy, avoid crowds and like to keep to themselves which comes in handy during the pandemic as social distancing is effective in stopping the spread of COVID-19. The following meme (Figure 55) is a good example of this. Two identical images showing people waiting for the bus, before and after the COVID-19 crisis. The joke refers to the distance that people keep to each other while waiting for the bus. The picture insinuates that in Sweden the distance was quite huge even prior to COVID-19.

Figure 55. Compliance with measures | Sweden

3.2.10UK

We received 55 memes from the UK. *Compliance with measures, News-related, Anti-vaxxer sentiments, Social criticism, Criticism of politics / politicians / the government, gallows humour fatalism, Conspiracy theories, Social tensions, Criticism of measures, Vaccination campaign and Public health advice.* Many of the memes are specific to the UK context. By far the most memes were coded to the category *Criticism of politics / politicians / the government*. Common themes we identified are: a commentary on the strictness of measures, a critique of the governments' crisis communication, the perceived incompetence of the government or individual politicians, a lack of measures to address the crisis and a perceived unpreparedness, critique of politicians for not following own measures, a

Figure 56. Criticism of politicians 1 | UK

commentary on illogical measure, as well as a lack of empathy. The majority of the memes in this category mock and critique prime minister (PM) Boris Johnson. Some examples are provided in the following three figures. Figure 56 shows Boris Johnson holding his hands up. The language used in the meme is belittling and dismissive of the PM. The general message relates to public health advice, 'wash your hands', to stop viral transmission. The meme was created when the PM had tested positive for coronavirus. Prior to his diagnosis, the PM had been open with the public about his own fear of the virus. He proudly broadcast that he had visited COVID-19 hospital wards and shook patients' hands.

The second example is Figure 57: the image shows the UK PM pulling exaggerated facial and body expressions. The description says: "Meet the person in charge of your life during the coronavirus outbreak. The comment is: A message to all British people!" The meme jokes about the facial and body expressions of Boris Johnson when he was the mayor of London. These expressions tend to be perceived as silly and uncoordinated, and therefore the meme implies that a silly uncoordinated person oversees a country during a pandemic. This communicates to the public that the prime minister lacks competency in his role and to be portrayed as a 'clown' by different media.

A message to all British people!

Figure 57. Criticism of politicians 2 | UK

Figure 58. Criticism of politicians 3 | UK

Finally, the third image shows Boris Johnson giving a ‘thumbs-up’ signal to journalists outside Downing Street. It uses satire to make light of failings in the UK response to COVID-19, which seen a high fatality rate in older adults in nursing homes and in the COVID-19 strategy to re-open society at the risk of more vulnerable older adults.

The image refers to the belief that the PM (and the UK government) failed to delay COVID-19 by delaying lockdowns during the initial stages of the pandemic. Therefore, resulting in unnecessary high mortality rates.

The second most used category is *Compliance with measures*. Here the leading topics are: Coping mechanism through making fun of the current situation and (struggles of the) everyday life during the pandemic.

One example is Figure 59: the image includes a picture of the actor Daniel Craig from the film ‘James Bond’. The British secret agent is pointing a disinfectant spray, in place of a gun. Additionally, the actor is seen wearing personal protective equipment, a mask, as encouraged in public health recommendations to prevent the spread of coronavirus. The image was posted in early winter 2020, during the second wave of the pandemic. At this time, public health campaigns strongly emphasised adherence to hygiene measures. At this time in pandemic when vaccines were not yet available, and with increased risks of transmission during the winter months, behavioural strategies were the only means of protection that people could exercise.

Figure 59. Compliance with measures | UK

The third most coded category is *Gallows humour/fatalism*. The memes were dealing with the current situation of life under COVID.19 and the potential future. One example is Figure 60: the image is taken

Figure 60. Gallows humour | UK

from a popular British comedy show, the *IT Crowd*, which is known for its sarcastic and dry humour. The leading character is calmly addressing a ‘small’ fire (or hazard) adding it to the already existing bigger fire pretending there is no need to further take care of the issue. The text above hints on the actual magnitude of the problem symbolised by the fire. This meme mocks the UK COVID-19 testing operation failure during the second wave of the virus when the situation was unstable. The meme makes light of the news coverage in March 2020, that a laboratory in Luxembourg had recalled testing kits for contamination reasons, when testing materials were in high demand. The meme reflects the level of immediate management and control the spiralling situation required.

3.3 Conclusions

Memes were used across all countries under research to cope with the pandemic situation. Regarding the RQ1, asking about the dominant narratives, we have found that the majority of the memes analysed reflect or comment on the pandemic situation, sometimes in a critique of measures or politics. Two categories or overarching themes were identified across all countries: a commentary on the measures on the one hand, and social criticism on the other hand. Measures are often commented as a coping mechanism, but we have also identified specific critique, for example, if measures seem too 'soft' to actually stop the spread of the virus, as well as when measures were perceived as exaggerated and restrictive. On the other hand, memes comment on the behaviour of people during the pandemic, including hoarding of goods (particularly toilet paper), non-compliance with measures (such as wearing masks), and the anti-vax movement. While there are cultural differences, we could observe this category across all ten countries under research.

Regarding RQ2, asking about the different focus (e.g., on measures, impacts, politicians, etc.) in the countries, we found that, besides the commentary on the pandemic situation in general, and a critique of the measures, in six of the ten countries memes included criticism of the government or individual politicians, commenting on the crisis management, crisis communication, and the behaviour of politicians. In half of the countries under analysis, the sample included memes that criticise the vaccines, sometimes in spreading misinformation. In three of the countries, memes addressed the anti-vax movement. Further categories were more specific, often connected to the country-specific context of measures.

Finally, RQ3 asked about how aspects of vulnerability were discussed within memes. While we could not find any direct reference to that, many memes commented on a feeling of uncertainty. In eight of the ten countries, we could observe a commentary on compliance with the measures, such as the struggles of everyday life during the pandemic. Here, humour is used to cope with the situation and the restrictions, commenting on the own vulnerability, feeling of isolation, etc. A similar category observed in six of the ten countries is gallows humour, defeatism and fatalism. In an exaggerated comment on the pandemic situation, feelings of uncertainty are addressed, particularly regarding the duration of the pandemic. Similarly, in five of the ten countries, memes addressed social tensions, particularly tensions within families. Here, memes address the tensions caused by lockdowns and the consequent confinement to the own home, especially for families with children, as well as the tensions caused by different stances towards the vaccines.

Despite differences in search strategies and numbers of included images per country, the above-described overarching themes show similarities across countries. This is in line with findings by Kuipers (2020); this may be caused by experiences of similar situations e.g. due to lockdowns. Similar to Kuipers' findings, jokes addressed inconveniences and irritations of measures, but not the disease itself in a mostly good-natured way. This may be caused, on the one hand, by the meme format itself, which is replicated beyond national borders (we found, e.g., the 'Drake meme' in several countries) and also shared beyond national borders. On the other hand, they are determined by similar experiences such as restrictions, lockdowns, fears and feelings of uncertainty, etc.

4 Good and bad practices of COVID-19 communication

The following chapter provides an overview of good and bad practices regarding COVID-19 communication practices in ten EU+UK COVINFORM partner countries (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, and England as well as Wales). The aim is to summarise the findings of D7.1, in relation to good and bad communication practices. The chapter focuses on communicator, communication strategies and channels as well as communication targeted at vulnerable groups. The analysis identifies several categories of relevance for good and bad communication practices. Finally, a library summarizing the identified good and bad practices is included.

4.1 Methodology

In a prior step all partnering countries in the COVINFORM project provided an extensive description regarding the communication strategies practiced in their national context (D7.1). These national reports were based on desk research and included, if available, an elaboration of good and bad practices in crises communication (see D7.1). The data was collected between March 2020 and March 2021. The following analysis uses the data provided and summarized in D7.1 and produces a cross-country comparison on communication practices within the partnering nations.

4.2 Context and Background

Each country has been applying a different communication strategy to inform their population about COVID-19 and measures to stop the spread of the virus. There are not only differences regarding the content communicated, but also in regard to responsibilities, timing, channels, target groups or campaigns. Even though communication strategies are very individually adapted to a country's setting, trends could be identified across the partner nations. Main lessons, good and bad practices can be derived for each country and provide an understanding of what could be done differently.

4.3 Findings

4.3.1 Main findings

Each country applied country-specific communication strategies, depending on historical factors, cultural factors, or policy-making practices. However, some overlapping patterns appeared among all countries and common challenges and good practices could be identified.

Responsibility for communication

Communication strategies were either developed by national governments, public health stakeholders or different organizations. Strategies developed by governments often implied that top-level government speakers, and particularly health entities took on the leading role in communicating with the population (see D7.1). However, in many societies the satisfaction of residents with their national government is sinking (Eurobarometer 2021). Based on the knowledge gained in D7.1, public health entities usually implemented a strategy where the minister of health acts as the main speaker, often in collaboration with national health agencies or institutes. Since people often have higher trust in health experts, this can be considered as a good approach in times of crises. Nevertheless, in most cases no communication specialists or behavioural scientists were involved, even though they could

make a valuable contribution. A reoccurring problem in the countries under research was that residents were on times not aware of the distribution of responsibilities amongst actors involved in crisis management. This created uncertainty and confusion. Furthermore, contradicting statements among ministers or between experts damaged trust. The often applied top-down nature of communicating led to a lack of community engagement in community strategies. Particularly when preparing for unknown or uncertain times, the community needs to be actively engaged instead of only providing information in a top-down manner (Burgess et al. 2020, Jasanoff 1996)

Non-governmental organizations or private companies often took on communicating with specific population groups, providing tailored information with a specific focus tailored to the group.

Communication strategies and channels

In the early phase of the pandemic, in most countries, the communication on public health measures were simple and straight forward as the messages were clear: keep your distance and wash your hands. These are important factors for good practice. However, the COVID-19 pandemic itself also involved uncertainties not accounted for in communication strategies. With the increasing amount of information, a lack of control of messages was the outcome- This resulted in inconsistent and contradicting messages that residents had to make sense of. Moreover, residents often criticised that it is not clear to them what they are supposed to do, what is legally required or optional, and on what legal basis decisions were taken. Opacity in decision making further increased confusion and lack of openness to critique was condemned by citizens. Nevertheless, in most countries an open data policy was practiced, and the population was frequently informed on updates, which is considered commendable as this fosters transparency (Hyland-Wood et al. 2021).

As the findings in D7.1 shows different communication channels were used to provide essential information on the COVID-19 pandemic. Especially press conferences were an effective way to reach large part of society and served as a successful tool to communicate updates on the situation. Governments and authorities put efforts in providing specific websites with up-to-date, reliable information and sources, which was another successful practice. Social media channels, text messages or traditional communication material such as posters or billboards further supported spreading information. However, a common criticism is that some groups are not reached by these messages and there is a need for tailored messages to vulnerable populations.

Addressing vulnerable groups

Overall, only very few countries specifically addressed vulnerable groups within their communication strategy. Usually, non-governmental organisations or companies targeted these groups and often translated critical information into various languages.

4.3.2 Findings EU-10 +UK

This section provides a cross-country comparison on good and bad communication practices for ten COVINFORM partner countries. The following countries are taken into consideration: Austria, Belgium, Greece, Germany, Italy, Romania, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, UK (England, and Wales).

Responsibility for communication

Across the countries under research, governments, public health actors and independent organisations had different extents of responsibility in COVID-19 related communication. In most

countries, communication was mainly delivered by national government leaders and ministers (see D7.1. In Austria, for instance, most of the official communication was provided by the government. Initially, this was perceived positively by the citizens, but over time this perception shifted. Citizens thought that the government's political agenda is given much more priority than the actual content and contradicting messages from different parties caused mistrust and confusion (Eberl et al. 2021). Similarly, in Italy the Prime Minister was the main spokesperson for COVID-19 communication, but the coordination between political, scientific, policy and media level was insufficient (Giorgino 2020, Reynolds 2005). Thus, mixed messages caused confusion, unclarity and dissatisfaction among Italians. In Portugal, the Prime Minister and President were the main spokespersons at key moments, but often they were unable to respond to questions from the audience (Lopes et al. 2020). In contrast, Germany applied a multi-channel strategy and communication was provided by the government, public health institutes and actors from the private sector. This combination experienced comparatively high levels of trust from the population (Wieler et al. 2021, Lindqvist et al. 2020). Sweden clarified from the beginning that the public health agency will be in charge for the COVID-19 response, which was perceived highly positive by the population. Representatives from other ministries often participated in press conferences, gave individual interviews, or made separate speeches, which achieved that Swedes felt well informed throughout the time (Ghersetti & Odén 2021, Girritli Nygren & Olofsson 2020). In Belgium, the city of Antwerp provides a good example on effectively involving citizens in their communication actions. They recruited people with large networks in their neighbourhoods, religious or migrant communities, provided training and enabled them to share reliable COVID-19 information within their networks (City of Antwerp 2020).

Communication strategies and channels

Different communication strategies and channels were applied across the countries. Particularly daily press conferences served as a key communication tool in most countries and was well accepted by citizens. Some countries (e.g. Belgium, Italy, Sweden) provided additional press conferences where experts discussed specific themes and updates. Most countries used multiple communication channels, which does increase the reach of the information, but can also cause confusion, due to the amount of information shared. In some countries, it was often not clear which measures apply for the entire country or only for parts (England & Wales), or fragmented communication appeared by authorities from different governmental levels (Belgium). In Romania, limited freedom of speech due to the emergency situation meant that authorities managed and to some extent controlled all content published online, which destabilized the population's trust in information^{3 4}.

The range of different campaigns launched by partner countries is vast, reaching from more informative messages (Austrian "Schau auf dich, schau auf mich") to emotional, motivational campaigns triggering feelings of solidarity and belonging (Belgian "one team of 11 million"). In the United Kingdom, the first campaign was already launched in the very early phase of the pandemic and the government put great effort in communicating to the population to stay home. A UK-wide campaign involved hospital staff and COVID-19 patients, aiming to trigger emotions in the population, similar to Greece, where sentimental TV spots aimed to encourage citizens. Other countries included influencers or celebrities in their campaigns to specifically target young people (Germany, Spain).

³ <https://www.euractiv.com/section/politics/news/romania-shuts-down-websites-with-fake-covid-19-news/>

⁴ <https://cji.ro/en/are-new-forms-of-censorship-taking-form-during-the-pandemic-the-case-of-romania/>

Messages fuelled by emotions can have greater impact than solely factual based information (Fairchild et al. 2018).

Good crisis communication should aim to achieve transparent, timely, open and clear messages in regard to the pandemic. However, most countries were lacking a defined communication strategy, which can impede good crisis communication. In Spain, for instance, the main spokespersons appeared to have shared information, which was later contradicted, and erroneous data regarding statistics was presented. The lack of special communication competences in key responsible persons weakened clear and correct communication. In Austria, lack of transparency on the legal basis of COVID-19 measures and lack of openness to critique caused negative feedback from the population⁵ (Eberl, Lebernegg, Partheymüller, & Boomgaarden 2021)). In comparison, Belgium organized regular press conferences consisting of a multi-spokesperson team, which provided most of the time clear, transparent, reliable information presented by health specialists instead of political leaders. However, communication was not always clear and transparent and health specialists in leading communication roles ended up being politicised. Similarly, Sweden followed a defined strategy to provide clear, prompt, reliable and accurate information, which was well received by the Swedish population.

Addressing vulnerable groups

In most countries, crisis communication targeted the general population, and the needs of vulnerable population groups were not always taken into consideration. Often, governments collaborated with non-governmental organizations or private companies to provide tailored messages for certain groups, but in many cases the organizations just established material for their targeted groups on their own initiative. In Austria, for instance, communication campaigns were tailored for the typical upper middle-class Austrians and were lacking inclusivity for other groups and mainly non-governmental organisations provided specialized information. Nonetheless, Austria established a Corona hotline and worked with direct targeting through text messages, emails and letter to on the one hand reach older people and on the other hand migrant communities. The Portuguese government was criticized that there was no clear definition on the target group and messages were not shared on appropriate channels to reach certain groups. In Belgium, the government has actively collaborated with different organisations to make information accessible for vulnerable groups and distributed material to professionals in those sectors. Moreover, on the official government website information was available in 34 different languages. Some governments produced information tailored for children (Italy, Germany). Particularly the City of Berlin has taken efforts to offer inclusive, multilingual, and culture-sensitive communication material, using different communication channels. Sweden was even announcing to establish a separate communication plan for vulnerable groups, acknowledging the diverse needs across different groups. Similarly, the UK reported an increased effort to target vulnerable groups, mainly by translating communication material. Chapter 6 and 7 will provide more examples of how groups at risk of communication vulnerability were targeted.

4.4 Discussion and recommendations

Each of the countries under research applied a country specific communication approach in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. We are still in the middle of this global pandemic, and to this point it is

⁵Tiefenthaler, G. (2020). Eine Frage des Vertrauens. *ORF*, 26.09.2020. Available at <https://orf.at/stories/3182473/>

difficult to clearly identify good and bad practices. However, some common agreements on best practices in crisis communication were visible, just as some similarities in insufficient communication. The previous discussion aimed to summarize the main findings on the practice of good and bad communication. Local context needs to be taken into account when developing specific communication strategies. Ideally these strategies already exist prior to a crisis. Multiple factors need to be taken into consideration when planning such strategies and ultimately, all population groups must be addressed. Below, a library for good and bad practices shortly summarizes the main points from this report. Moreover, these are translated into a set of qualitative and quantitative indicators as below.

Table 2. Good and bad practices of COVID-19 communication

Good practices	Bad practices
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Developing strategy from the beginning; ▪ creating a collective feeling, a feeling of responsibility of individual, feeling of belonging; ▪ Stressing on what is still allowed; ▪ acknowledge effort of population; ▪ examples of positive acts; ▪ target vulnerable population groups; ▪ strategy to handle misinformation; ▪ use different media channels; ▪ provide multilingual, simple, culture-sensitive information; ▪ multi-spokespersons strategy; use networks and collaborate with private organizations; ▪ messages need to be: transparent, clear, precise, open, timely, understandable, grammatically and lexically precise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No adaptation of present strategies; ▪ lack of openness to critique; ▪ press conferences only led by political leaders; ▪ inconsistency and confusion across different actors; ▪ lack of expertise of spokespersons; lack of involvement of experts from communications/ behavioural sciences; ▪ delays in information release; no immediate reaction to rumours/ misinformation; ▪ errors in data; ▪ no focus on vulnerable groups; ▪ mass media and overload of information; ▪ lack of clarity and transparency of measures

5 Communication to influence behaviour change

During the COVID-19 pandemic, recommendations for effective communication strategies have been proposed to encourage people to adopt protective public health behaviours in the EU (Anson et al., 2020; Van Bavel et al., 2020; Hyland-Wood et al., 2021; Warren & Lofstedt, 2021; see also COVINFORM D7.1 '*Baseline report: Communication and information*'). To summarise, the recommendations for effective communication strategies include:

- Raising awareness and influencing risk perceptions, by communicating the benefits of adhering to government measures and undertaking protective public health behaviours;
- Building trust and resolving conflict by fostering collaboration with organisations connected with local communities (e.g., civil society and faith-based organisations);
- Providing inclusive information by tailoring strategies to the needs of different audiences and integrating diverse groups of people with different information needs into decision-making;
- Replacing top-down communication approaches with bottom-up and co-designed strategies that account for public values and perceptions and enhance trust in institutional information;
- Communicating clear and actionable instructions with consistency and honesty, while demonstrating empathy and compassion;
- Ensuring that the selection of government and public health actors communicating with the public is based on their credibility and ability to lead by example, in order to enhance trust in the information source;
- Being honest in recognizing that uncertainty is inevitable;
- Promoting desirable social norms by using both descriptive norms (everyone is doing it) and injunctive norms (it is the right thing to do);
- Being proactive in combating misinformation;
- Avoiding the use of fear- and guilt-based frames;
- Pre-testing communication campaigns beforehand and evaluating them afterwards to increase effectiveness and avoid potential unexpected outcomes.

This chapter of the present Deliverable 7.3 aims to explore how, if at all, communication strategies from the eleven COVINFORM target countries (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Romania, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, England, and Wales) followed these recommendations and have been able to encourage people in undertaking protective public health behaviours, including: mask wearing and regular hand washing; physically distancing; avoiding mass gathering; staying at home; working/schooling from home; public testing; and vaccinating (see COVINFORM D2.1 '*Database containing different data sources*').

5.1 Methodology

This report provides a summary of communication strategies of the eleven COVINFORM EU plus UK target countries based on COVINFORM D2.1 '*Database containing different data sources*' and COVINFORM D7.1 '*Baseline report: Communication and information*'. The research question set out to understand to what extent these communication strategies encouraged people to protective public health behaviour change. However, research and evaluations on this topic are scarce. As an alternative this report now looks at the compliance of residents to government measures that involve behaviour change.

5.2 Context and Background

In the pandemic context, national governments (supported by government and public health specially nominated taskforces and expert groups) communicated the measures residents should adhere to in order to reduce the spread of the coronavirus and minimise its impact. Therefore, the communication strategies needed to be based on scientific evidence and deliver clear, actionable, credible, relevant, timely, and understandable messages (see COVINFORM D7.1 '*Baseline report: Communication and information*') to influence people to undertake protective public health behaviours. In the next section a brief summary of the countries COVID-19 communication will be present as well as available evaluations of compliance to government measures and resident satisfaction with their respective government's communication.

5.3 Findings

5.3.1 Main findings for communication strategies

Austria

The government used press conferences and institutional websites⁶ to update residents about the COVID-19 situation in the country, also with information in different languages. The government also launched an open data information portal including two dashboards dedicated to daily updates of the COVID-19 situation and the vaccination strategy⁷, the Corona traffic light system (in September 2020)⁸. The government also released several information campaigns by using different communication channels to reach a larger audience, including TV, radio, newspapers, and social media. Different hotlines also provided specific support to the general public as well as different sectors (e.g., education, art, sport, economy, and social services) (see COVINFORM D7.1 '*Baseline report: Communication and information*').

A survey conducted between March and May 2020 (Kittel et al., 2021) found that between 63% and 73% of the respondents considered the measures enacted by the government as adequate. Respondents were motivated to undertake protective public health behaviours, although they reported their commitment decreased with time. In addition, a survey of 1,798 residents in Austria (Willems et al., 2020), conducted in April 2020, reported that people were overall satisfied with the various crisis management elements of the COVID-19 pandemic. People were most satisfied with how well they themselves comply with the government measures and about how they are able to comply with these measures. Similarly, a survey of 1,057 residents in Austria (Schernhammer et al., 2021) reported a high adherence to the government measures (91.1%). In addition, 46.2% of the respondents had little or no hesitancy in undertaking vaccination after the government launched the vaccination campaign. In a survey on 3,006 residents in Germany and Austria, during the early pandemic stages (Eichenberg et al., 2021), most of the respondents perceived the government measures as adequate and informative enough to undertake protective public health behaviours. While 1,004 (33.4%) respondents reported higher perception of susceptibility to COVID-19 and severity, 984 respondents (32.8%) reported a lower perceived susceptibility. Both respondent groups, however, considered

⁶ E.g., <https://www.oesterreich.gv.at/>

⁷ E.g., <https://covid19-dashboard.ages.at/>

⁸ <https://corona-ampel.gv.at/>

government measures as being able to provide benefits. Therefore, they adhered to them and undertook protective public health behaviours motivated by a sense of responsibility toward others. Finally, in January 2021, the Austrian Corona Panel Project (ACPP) published a study that found the government and its communication were received positively in the initial phase of the pandemic. However, over time, the positive sentiment started to shift (Eberl et al., 2021) (see COVINFORM D7.1 '*Baseline report: Communication and information*').

Belgium

The National Crisis Centre (NCN) oversaw the federal government's communication strategy. The federal government organized press conferences, with regional and local authorities spreading contents through their channels. In late January 2020, a multilingual COVID-19 website was launched⁹. By February 2021, its information was available in 38 languages. The NCN also released communication materials such as texts, infographics, and videos tailored for different audiences. In Brussels, local institutions cooperated with non-governmental organisations at the local level (e.g., religious leaders, youth panels) and distributed flyers in different languages. Institutional social media accounts published information on COVID-19, while smartphone users can access information on the contact tracing app CoronaAlert¹⁰. Posters with hygiene messages were distributed into public spaces, and different campaigns were launched accounting for national unity and public values (see COVINFORM D7.1 '*Baseline report: Communication and information*').

In a survey of 2,008 residents in Belgium (September 2020) (van Loenhout et al., 2021), respondents provided high scores about compliance and perceived efficacy for each of the government measures. The measure that received the highest scores was "wearing a face mask in public spaces", while "the social bubble of 5" received the lowest scores. In a follow up survey (Vanderplanken et al., 2021), 1,811 (90%) of the respondents gave a score of 50 or more (on a scale of 0-100) for the quality of information delivered in the federal government response. A high level of perceived understanding was reported for all these measures, in particular mask wearing, while less understood was the limitation on mass gathering. Most of these respondents reported to have undertaken protective public health behaviours by adhering to mask wearing, while the least adherence was for limiting personal contacts.

Greece

The Ministry of Health, the General Secretary of Civil Protection, and the Ministry of Citizen Protection carried out the communication campaigns to raise awareness and provide tailored information for specific audiences (e.g., elderly, vulnerable groups, children). These campaigns were released on TV, radio, newspapers, magazines, social media, and billboards. A dedicated website and specific hotlines were also launched¹¹. Meanwhile, social media shared all government campaigns. In the first waves, social media mainly communicated about government measures, while in 2021 they focused more on vaccination campaigns. Different national and international organizations also launched communication campaigns tailored on the needs of migrants and asylum-seekers (see COVINFORM D7.1 '*Baseline report: Communication and information*').

⁹ www.info-coronavirus.be

¹⁰ <https://coronalert.be/en/>

¹¹ www.covid19.gov.gr

A survey of 3,559 residents in Greece (Kamenidou et al., 2020) found three clusters of residents that comply with government measures by undertaking protective public health behaviours. The largest cluster consists of 1,634 “Meticulous Proactive Citizens” (48.6%). These citizens comply to most of the government measures and undertake protective public health behaviours, from self-isolation to hygienic practices and using protective equipment. These citizens are motivated by personal reasons and by the need to protect their families. The second cluster consists of 599 “Self-isolated Citizens” (17.8%). These citizens tend to frequently adhere to government measures for personal protection but prefer self-isolating rather than going to public areas. Therefore, they undertake protective public health behaviours mainly by minimizing personal exposure rather than e.g., using protective equipment. The third cluster consists of 636 “Cautious Citizens” (18.9%). These citizens adhere to government measures and undertake protective public health behaviours for personal protection, but they are not meticulous.

Germany

Chancellor Angela Merkel communicated through public press briefings, supported by institutional websites, and digital communications campaigns. Both national and State governments released several campaigns by using slogans and hashtags to raise awareness and promote acceptance of government measures, and to communicate the benefits of undertaking protective public health behaviours. In addition, a website¹² was launched to provide tailored information for families and workers in different languages. The Federal Ministry of Health also launched the German-language website “Together Against Corona”¹³, providing information about Coronavirus, the vaccines, and the other existing government campaigns) (see COVINFORM D7.1 ‘*Baseline report: Communication and information*’).

Press briefings by Chancellor Angela Merkel demonstrated confidence in science and effective communication style (Warren & Lofstedt, 2021), and contributed to ensure citizens trusted the government action and measures. Clear expectations, credibility, and transparency further helped to gain public trust (Sjölander-Lindqvist et al., 2020; Wieler et al., 2021). Communication clearly focused on individual responsibility and self-discipline, with speeches by government actors focusing on national values (Sjölander-Lindqvist et al., 2020). The hashtag #specialheroes “together against corona” raised risk awareness and promoted protective public health behavioural changes with a positive style and tailored information for young adults (Warren & Lofstedt, 2021). In addition, as reported in a survey of residents in Germany and Austria conducted in 2020 (Eichenberg et al., 2021), most of the respondents perceived the government measures as adequate; therefore, they undertook protective public health behaviours such as social distancing and mask wearing. While respondents with higher perceived susceptibility to, and severity of, COVID-19 undertook protective public health behaviours motivated by individual protection, those with a lower perceived susceptibility undertook these behaviours as motivated by a sense of responsibility toward others.

Italy

The Italian Prime Minister raised risk awareness and communicated measures through press conferences, broadcasted live via social media. Several campaigns were also activated in collaboration with different ministries and the National Health Institute through TV, radio, brochures, commercials

¹² www.bundesregierung.de

¹³ <https://www.zusammengegencorona.de>

with testimonials from famous people, apps, dossiers, and infographics, tailoring different audiences. The Ministry of Health also created a website¹⁴ to tailor information for specific audience such as older people, children, and youth. In addition, a hotline number was available for older people and women victims of domestic violence) (see COVINFORM D7.1 '*Baseline report: Communication and information*').

In a survey conducted between February and March 2020 (Lim et al., 2021), 72.2% of the Italian respondents trusted the governments online communication and had greater acceptance of government measures. Based on this, they undertook protective public health behaviours, also to protect family and community. Similarly, a survey of 3,964 residents in Italy conducted in March 2020 (Carlucci et al., 2020) found that respondents adhered to government recommendations by undertaking protective public health behaviours, including avoiding mass gatherings (92.8%), covering mouth/nose (when sneezing/coughing) (78.5%), avoiding handshake/hug (76.8%), and respecting social distancing (70.6%). Wearing a mask had a low rate (35.7%) of adoption. In addition, a survey of 1,332 residents in Italy (Stojanovic et al., 2021), conducted from 27 March to 5 May 2020, found that most of the respondents reported being aware of the major recommendations from the Italian government, including handwashing (99.9%), physical distancing (99.8%), social distancing (98.9%), self-isolating (98.2%) and self-quarantine after a trip (96.4%). About 88% of the respondents also recognized that government measures were 'very important' for preventing and/or reducing the spread of COVID-19.

Romania

On 16 March 2020, the President Klaus Iohannis declared a state of emergency with a presidential decree. The National Authority for Management and Regulation in Communications (ANCOM) became the body responsible for combating online disinformation; the Romanian government was therefore proactive and launched a website¹⁵ to disseminate official communication. The government raised risk awareness through press conferences and official statements published on the Ministry of Internal Affairs' website. In partnership with NGOs, the government also implemented an information campaign through channels such as TV, radio, social media, banners, and door-to-door printed materials. Local authorities then disseminated the decisions taken at the national level. In addition, several hotlines were available for citizens, including Tel Verde (Green Line, 24h/7 national hotline), also accessible for Romanian expats (see COVINFORM D7.1 '*Baseline report: Communication and information*').

According to Dascalu (2020), the nationwide information campaign by the Romanian government encouraged people to adopt protective public health behaviours, including social distancing, mask wearing and the use of disinfectants. A survey conducted in April 2020 by Popescu and Vilcea (2021) of 734 residents in Romania also found that most of the respondents (54%) trusted the government measures, although manifested a lower confidence in the capacity of the public health system (69%). Respondents declared that they adhered to government measures and changed their normal behaviour in terms of meeting with friends and other family members (94.5%), reasons to get out of the house (93.2%), keeping the recommended distance (92.5%), avoiding persons returned from red

¹⁴ <https://www.salute.gov.it/portale/nuovocoronavirus/homeNuovoCoronavirus.jsp>

¹⁵ www.stiriofficiale.ro

zone countries (97.6%), avoiding crowded places (88.8%), and stricter hygiene and use of disinfectants (89.3%).

Spain

In the first phases, the Coronavirus Technical Management Committee, composed by different ministries and security and emergency national bodies, was in charge for the crisis management. The government communicated mainly through press conferences of political representatives and technical experts. These conferences were broadcasted live, and their contents spread on TV, radio, press, and social media. These press conferences aimed at raising risk awareness, the government's control of the situation, and at enhancing national values of unity with the adopted slogan “We can stop this virus together”. Further to the press release, official websites and educational materials translated the recommendations of international organisations into accessible and easy-to-understand information (see COVINFORM D7.1 ‘*Baseline report: Communication and information*’).

A survey by Losada Díaz et al. (2020) of 1,823 residents in Spain, conducted between March and April 2020, found that 1,135 respondents (62.3%) approved the communication strategies carried out by the Spanish government during the first phase of the pandemic. More than half of the respondents (952, 52.27%) scored the government's crisis communication between 5 and 8 (on a scale of 1 to 10), while 517 respondents (28.4%) scored a range of between 7 and 8 points. In addition, in a survey by Frias-Navarro et al. (2021) on 1,122 residents in Spain, respondents stated that they followed the recommendations of the government and health professionals to a greater extent, and believed to a greater extent that others are also acting in accordance with these guidelines.

Sweden

The government’s communication followed scientific expertise and recommendations of the Public Health Agency (PHA) that used websites, digital/traditional billboards, and social media to disseminate information. The PHA also provided information material to health organizations, adjusted to regional and local settings. A special communication plan also tailored simplified messages and in different languages. The Swedish Civil Contingency Agency arranged press conferences where the Prime Minister and/or the Minister of Social Affairs communicated with the citizens. These press conferences were broadcasted on TV, on online media outlets and social media. The government’s communication aimed at being clear and coordinated, at reaching large audiences and at providing tailored support and information. Verified and reliable COVID-19 information were available on the official crisis website¹⁶. The King of Sweden, Carl XVI Gustaf, also participated in communication with two speeches in the early stages of the pandemic. These speeches were of great symbolic value and strengthened national identity (see COVINFORM D7.1 ‘*Baseline report: Communication and information*’).

Sweden adopted an approach that was initially different from most of the EU countries. This approach aimed at mitigating the virus impacts, by limiting the extent of disruptive interventions and relying on voluntary measures (e.g., self-isolation, mask wearing, and business closure) while still aiming to slow the spread (Kamerlin & Kasson, 2020). Kamerlin and Kasson (2020) suggested that this approach has provided an intermediate response between the public health mandates alone and the stronger mandates implemented by other countries. Large portions of the population voluntarily self-isolated in the first waves, leading to an intermediate number of reported deaths per capita fewer than other

¹⁶ www.krisinformation.se

countries, but higher than other Scandinavian neighbours and European countries that implemented strong measures. Similarly, a survey conducted in May-June 2020 (Andersson et al., 2021) among 4,495 university students in Sweden found that the adoption of protective public health behaviours to comply with government and public health recommendations was the highest for handwashing (95.7%) and risk group avoidance (95.5%), and the lowest for avoiding public transportation (69.7%).

England and Wales

Initially, the four nations forming the United Kingdom (Wales, Scotland, Northern Ireland and England) worked together to respond to the coronavirus pandemic. A UK-wide information campaign was launched in early February 2020, including advice to slow the spread of coronavirus. The campaign was featured on TV, radio, media, and social media. On 15 March 2020, the UK government started the campaign “Stay home, protect the NHS, save lives”. On 29 March, a letter and a leaflet were sent to 30 million households that included social distancing rules and instructions. In April 2020, Queen Elizabeth II made two speeches broadcast on television to thank people and foster national unity. On 9 May 2020, a new campaign “Stay Alert, control the virus, save lives” led to fragmented responses across the four UK nations, with each nation following their own approach (Wardman, 2020). The main governmental communication strategy lies in the test-and-trace or contact tracing approach. Each nation of the UK has its own contact tracing service including “Test, Trace and Protect” in Wales, NHS Test and Trace” in England, “Test and Protect” in Scotland, and “Contact tracing service” in Northern Ireland) (see COVINFORM D7.1 ‘*Baseline report: Communication and information*’).

In May 2020, over 1,100 experts shared concerns about COVID-19 communications strategies of the UK government, and argued that that UK government messages were unclear, inconsistent, and unable to call out misinformation¹⁷. Notwithstanding these criticisms, other scholars argued that the UK government’s public press briefings with a minister and one scientist/expert demonstrated alignment with scientific expertise and increased credibility and trust in government (Warren & Lofstedt, 2021). It was also argued that the slogan “Stay at Home, Protect the NHS, Save Lives” released in the first wave offered the simple and clear message to stay at home and protect the public health system and the community (Warren & Lofstedt, 2021). This resulted in high compliance, as 90% of people reported that they understood the benefits of the protective public health behaviours that they were expected to undertake (Warren & Lofstedt, 2021). A survey on 20,947 residents in the UK (17 November - 23 December 2020) (Wright et al., 2021a) found that most of the respondents (52.5%) complied with government measures by adopting protective public health behaviours related to mask wearing, hand washing, indoor and outdoor mixing, social distancing, and other guidelines. Mask wearing was the most adopted protective public health behaviour, while social distancing was relatively less adopted. A follow up survey of 50,851 residents in the UK (01 April 2020 - 22 February 2021) (Wright et al., 2021b) reported similar findings. Indeed, 32.8% of the respondents complied consistently with all measures throughout the pandemic. However, approximately one in seven respondents reported lower levels of compliance in the second wave.

Portugal

The Prime Minister communicated mostly via press conferences, by both raising awareness among the general population and tailoring communication for specific sectors. These conferences were also

¹⁷ <https://post.parliament.uk/media-communications-and-covid-19-what-are-experts-concerned-about/>. See also COVINFORM D7.1 *Baseline report: Communication and information*.

aired on public television channels, while their videos were uploaded on institutional websites and social media. The information was then converted and summarized into brochures or written press release. The Ministry of Health and the General Department of Health (DGS) developed the COVID-19 communication plan. This included main communication guidelines and a health plan for autumn-winter 2020-21. Initially, the Minister of Health and the DGS communicated with the general population via daily press conference, but from May 2020 communication occurred through brochures. The DGS and the Ministry of Health have also produced leaflets and brochures with instructions on how to undertake protective public health behaviours in everyday life and into workplaces (see COVINFORM D7.1 *'Baseline report: Communication and information'*).

According to Silva et al. (2021), the communication strategy of the Portuguese government helped citizens in adopting protective public health behaviours and searching for a common national goal. In turn, this generated higher levels of government support and allowed the successful implementation of social distancing rules. Indeed, the majority (92%) of citizens considered the restrictions on personal freedoms justified by the scale and severity of the pandemic during the first lockdown. Similarly, in a survey across students at the University of Minho (Braga, Portugal), Alves et al. (2020) found that respondents complied with government measures and showed high motivation to undertake protective public health behaviours during the first lockdown. Strzelecki et al. (2020) also claim that correlation exists between the COVID-19 spread and the search in Google for personal protective equipment and hygiene. This can help, to a certain extent, to understand risk awareness and the adoption of protective public health behaviours across the general public.

5.4 Discussion

The insights presented here have discussed the government communication strategies in the eleven target countries that have been designed to influence residents to comply with institutional measures and to undertake public health protective behaviours. However, there is limited research examining the impact that these communication strategies have had on influencing behaviour change. Research predominantly focuses on examining the compliance with measures and the adoption of public health protective behaviours, rather than the impact of communication on behaviour change. As a result, the research findings presented in this chapter predominantly highlight compliance. Some evaluations also covered residents' satisfaction with government measures to stop the spread of COVID-19. In general, compliance with government's measures was high in the majority of countries during the first lockdown. However, this allows no in-depth evaluation of the impact of government communication on behaviour change itself. Nonetheless, it gives an indication that government communicated in a way that enabled the majority of residents to follow their measures at least to some extent. Further research and evaluation are needed to understand the effectiveness of government communication on behaviour change, particularly in relation to diverse and vulnerable audiences. Further, as the pandemic is unfolding for almost two years now, communication and measures have changed and so has, most likely, the willingness or ability to comply to measures involving behaviour change. Here too, further research is needed. Investigating time dimensions would also allow for insightful comparisons.

6 Digital communication and exclusion

This chapter focuses on digital communication and exclusion. There was a shift towards digital communication during the COVID-19 crisis. While digital communication is a great way of reaching broad audiences as it is easy to upscale, it has effectively excluded several groups from relevant information, as well as communication. This chapter presents a comprehensive literature review on the topics of the digital divide, digital inequality, groups who are impacted by it, and ways to mitigate the risks. Furthermore, it summarises the way governments in the ten EU+UK countries under research have taken those groups most affected by digital inequalities into account. This is embedded in a broader geographical context provided by the literature review.

This chapter responds to a gap in D7.1, where digital inequality was not explicitly explored. Due to the COVINFORM project's focus on vulnerability, we have explored this topic more closely, aiming to gain a better understanding of communication vulnerability. As such, this chapter presents the base for further investigations during the empirical research for WP7 and WP6.

6.1 Growth of Digital Spaces

The COVID-19 pandemic and its associated lockdown restrictions have been met by the burgeoning and rapid uptake in digital technology. In an American study by Nguyen et al. (2020), they found that people were overall more likely to increase their digital communication during the pandemic than to decrease it. And, according to Budd et al. (2020), this growth has been caused by the unprecedented humanitarian and economic needs caused by the pandemic, as every day and in-person activities like working, going to school, and grocery shopping have relocated to an online environment. The internet has become a crucial source for information during the crisis, with national and international news, general information about the virus, and guidelines on behavioural norms provided online (van Deursen 2020).

While there was an increase in all forms of digital media use in the first few months of the pandemic, video conferencing technologies in particular experienced unprecedented growth (Nuyen et al., 2020) as people not only sought to telework but to maintain social connectedness (Kirk & Rifkin, 2020). In a study of Italian adults from the early months of the pandemic, Gabbiadini et al. (2020) found that when people connected with others via digital technology during the lockdowns, feelings of loneliness, anger/irritability, and boredom reduced, while belongingness via the perception of social support increased, highlighting the role of digital technologies as a tool for social connection during the pandemic. The shift to the online realm has elevated the power of digital spaces in the pandemic – they are the main way to access information and services and are also one of the only remaining avenues where economic, educational, leisure, and social interactions can take place (Beaunoyer et al., 2020). As Barnes (2020) states, the COVID-19 pandemic has “brought information and communications technologies to the forefront of human life.” (p. 1).

6.2 Digital Inequalities

However, this move to the online sphere has not been a socially equal one, and the inability for many to meaningfully connect online is a critical concern. With physical distancing and lockdown restrictions in place, activities that did not require a person to have a personal computer and home internet connection pre-COVID-19, like working, learning, or meeting with friends, now require these digital

tools (Beaunoyer et al. 2020). With personal computers the “gateway to the majority of human interaction and socializing” (Kirk & Rifkin 2020, 127) during the pandemic, those who are not connected to the internet are facing “total exclusion” (De et al. 2020, 3). Virtual digital spaces are no longer an amenity but a necessity for survival (Beaunoyer et al. 2020; De et al. 2020), and those who find themselves on the “wrong side of the digital divide are completely left out” (De et al. 2020, 3).

6.2.1 Reasons for Digital Divide

Hargittai (2003) presents four factors that impact digital technology use, and can thus impact digital inequalities. The first, *technical means*, refers to the usability and speed of the software and hardware as well as the reliability of the internet connection. Just being connected to the internet may not be enough to engage meaningfully online, with activities like using Skype, Zoom, and Microsoft Teams requiring internet speeds of 10+mbps, and streaming 4k videos needing 150+mbps (Kuc-Czarnecka 2020). Hargittai’s second factor, *autonomy of use*, references the location where the technology is being accessed and the ability to use it when and how the user needs. For example, only being able to access the internet at a public space may influence how a person engages online. The third factor is *social support networks*, which is where inexperienced users can seek support from more experienced users within their social network. The last factor, *experience*, refers to how familiar users are with the technology in order to retain the benefits from its usage. These factors align with the three dimensions of capital presented by Bourdieu and applied to digital technologies by Baum et al. (2014): they argue that a person’s economic, cultural, and social capital play a role in digital inequalities – a person may not be able to afford new technologies (economic capital), may not be able to use the technology well due to limited educational opportunities (cultural capital), and may not have the social connections required to support their use of the technology (social capital). Thus, they argue that being digitally excluded is becoming one of the many ways in which disadvantaged people are being further disadvantaged.

In addition to those of lower socio-economic status in high-income countries, those in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) are most affected by the digital divide (Budd et al. 2020). When looking at *mobile internet connectivity*, LMICs account for more than 90% of the world’s unconnected population and 98% of the uncovered population (GSMA 2021). The impact of this digital exclusion has been seen from the first months of the pandemic, such as when a targeted mobile internet shutdown in some townships in Myanmar – a shutdown that had been ongoing since mid-2019 – meant that people in affected villages were unaware of the COVID-19 outbreak (Human Rights Watch, 2020). And, throughout 2020, authorities in India shut down the internet 109 times, mostly in the union territory of Kashmir, citing “precautionary measures” at a time when the region was heavily dependent on the internet for study and work due to lockdown restrictions (Duggal 2021). Further to this, almost half of the world’s population (49%) is disconnected from the mobile internet due to five potential barriers to mobile internet usage: Access; Affordability; Knowledge and skills; Safety and security; and Relevance (GSMA 2021). These barriers align closely with the factors presented by Hargittai (2003) outlined above.

In a study by Kuc-Czarnecka (2020), who analysed GIS data from Poland, 2.5 million Polish inhabitants were found to not be able to participate in online work and learning during the pandemic due to infrastructure deficiencies. Kuc-Czarnecka argues that while *digital skills* can be acquired “relatively quickly”, gaining access to hardware and infrastructure is more difficult to overcome during lockdown restrictions. Her study found that 4% of Poles remain outside of internet coverage, and she argues that

the pandemic has shown “that the assumption made by policymakers and entrepreneurs that everyone has at home decent equipment and broadband internet connection to participate smoothly and efficiently in webinars, online meetings and conferences, was entirely erroneous” (p. 418).

6.2.2 Impact of the Digital Divide

Even outside of the COVID-19 pandemic, being digitally excluded impacts on a person’s health determinants, such as education and employment, ultimately contributing to what Baum et al. (2014) describe as a “digital vicious cycle” (p. 349). In their Australian focus group study, Baum et al. found that people from lower socio-economic backgrounds are limited in the ways in which they can access and beneficially use digital technologies and that this amplifies existing disadvantages. This is supported by Ragnedda (2017), who states that limited or lack of access to ICTs can reinforce existing societal inequalities. Socioeconomic status is seen as an important predictor for how well people engage with the internet, with more privileged individuals using it in more informed ways and for a broader range of activities (Hargittai 2010).

Impact on existing societal inequalities

This phenomenon has become apparent during the COVID-19 pandemic. The reliance on digital technologies in the crisis has reinforced and deepened existing societal inequalities related to factors like socio-economic status, age, education, and health literacy (Beaunoyer et al. 2020; van Deursen 2020), and we have seen that health, societal, and economic impacts of the virus disproportionately affect these vulnerable and disadvantaged populations (Budd et al. 2020).

Nguyen et al. (2020) argue that a lack of access to digital support during the pandemic may be further reinforcing digital inequalities, with marginalised groups more at risk at becoming disconnected from their social environment than others. In their survey study of American adults, conducted in the early months of the pandemic, Nguyen et al. (2020) found that older people, those with internet access insecurity, and people with lower internet skills were more likely to have reduced their digital communication during the pandemic. A later study by Nguyen et al. (2021), which builds on these findings, reinforces this. With the opportunities for in-person interactions heavily reduced during the pandemic, older people showed a higher likelihood for decreasing their digital communication use, and when looking at differences across ethnicities, they found that African American people were more likely than White people to have decreased their digital communication (Nguyen et al. 2021).

The researchers also looked at other factors that influence digital communication, like people’s living arrangements and internet skills. They found that people living alone were more likely to have increased their use of video calls, social media, and online games, indicating that this was an avenue for social interaction (Nguyen et al. 2021). When looking at internet skills and experiences, they found that more frequent internet use corresponded with an increase in digital communication across all methods, while people who had concerns regarding internet access both increased and decreased different methods, indicating that their digital communication uses were more likely to change during the pandemic. Interestingly, they also found that people who had left their homes for non-essential social activities were more likely to worry about Internet access, suggesting this may be the reason why they ventured out (ibid.).

Impact on vulnerable groups

These findings are supported by van Deursen (2020), who conducted a similar study of adults in the Netherlands in the early months of the pandemic. His results showed that groups of vulnerable people, such as older people, less educated people, people with physical health problems, low literacy levels, or low internet skills, were less likely to benefit from the information and communication opportunities afforded by the internet. He argues that the COVID-19 crisis is reinforcing existing inequalities, where marginalised people are likely to have “fewer types of access available to take actions, behave as requested, or be comforted by help, creating a vicious cycle where already marginalized groups are further marginalized in a time of crisis” (p. 11). The inability for many people to replace in-person interactions with digital communication is a key reason why the disadvantages of the pandemic particularly affect the already-disadvantaged (Robinson et al. 2020).

It is interesting to note that the study by Nguyen et al. (2021) indicates that a person’s socioeconomic privileges were not always indicative of digital communication use. When looking at gender differences, they found that women were more likely than men to increase their digital communication across several methods. This finding is, however, in contrast to the study by van Deursen (2020), who found that men were more likely than women to use the internet for communication about COVID-19. Nguyen et al. (2021) suggest the reason for this difference lies in the fact that van Deursen’s study focused on communication activities related to COVID-19, while Nguyen et al.’s study looked at digital communication in a more general, social sense. The latter’s findings are supported by research by Jackson et al. (2001), who find that women use technology more than men to connect socially. Regardless, Nguyen et al. (2021) argue that digital inequality is a contributing factor to the “broader unequal unfolding of the crisis in terms of the negative impacts experienced across more and less privileged groups” (p. 7).

Barnes (2020) describes the rapid shift to digitalisation as a double-edged sword. While he acknowledges the emerging benefits of digital technologies in areas such as medicine and education during the pandemic, he argues that the shift has “surfaced old wounds” (p. 3) regarding the digital divide, with the most vulnerable groups being low-income households, those with lower educational achievement, the elderly, disabled, and potentially certain ethnic minorities. More specifically, he says the pandemic has shut the elderly out of digital communication and activities like online shopping, while high school aged children from poor communities have been shut out of online education, which may have long-term effects on their future (Barnes, 2020).

While evidence shows there are social connectivity benefits to gain from using digital technology (Gabbiadini et al. 2020), those who are unable to join the digital space are unable to access those benefits. “The lack of reliable access to online services may, therefore, represent an additional burden for those with less access to material and social resources to buffer the negative effects of the coronavirus lockdown” (Gabbiadini et al. 2020, p. 9).

Impact on less digitally-savvy

Further, even when vulnerable people do have access to the internet, they also need to be able to understand how to use it to experience its benefits. For example, an older person who rarely uses digital technology may struggle trying to download and navigate new apps to participate in digital spaces, like attending a virtual birthday party or playing an online game with family members (Nguyen et al. 2020). Together, findings suggest that the less digitally-savvy may be becoming more digitally

disconnected at a time when such digital communication is especially critical (van Deursen 2020), and many may be missing out socially (Nguyen et al. 2020).

In addition, traditional literacy skills were still considered important when using digital tools. Baum et al. (2014) highlight how low literacy can disadvantage both non-native and native English speakers when it comes to written content provided in the internet. And, in van Deursen's (2020) study, when looking at the relationship between literacy skills and digital communication use, he found that those who struggled to read, write, and understand text were further disadvantaged during the pandemic, as they had fewer information and communication sources. Thus, a person's literacy skills were vital in determining how much benefit a person could get from accessing digital communication tools. However, it is important to note that there are image and video-based platforms, as well as speech-to-text services, that may soften the exclusion on persons with low literacy.

Impact on health

Scholars also raise the concern that the digital divide is increasing the risk of contracting the virus among vulnerable people. For example, Van Deursen (2020) and Gabbiadini et al. (2020) describe how vulnerable people (such as the elderly, ill people, and those living in poverty), who are generally more digitally disconnected, are also at higher risk of the effects of the COVID-19 virus. When looking at older people, van Deursen (2020) found that older people did increase their internet use to search for COVID-19 information and communication in the early months of the pandemic, but this did not translate to beneficial information outcomes – demonstrating that internet skills were still critical for getting the most beneficial use out of the internet. A lack of internet skills may further endanger older people as they may be unable to gain critical information or the necessary support during the crisis (van Deursen, 2020).

Beaunoyer et al. (2020) also argue that digital inequalities are contributing to people's vulnerability to contracting COVID-19. A large amount of information about COVID-19 has been disseminated digitally – by April 2020, 86% of the United Nations' member states had shared COVID-19 information on their website (United Nations Division for Public Institutions and Digital Government, 2020), and official health organisations like the WHO were using the internet to share information about COVID-19 (Beaunoyer et al. 2020). Beaunoyer et al. (2020) argue that people with low eHealth literacy are less likely to access official government and health agency websites and are therefore more likely to contract the virus as they struggle to understand and apply protective measures. This is supported by a study by Robinson et al. (2020), who found that vulnerable people (their study specifically looked at the socially isolated, older adults, penal system subjects, digitally disadvantaged students, gig workers, and last-mile workers) were less likely to have the economic means to use digital services and more likely to engage in face-to-face interaction to meet their family and community needs, thus putting themselves at more risk of contracting the virus.

Impact on socio-economic status

Beaunoyer et al. (2020) also note that vulnerable people are more likely to suffer the wider socio-economic impacts of the pandemic, as those with low digital literacy may not be able to identify 'fake news' or disinformation, and may follow advice that is detrimental to their own health and the health of the population (Beaunoyer et al. 2020). Additionally, digitally disconnected people are more at risk of breaches of cybersecurity (Beaunoyer et al. 2020) as their inexperience with using the internet and digital resources during the pandemic may make them targets for fraud and scams (De et al. 2020).

However, some organisations and governments are responding to these wider socio-economic impacts. For example, Zoom was forced to upgrade its security standards after some governments refused to use the platform (De et al. 2020), while organisations like Google now prioritise the WHO and other trusted sources of information in their SOS alert system (Budd et al. 2020). There is also evidence that some governments have attempted to address the digital divide with alternative communication during the pandemic. A study by the United Nations Division for Public Institutions and Digital Government (2020) found that some member states were partnering with external stakeholders to implement text messaging services to reach those who did not have access to the internet. Similarly, the European Commission, in partnership with the Body of European Regulators of Electronic Communications, monitors internet traffic in each member state to ensure internet connectivity (United Nations Division for Public Institutions and Digital Government 2020).

6.3 Mitigating Digital Inequalities

At the time of publishing their article (September 2020), Nguyen et al. suggest that it is still too early to tell if the new digital behaviours are here to stay, but they do point to a study by the GlobalWebIndex that indicates that people expect to maintain their new digital behaviours after the pandemic ends. De et al. (2020) argue that the trend towards digital communication and online technologies will remain, with the internet expected to stay “central to the post-pandemic scenario” (p. 3). When looking specifically at health outcomes, Budd et al. (2020) say the future of public health is likely to be increasingly digital. This points to an outcome where the digital divide, exacerbated by COVID-19, is expected to continue post-pandemic.

To address this, several researchers call for policy change. Gabbiadini et al. (2020) say that policymakers should introduce strategies to reduce the digital divide and offer affordable access to communication technologies, while Kuc-Czarnecka (2020) argues that to ensure ICT access for all, government intervention is required as market forces alone are not enough. Van Deursen (2020) calls for more focused policies that aim to enhance people’s health outcomes, such as encouraging people to engage with information and communication related to COVID-19 online. He argues that the internet plays a vital role for people from all “social strata” and backgrounds, and thus all people should be able to access the internet as a source of information. Further to this, Baum et al. (2020) call for health promotion that interrupts the “vicious cycle” of digital exclusion, advocating for more digital inclusion to create better health equity.

Some researchers have presented some strategies to mitigate the impact of the digital divide during the pandemic. Beaunoyer et al. (2020) propose a number of mitigations – what they refer to as a “social safety net” (p. 7) – to digital inequalities that can be implemented at a governmental, organisation, community, and individual level. They recommend increasing physical access to connected devices and the internet, increasing digital literacy, increasing access to social support, increasing the diffusion of the messages, increasing the control over the quality of the messages, increasing the understandability of the messages, and increasing the acceptability of the messages. The potential of social media as a way to combat the digital divide during the pandemic has also been highlighted. Nguyen et al. (2021) argue that social media presents a “unique channel for retaining communication and information sharing” within groups that are disadvantaged in their internet use. For example, African American people were no more likely than White people to have decreased their social media use during the pandemic, while Native American people were more likely than White people to have increased their

social media use (Nguyen et al., 2021), thus highlighting the potential for social media as a digital communication tool in certain groups. However, as noted in the section below, social media use may have a negative impact on mental health.

To address the digital divide in LMICs, the Mobile Economy 2021 report by the GSMA outlines potential ways to overcome the five barriers to mobile internet use. Barriers to access can be overcome by improving access to quality network coverage and enablers, such as handsets and electricity, and improving the usability of both the technology and the services. Barriers to affordability can be overcome with more affordable handsets, tariffs, data, and service fees. (A lack of) knowledge and skills can be addressed by investing in digital skills and literacy and increasing the awareness of mobile technology and its benefits. Gaps in safety and security can be overcome by addressing the issues of theft, fraud, and security and building consumer trust. And finally, relevance can be addressed by providing relevant – such as local – content, products, and services (GSMA, 2021).

Measures implemented in the EU+UK countries

Based on D7.1, we have identified a number of measures conducted in the ten countries under research to mitigate digital divide and exclusion through the shift towards digital communication. First, it needs to be mentioned that all countries under research conducted multi-channel information campaigns, making use of both digital and traditional media including websites, TV, radio, newspaper, and other channels (such as social media, or billboards). However, up-to-date information has usually been provided on dedicated websites.

An overview of measures implemented to avoid digital inequality and reach out to vulnerable groups who are impacted by digital inequality – particularly older people – are provided in Table 3 below. This reflects the time of data collection in the COVINFORM project, i.e. between March 2020 and March 2021, and may have been updated since.

Table 3. Measures to mitigate digital inequalities

	Austria	Belgium	Italy	Germany	Greece	Portugal	Romania	Spain	Sweden	UK
Targeted info campaigns	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Social organisations & CSOs	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Hotlines	x		x			x	x		x	
Teletext	x									
Easy-to-read / simple language	x	x		x					x	x
Sign language interpretations	x		x	x					x	
Personalised guidance					x	x				
Letters	x		x							x

What we can see is that in all countries under research, there were (at least to some degree) information campaigns targeted at different groups, including those defined as vulnerable such as older people. Furthermore, all governments collaborated with social or civil society organisations to reach out to specific groups such as migrants, homeless persons, children, etc. However, there is still a focus on digital communication in the COVID-19 crisis communication, and no measures (in the timeframe observed) have been implemented to address digital inequalities themselves.

6.4 Mental Health Impact of Digital Technologies

During the pandemic, Garfin (2020) states that people have experienced collective trauma, with its psychological effects seen at both a direct and indirect (i.e. via the media) level, as well as secondary stressors such as job losses or reduced wages. However, these impacts on mental health may be worsened by the increased use of digital technologies. As already noted, the global lockdown restrictions and stay-at-home orders led to a rapid increase in digital technology use, such as online gaming and social media. However, studies have shown that excessive smartphone use may lead to social withdrawal and damaged personal relationships (Barnes, Pressey & Scornavacca 2019), while the overuse of technology has been linked to heightened anxiety caused by an overload of communication and information (Ragu-Nathan et al. 2008). Further, heavy social media use may be associated with increased anxiety and depression (Haidt & Allen 2020), and social media has been shown to have a strong cognitive absorption impact, particularly among female users (Barnes, Pressey & Scornavacca 2019).

Studies have demonstrated the impact of digital technologies on mental health during the pandemic. In a study of 917 Chinese residents, the use of new media (such as online news sites or social media updates) was associated with negative psychological outcomes, while the use of traditional media (such as television, radio, and newspapers) was not (Chao et al. 2020). Additional studies support this finding: social media exposure was associated with higher levels of anxiety or a combination of depression and anxiety during the COVID-19 outbreak in China (Gao et al. 2020), while an Iraq study shows that social media (particularly Facebook) played a key role in spreading fear and panic related to the COVID-19 outbreak in Iraqi Kurdistan (Ahmad & Murad 2020). A study by Liu et al. (2021) shows that members of Gen Z in the UK are experiencing social media fatigue and fear of COVID-19 during the crisis as a result of information overload on social media, leading some to discontinue their social media use. Interestingly, the levels of stress caused by social media depends on a person's gender, age, and level of education, with younger people aged 18-35 more likely to be psychologically affected (Ahmad & Murad, 2020). This reflects a similar finding by Ragu-Nathan et al. (2008), who found that "technostress" was more likely to be experienced by younger people, the less educated, and less computer confident, which further demonstrates the disadvantages more vulnerable people are facing when using ICTs and digital technology during the pandemic. When looking at online gaming, King et al. (2020) note that while online gaming has been used and promoted during the COVID-19 pandemic as a means for socialisation and as a healthy coping strategy, there is evidence of it being problematic for vulnerable individuals, as it poses risks for developing unhealthy lifestyle patterns and an inability to re-adapt post-pandemic.

These examples are especially concerning considering that this pandemic-induced psychological distress may be adding more pressure to an "already fragile" mental health system (Beaunoyer et al. 2020). Researchers have called for more government attention to the mental health impacts and the

“infodemic” and “emotional contagion” occurring through social media platforms during the pandemic (Gao et al. 2020; Ni et al. 2020). In their systematic review, Xiong et al. (2020) identify a high prevalence of adverse psychiatric symptoms during the crisis, and they argue that Covid-19 represents an “unprecedented threat” to mental health in high, middle, and low-income countries. They argue that mitigating the hazardous effects on people’s mental health should be “an international public health priority” (p. 1) and call for a combination of government policy as well as personal provisions, such as exercise and a healthy diet, to alleviate hazards to mental health.

6.5 Conclusions

During the pandemic, an increase of all forms of digital media use, particularly of video conferencing tools, but also an increase in internet use, has had both positive and negative effects on people: staying connected via digital technologies may reduce feelings of isolation and loneliness. However, some groups within society may face challenges to meaningfully connect online.

The digital divide is caused by four factors that increase digital inequality: technical means, the autonomy of use, social support networks, and experience. Research (Baum et al. 2014; Ragnedda 2017) has shown that lower socio-economic backgrounds impact the digital divide and thus amplify existing disadvantages. This existing effect has been worsened during the pandemic; the reliance on digital technologies in the crisis has reinforced and deepened existing societal inequalities related to factors like socioeconomic status, age, education, and health literacy (Beaunoyer et al., 2020; van Deursen, 2020), and we have seen that health, societal, and economic impacts of the virus disproportionately affect these vulnerable and disadvantaged populations (Budd et al., 2020).

Some vulnerable groups may be at increased risk of contracting the virus due to the digital divide and a subsequent lack of information on the virus, vaccines, and other public health aspects provided online: vulnerable groups such as older or chronically ill persons as well as those living in poverty, who are generally more digitally disconnected, are also at higher risk of the effects of the pandemic (Van Deursen 2020; Gabbiandini et al. 2020).

For this reason, there is a need for policy change to mitigate digital inequalities, including the development of strategies to reduce the digital divide, offering affordable access to communication technologies, as well as more focused policies aiming to enhance people’s health outcomes, such as encouraging people to engage with information and communication related to COVID-19 online. There is, however, still a lack of addressing digital inequalities. While we could observe some measures implemented to overcome the digital divide in the countries under research, such as targeting of information campaigns, collaboration with social or civil society organisations, as well as measures such as offering information via hotlines, in easy-to-read language or through personalised guidance, the underlying inequalities are not addressed. Due to the ongoing nature of the pandemic and its socio-economic impacts, digital inequalities may worsen. Fieldwork in WP6 and WP7 of the COVINFORM project will investigate this aspect further, aiming to get an in-depth understanding of the impacts of the pandemic, as well as of digital exclusion.

7 Fighting disinformation and misinformation

The COVID-19 pandemic has been accompanied by an ‘infodemic’: the spread of an overwhelming amount of information, including misinformation and disinformation. Both can have harmful effects, particularly during a public health crisis. This part of the deliverable contains a review of measures taken by 10 EU+UK (England and Wales) countries to fight and cope with misinformation and disinformation during the COVID-19 pandemic. The information used for this review is based on findings provided in COVINFORM *D7.1 Baseline report: Communication and information*¹⁸ and COVINRORM *D6.1 Baseline report: Community and citizen responses*. Data used for this analysis was gathered through desk research. The measures and initiatives taken can broadly be divided in twelve categories. These will be presented in more detail below. This will be followed by a short paragraph on Romania and how the state of emergency was used to restrict freedom of speech, to some extent. Finally, we present good and best practices examples on national local government level. These initiatives are targeted at groups at risk of communication vulnerability. Qualitative analysis on the effectiveness of the measures taken was not possible due to missing data and a continuously evolving pandemic and ‘infodemic’ situation. However, we aim to provide a more in-depth analysis in the second iteration of this deliverable.

7.1 Methods

The measures taken to fight and cope with mis- and disinformation by 10 EU countries + UK (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, UK) are synthesized below. The findings of this section draw on data provided in COVINFORM *D7.1 ‘Baseline report: Communication and information’* and COVINRORM *D6.1 ‘Baseline report: Community and citizen responses’*. The main research questions are: What measures and initiatives have been implemented by (national) governments to fight and cope with mis-and disinformation during the COVID-19 pandemic? What best practices can be found amongst those measures and initiatives? The information analysed does not claim to be complete. Rather, it represents the data that was available online in the time period of March 2020 until March 2021 (D7.1) and March 2020 until June 2021 (D6.1). The various measures and initiatives were inductively categorised and then described.

7.2 Context and Background

The COVID-19 pandemic has been accompanied by an ‘infodemic’. According to the WHO an ‘infodemic’ is an overwhelming amount of information that also includes false or misleading information distributed in online and offline environments¹⁸. Especially the rapid development and distribution of vaccines have been accompanied by a large amount of misinformation, myths and conspiracy theories. However, even prior to that an abundance of false information on coronavirus cures and treatments, its origin and conspiracy theories about the virus itself circulated, particularly via social media. The growing digitalization contributes the rapid spread of any kind of information. Misinformation is harmful in several ways: it endangers democracy, public health, and even the lives of individuals. A particular negative consequence of this ‘infodemic’ is that misinformation can intensify and lengthen the COVID-19 outbreak as people receive false information about how to

¹⁸ https://www.who.int/health-topics/infodemic#tab=tab_1

protect oneself¹⁹. This becomes particularly apparent through the growing anti-vaxxer movement as there is a close connection between the spread of misinformation and anti-vaxxer beliefs (Germani & Biller-Andorno 2021). **Misinformation** is false information that is unintentionally propagated. **Disinformation** is deliberately propagated false information and includes what is understood under the term 'fake news'. **Malinformation** is information distributed with the intent to inflict harm on a person, organisation or country (Tucker et al. 2018). The latter will not be discussed in this report. Although they are distinct there is a close connection between disinformation and misinformation. While disinformation is deliberately spread, it can turn into misinformation when unsuspecting persons disseminate the misleading information. Misinformation is a multi-layered societal problem and should be treated as a serious danger to societies and individuals, as the ongoing "infodemic", accompanying the COVID-19 pandemic, has illustrated. Identifying and correcting misinformation is challenging for individuals but also for governments (Bertel 2020). The WHO (2020) outlined that meaningful 'infodemic' management should:

- Listening to community concerns and questions
- Promoting understanding of risk and health expert advice
- Building resilience to misinformation
- Engaging and empowering communities to take positive action

The European Commission²⁰ had developed a number of initiatives to tackle disinformation:

- the Code of Practice on Disinformation lays out a set of worldwide self-regulatory standards for industry;
- the European Digital Media Observatory is a European hub for fact-checkers, academics and other relevant stakeholders to support policy-makers;
- the action plan on disinformation aims to strengthen EU capability and cooperation in the fight against disinformation;
- the European Democracy Action Plan will develop guidelines for obligations and accountability of online platforms in the fight against disinformation;
- the Communication on 'tackling online disinformation: a European approach' is a collection of tools to tackle the spread of disinformation and ensure the protection of EU values;
- the COVID-19 monitoring and reporting programme, carried out by signatories of the Code of Practice, acts as a transparency measure to ensure accountability in tackling disinformation.

Hyland-Wood et al. (2020) point out that governments need to be pro-active in combating misinformation. Key is the provision of transparent provision of factual and current information as this can prevent the susceptibility of residents to misinformation and conspiracy theories (Jolley & Douglas 2017). In this deliverable we analyse the measures and initiatives used by 10 EU countries plus UK to tackle misinformation and disinformation.

¹⁹ <https://www.who.int/health-topics/infodemic>

²⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/online-disinformation>

7.3 Findings

7.3.1 Main findings

The following Table presents an overview of the implemented measures and initiatives to fight mis- and disinformation in the countries under research.

Table 4. Measures and Initiatives to fight mis- and disinformation

	Austria	Belgium	Ireland	Italy	Germany	Greece	Portugal	Romania	Spain	Sweden	UK	
											England	Wales
Channelling Information	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x		
Individual targeting	x											
Vulnerable group targeting	x		x								x	x
Information & awareness raising campaigns		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Info hotlines	x											
Taskforces	x	x		x								
Community based initiatives		x	x		x							
Trainings				x								
Strategic plan				x								
Fact checking							x		x			
Legislation									x			
Monitoring info									x			

All countries under research implemented some measures to fight mis- and disinformation. However, the numbers of measures and initiatives as well as the measures and initiatives themselves differ substantially from country to country. For example, Austria, Spain and Italy implemented a number of measures whereas little information could be found on the situation in Belgium and Romania. All countries set up information websites which provided residents with the latest government issued information on COVID-19. Most of the homepages have separate sections on mis- and disinformation. These government led websites were often accompanied by multi-channel information campaigns. Other countries run campaigns that specifically targeted mis- and disinformation through awareness raising campaigns. These should help residents to identify false information and stop their spread. Ireland was the only country that specifically targeted youth and teenagers with multiple campaigns. Striking was the lack of coherent strategies to fight mis- and disinformation. Only Italy implemented a

strategic plan to tackle this issue. In the next sections follows a more detailed explanation of the measures and initiatives taken by the 10 EU countries+ UK

7.3.2 Findings EU-10 UK

We could identify 12 different categories of measures and initiatives taken by national and local governments implemented by the countries under research. Below we will engage more in-depth with them.

Channeling of COVID-19 information

Eight out of ten countries cooperated with Google and/ or Facebook to channel user searches to official government communication instead of unreliable sources that potentially provide misinformation. This means that when users are searching for information on Google government homepages are the highest ranked search results.

Information and awareness raising campaigns

Many of these information campaigns used websites as their main information channel. However, information campaigns were also broadcasted on social media as well as traditional media outlets. The approaches of these various campaigns, however, differed from country to country. For example, Austria's approach lies in providing reliable information about the vaccine campaign and vaccination to residents. As such, the campaign tackles misinformation on vaccine but has no dedicated section addressing misinformation campaign. The campaign consists of a webpage, social media posts, videos and tv spots. Germany had a dedicated section on the federal government's website, titled "Myths and False Reports", which was set up to provide information and guidance detecting and handling misinformation. In addition to a list of reputable sources, the website section provides instructions on how false reports can potentially be identified.

Italy initiated multiple campaigns. Italy's public health authorities increased their use of social media channels to increase trust and reduce the impact of false information. Italy additionally launched info videos regarding vaccination. The country's awareness raising campaign focused on spreading greater knowledge on digital tools as well as the cognitive mechanisms on which the rapid spread of fake news is based.

Ireland launched national and local awareness raising campaigns to inform residents how best to identify fake news and 'de-bunking' misleading news stories or public health advice. In the course of the pandemic campaigns to raise awareness about misinformation became more target. For example, the government launched campaigns targeted at young people in the country. Portugal based their recommendations on combating misinformation on a UNESCO document and developed an information website^{21,22}. The Romanian government also launched a website which is the main portal to all relevant COVID-19 information including how to combat fake news²³. The Greek national government created a webpage where they counter mis- and disinformation as well as myths with scientific evidence whereas in Belgium the national as well as some of the local governments set up info homepages²⁴. Denmark launched information campaigns about vaccination based on reliable

²¹ <https://unescoportugal.mne.gov.pt/pt/temas/covid-19/a-unesco-combate-a-desinformacao-sobre-a-covid-19>

²² <https://covid19.min-saude.pt/>

²³ www.stirioficiale.ro

²⁴ www.info-coronavirus.be

experts and transparency. Additionally, a homepage provides information for the public on how to detect and handle dis- and misinformation. The UK launched multiple campaigns on local and national level to tackle for example misinformation in relation to vaccine for children aged 12 to 15. Social media such as Instagram and TikTok were used²⁵. Finally, Spain's national broadcaster developed an awareness raising campaign based on an interactive image that contains guidelines to identify common COVID-19 fake news.

Task forces, fact checking and monitoring

Austria and Italy created special task forces and teams to combat mis- and disinformation. The Austrian government installed the so-called 'digital emergency task force' which two main aims are to detect and correct fake news and misinformation and to guarantee that the community is well and comprehensively informed about the novel Corona virus^{26,27}. It sits within the Federal Chancellery of the Republic of Austria and receives support from the police. In Italy, the Autorità per le Garanzie nelle Comunicazioni (AGCOM) (English: Authority for Communications Guarantee) has appointed a *Task force on data science and online disinformation* with the aim to conduct studies and analysis on online disinformation and on the social / economic impact of both fake and real news on the epidemic. The taskforce has set up a monitoring system and analytical tools to tackle the spread of online disinformation. The Belgian police established a group of 21 investigators looking for online fake news and deleting false information where necessary²⁸. The Portuguese health department formed a partnership with an online factchecking journal to fight the spread of misinformation on COVID-19. This partnership identifies, evaluates and classifies information that is being publicly shared about COVID-19²⁹. The Spanish National Security Council passed the Action Procedure Against Disinformation (O. PMC/1030/2020) ordered by the Ministry of Presidency. This measure was taken to grant the authorities permission to permanently monitor and surveil various sources in order to detect dangerous fake news and stop their spread as soon as possible.

Other approaches

Italy has a comprehensive strategy to stop the spread of fake news and misinformation. The plan outlines measures to prepare for the autumn-winter season 2020 and to raise people's awareness and combat the spread of mis- and disinformation through targeted use of institutional channels such as press releases, web sites and social media, infographics and videos.

The plan included:

- management of interviews and the identification of institutional spokes-people;
- communication actions aimed at prevention for vulnerable population groups;
- activation of inter-institutional synergies to promote stakeholder training;
- dissemination of technical content and related updates on the management of this phase of the emergency to stakeholders (school, supermarkets, etc.)."

²⁵ <https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-england-suffolk-59289051>

²⁶ https://www.parlament.gv.at/PAKT/VHG/XXVII/AB/AB_01334/imfname_799682.pdf

²⁷ <https://www.derstandard.at/story/2000115961255/coronavirus-digitaler-krisenstab-im-kanzleramt-will-fake-news-bekaempfen>

²⁸ <https://radio1.be/federale-politie-zet-speurders-om-fake-news-te-bestrijden-gevaar-voor-maatschappij>

²⁹ <https://www.dgs.pt/em-destaque/coronavirus-poligrafo-e-direcao-geral-da-saude-estabelece-parceria-contra-as-fake-news.aspx>

- Moreover, there is also an effort for “preparedness activity to address increased transmission scenarios including:
 - constant monitoring of population sentiment through research, surveys and focus groups;
 - adaptation of the communication strategy to the different epidemiological scenarios by preparing where necessary media briefings and press conferences, with the presence of representatives of the institutions involved;
 - adaptation of the strategy and possible enhancement of activities on social channels;
 - timely information on new diagnostic and prevention tools.”

Additionally, Italy also planned on conducting distance training courses for public communicators to prepare them to counter mis- and disinformation.

Finally, Sweden and Greece, both had communication strategies. These overall risk communication strategies also outlined steps to stop the spread of mis- and disinformation. The information and awareness raising campaigns mentioned above were outputs of these plans.

The UK developed a toolkit as part of their misinformation awareness raising campaign. The toolkit can easily be disseminated via WhatsApp, Facebook Twitter, Youtube and Instagram. The goal was to tackle false information spread through private channels due to fears of low vaccine uptake amongst members of ethnic minorities. The campaign engaged community figures such as Imams, pastors and clinicians in the creation of shareable videos which include tips on how to spot and reduce the spread of misinformation, and links to trusted sources, such as the NHS³⁰.

Romania

The Romanian case is mentioned here as a negative example. Romania used its state of emergency as well as the provision relating to ‘misinforming the public’ to hold back information on COVID-19 cases in the country and to target people who were critical of the government’s pandemic management. For example, a criminal complaint for defamation was launched against the creator of video footage highlighting the poor quality of protective equipment issued to health service personnel³¹. Over 15 websites have been taken down during the state of emergency claiming the spread of fake news³². However, no any further explanation was given how these decisions were reached and the content and risk of these website was assessed. The ease with which these “extraordinary” measures were drafted and implemented raises serious concerns over the future of freedom of expression in Romania^{33 34}.

Reaching populations at risk of communication vulnerability

Risk communication as any communication needs to consider its audience and choose the medium, channel and content of communication accordingly. Further, government public health communication in times of crisis should be transparent and clear (Hyland-Wood et al. 2021). In the beginning of the pandemic simple and general information about the virus and how to protect oneself

³⁰ <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/government-targets-false-vaccine-information-on-social-media>

³¹ <https://cji.ro/en/are-new-forms-of-censorship-taking-form-during-the-pandemic-the-case-of-romania/>

³² <https://www.euractiv.com/section/politics/news/romania-shuts-down-websites-with-fake-covid-19-news/>

³³ <https://cji.ro/en/are-new-forms-of-censorship-taking-form-during-the-pandemic-the-case-of-romania/>

³⁴ <https://www.monitorulsv.ro/Ultima-ora-local/2020-04-09/Plangere-penala-facuta-de-Prefectura-Suceava-pentru-dezinformarea-publicului-larg>

was useful and appropriate because the lack of information was big and most people were seeking for information on the novel virus³⁵. Over time, more information on the virus and the ways to protect oneself and government measures to stop the spread were disseminated. At times, governments and their spokespeople contradicted themselves due to new scientific information, nontransparent communication, change of circumstances or political decision-making. As a consequence, there was more and contradictory information out there. This may have had an effect on how residents engaged and understood government communication and residents' trust in governments, in particular when residents felt that information was not transparent. Transparency in communication during a public health crisis should disclose what evidence was used to inform public-health recommendations, who was consulted, and what trade-offs were considered (Hyland-Wood et al. 2021).

Already early on in the pandemic the disproportional negative effects of COVID-19 on various social groups within the overall population were visible. For example, migrant groups, older people, people from a lower socio-economic background, Health Care Workers and BAME communities were amongst those social groups most vulnerable to negative health and socio-economic impacts of COVID-19^{36,37}. Communication-related factors such as social inequality, poor communication infrastructure, norms around information seeking, overly complex information or distrust towards sources of information too can be drivers of vulnerability, especially in crisis situations. Communication vulnerability occurs when the way in which information is received, understood, acted upon or considered trustworthy is negatively impacted by the above-mentioned factors (Hansson et al., 2020). In the specific context of COVID-19 communication vulnerability may be a result of e.g., language barriers in the case of migrants, lack of access to technology in the case of old people or lack of trust in the case of minority groups to only name some examples (Burgess et al. 2020).

Burgess et al. (2021) point out how essential participatory community engagement is for successful vaccination particularly when trying to reach groups that are most at risk. As Burgess et al. (2020) point out

The public is not a homogeneous entity. It is complex, composed of individuals, families, and other groups shaped by contexts, experiences, and desires in a constellation of communities with different patterns of health literacy, values, and expectations.

It has been proven that top-down, one-size-fits-all approaches often hindered the success of global health solutions. Particularly, in the case of vaccine implementation these approaches have the risk of leaving many groups behind. Vaccine campaigns should acknowledge the importance of local and community-led approaches. Their valuable advantage is that voices of diverse communities can be heard, concerns and alliances can be taking into consideration and allow for co-design solutions which have the potential to maximise vaccine uptake (Burgess et al. 2020, Anson et al. 2020).

The following local and national initiatives are well thought out approaches to stop the spread of mis- and disinformation. They are targeted at social groups at risk of communication vulnerability during

³⁵ <https://viecer.univie.ac.at/corona-blog/corona-blog-beitraege/blog04/>

³⁶ <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/community/health-equity/race-ethnicity.html>

³⁷ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/908434/Disparities_in_the_risk_and_outcomes_of_COVID_August_2020_update.pdf

the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the recommendations outlined by Burgess et al. (2020) the Irish, Flemish as well as Welsh approach stand out as best practice example:

In Ireland, local authorities collaborated with community leaders to fight misinformation in relation to the vaccine. As the vaccine rollout commenced in Ireland, a few vulnerable populations were targeted with misinformation regarding the ethical and medical qualities of the vaccines available. In one of the instances false information regarding the manufacturing processes of the vaccine were distributed via social media targeting Muslims and other minority groups and urge them not take the vaccine. To fight this false information a leading Irish Muslim scholar reassured clarified that the vaccine and its production fully comply with Islamic religious requirements. Further, he offered that the local authorities could use major Islamic centres as vaccination centre³⁸.

The city of Antwerp used a diverse group of so-called Sensi Ambassadors to support the government's COVID-19 communication while promoting trust and counter the spread of misinformation. Sensi Ambassadors do have a broad network in their respective community such as neighbourhood and migrant or religious community. These communicators were trained by the City of Antwerp. They distributed multilingual information materials and positioned themselves as trusted source of information within their community (City of Antwerp, 2020).

In Wales, the local government in cooperation with the Wales-oriented organisation 'Diverse Cymru' created a BAME Mental Health Online/Telephone support project in December 2020 to support Black, Asian, and minority ethnic people across Wales who struggled with their mental health during the pandemic. And at council level, representatives of the BAME communities in Swansea and Neath Port Talbot launched a campaign to dispel fear and mistrust about the COVID-19 vaccination programme to encourage people to get vaccinated. This 'Tell Me More Campaign'³⁹ signposts to accurate information from local BAME medical practitioners, faith and community leaders. It also relies on 'ordinary', non-expert, people who people are familiar with and are likely to take advice from.

Other well thought out strategies were implemented by the national government in Austria and the district office of Neukölln in Germany.

In Berlin the District Office of Neukölln has produced multilingual videos that debunk myths and conspiracy theories surrounding the virus, and most recently, vaccines. Videos are available in Turkish, Bulgarian, Romanian, Arabic, and German, reflecting the multicultural composition of the district itself.⁴⁰

Austria offered a CORONAVIRUS hotline to provide overall information on COVID-19. This hotline played an important role in countering misinformation while providing reliable information on the virus. The phone hotline played an important role in the COVID-19 information campaign as the government was able to reach people who are affected by the digital divide. Using phone services to reach older populations during COVID-19 has already proven to be effective in other contexts (Venville et al. 2021). Austria also used individual targeting to combat mis- and disinformation in the form of

³⁸ <https://www.irishexaminer.com/news/arid-40223888.html>

³⁹ <http://www.tellmemore.wales/>

⁴⁰ www.berlin.de/ba-neukoelln/corona/impfengegen-corona-wem-kann-ich-glauben-1050378

letter, emails and text messages in multiple language. This campaign was particularly aimed at migrants living in Austria.

7.4 Discussion/ Recommendations

The insights presented here have discussed the government measures and initiatives to fight and cope with mis- and disinformation. There is limited research and data examining the effectiveness of these measures and initiatives and further research should be conducted on this topic. Bertel and Troullinou (2020) outline several ways of fighting the spread of misinformation. These are: correcting and debunking, through nudging and cuing, and through education on media literacy and scepticism. Fact checking, for example, would fall under correcting and debunking false information whereas awareness raising campaigns could be categorised as education on media literacy and scepticism. However, to be effective, for example, fact checking must not directly challenge people's beliefs and values and it must and explain *why* the misinformation was disseminated in the first place or provide an *alternative explanation* of the relevant information (Lewandowsky, Ecker, & Cook 2017). This means fact checking alone is not a guarantee for a change in beliefs (De keersmaecker & Roets 2017). Even when set up according to guidelines evaluations will be needed to see if fact checking on governmental level proofs to be effective in the fight against mis- and disinformation. This report will be used as a starting point to investigate, if possible, the effectiveness and the evolution of measures and initiatives taken by governments during the COVID-19 pandemic in the next iteration of this deliverable. Another question that remained open are legal measures implemented in the countries under research. We will aim to answer these questions through our empirical research with experts and residents in 10 EU countries +UK. Finally, this report presented good and best practice examples of how to reach people at risk of communication vulnerability.

8 Representation and justice in media

This chapter focuses on the topic of *Representations and justice in media*. The spread of COVID-19 and the management of the pandemic have been surrounded by massive information and communication campaigns and intensive media coverage in all European countries (Pearman et al. 2021). Most of the crises occurring in Europe during the post-war period have affected limited numbers of citizens, or specific groups in society, and the majority of citizens usually only experience crisis through the news and/or social media. COVID-19 is a clear exception to this; during the pandemic, many people have been directly and personally affected by infection with the virus, and all have been indirectly affected in one way or another. As a consequence, the demand for information skyrocketed for example in Sweden during spring 2020 and has remained exceptionally high throughout the whole pandemic (Dahlgren, 2021). Not only personal experiences, but also media reports and narrations of the ongoing situation have contributed to people's perceptions of the pandemic and the way they have acted under the prevailing circumstances (Lilleker et al., 2021; Van Aelst & Blumler, 2021).

In this chapter, we address questions regarding media representations of issues, groups and single individuals related to the COVID-19 pandemic.

8.1 Methods

In the following we first provide a cross-country summary based on secondary data from Austria, Belgium, Greece, Germany, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, England, and Wales, based on the data collected and reported on in the D7.1 *Baseline report: Communication and information*. The country reports are rather inconsistent, but as far as the data permit, we try to compare which issues, groups and single individuals that are targeted in the media content, as well as how.

We then proceed to a more detailed case study of representations in Swedish media. This part of the report builds on content analysis of news media and social media, using both manual and automatized techniques. Some studies building on survey and interview data are also included.

8.2 Research questions

The following two research questions are addressed both in the cross-country overview and in the case study:

1. Which groups are represented in the media?
2. How are different concerns and threats addressed?

The third research question we will try to address in the final summary/discussion:

3. How might certain fears and threat perceptions be connected to prejudice, discrimination and hate speech?

8.3 Context and Background

Our point of departure is that creation, reinforcement, and modification of public attitudes is continually affected by messages in all forms of media content (Eayers, 1995). The media content affects *what* issues and *which* groups and individuals in society the public considers being important and holds an opinion about. What gets media attention also gets the public's attention, and media

thus contribute to *setting the agenda* for society's public debate (McCombs & Shaw, 1972). Furthermore, media take and copy content from each other. For example, smaller and local media with limited resources follow what is reported in elite national media. Similar journalistic content is then published with a local angle. Also, news media may monitor what is being discussed in social media, and then pick up on the same issues and topics in their own news reporting. This indicates the presence of an *intermedia agenda-setting*, with some media influencing what other media have on their agenda (Danielian & Reese, 2009).

But media content also affects *how* issues, groups and individuals are presented and perceived by the public (Entman, 1993). A frequently used metaphor in news media context to illustrate this aspect of the relation between news and reality is *framing*. It illustrates that for most people news acts as a window to reality, and that through its frame, people learn of themselves and others, of relevant issues and institutions, of lifestyles and of other countries. But like any other frame that delineates the world, the news frame focuses on certain aspects of reality, while it at the same time delimits and omits others (Tuchman, 1978). News content may thus never be a completely objective reflection or representation of reality (Hall, 1997). Instead, news content only reports fragments of what is happening in the real world, and the selection of these fragments is based on professional criteria of news value (Harcup & O'Neill, 2020). Issues, groups, and single individuals may thus be discriminated in media reporting in different ways: by incomplete or incorrect contextualization, by distorted or falsified information, or by not being represented in the media at all (cf. Tukachinsky, 2015). Although the theories of agenda setting (McCombs & Shaw, 1972) and of framing (Entman, 1993; Tuchman, 1978) are usually applied in studies of news media content, we argue that they are also applicable to other media, such as social media, entertainment media and advertisements (Stuart Hall, 1997). The content of these media also helps to direct the recipients'/public's attention to (strategically) selected issues and topics, to certain groups or individuals but not others, and to how different issues and problems should be understood, interpreted, and eventually solved.

Crises are events that usually occur unexpectedly, and that pose a threat to key societal values. Crises also produce a sense of urgency, a need of immediate action and response to mitigate negative consequences (Rosenthal et al., 1989; Sellnow & Seeger, 2021). In these acute situations people tend to rally around those responsible for dealing with the crisis. During such events of external threat, the public express support for the incumbent political leadership (Mueller, 1973; Tajfel, 1982). This rally-effect may help policy makers and responsible authorities to implement forceful measures to fight the crisis, even measures that severely restricts the freedom of the individual to behave and move as she or he prefers (Boin et al., 2016). But for this to be possible, responsible authorities depend on quick and reliable dissemination of necessary information to the public. In these situations, information and knowledge is transferred through major news media, which was also the case during the COVID-19 pandemic (Pearman et al., 2021). Media thus play an essential role in societal crisis communication, and the representation of the crisis in news media may both facilitate and complicate crisis management.

Two central concepts in this report are media and media representations. By *media* we intend news media, social media, websites, and entertainment media. By *media representations* we intend the ways in which media portray groups, communities, experiences, ideas, or topics from a particular ideologic or value perspective and thereby both create and communicate meaning (Bruns et al., 2017; Hall, 1997).

8.4 Findings

8.4.1 Main findings

EU-10

The media most used to disseminate information about the development of the pandemic in Austria, Belgium, Greece, Germany, Italy, Romania, Spain, Sweden, England, Wales, and Portugal were news media, government and organisational websites and social media. Authorities also frequently – sometimes daily – used press conferences to inform the public. These were often broadcast live via legacy news media and government websites.

The institutions and individuals that most frequently appeared in the media in connection with the COVID-19 pandemic represented either public authorities at the national, regional or local level, or medical expertise.

All countries identified several particularly vulnerable groups in their reports, and information measures that were specifically targeted at these groups. It may be assumed that the same groups were also mentioned and featured in the media coverage of the pandemic and in the discussions that took place on social media. Vulnerable groups became thus visible, and their needs highlighted in the public debate about the spreading of infection and mitigation measures during the pandemic.

The Swedish case study

The groups of actors that appeared most prominently in the Swedish news media during the corona pandemic were representatives of public authorities and politics, in particular the PHA and the government, representatives of businesses and enterprises, health care personnel and the public.

In the Swedish media, the pandemic has first and foremost been described as a contagion that affects the entire population. Just under a tenth of all articles and news items have focused on particularly vulnerable groups. During the spring and summer of 2020, the vulnerable groups that were specifically targeted were elderly persons, especially those living in care homes and those with home care, people with diabetes, cardiac and/or respiratory problems and pregnant women. The fact that people in immigrant dens areas were also more affected by the infection than others only became apparent in the autumn of 2020.

The news reporting of the pandemic had a distinct alarmistic tone, in the sense that dramatic and disturbing aspects of the pandemic were emphasized more often than reassuring and encouraging aspects.

The two overarching themes in the Swedish news reporting of the pandemic dealt with issues covering how the virus should be handled politically and medically, and how citizens generally should act and behave. The most common topics focused on government and political action, economic consequences of the pandemic, social restrictions, and the spread of infection. Four out of the five most common topics in the news gave a negative framing to the pandemic.

News media's reporting of the pandemic generated intense activity and interactions from the public on social media. Parallel patterns were apparent between the intensity of news media reporting and the public's corona-searches on Google. There was a more accentuated focus on human interest stories and conflict in news articles published on Facebook and Twitter than in news published in legacy

news media. News stories that dealt with individual experiences of the pandemic, or with moral dilemmas related to it, generated most interactions.

8.4.2 Findings from EU-10 reports

The country reports that form the basis of the following summary to varying degrees provide information on which actors – governmental representatives, organizations, and individuals – that appeared most in the media, which vulnerable groups that were identified and what issues and perspectives on the pandemic that dominated media content. While some countries' reports cover all aspects in detail, others cover some, and still others only a few. Hence, the results presented should be treated with caution and regarded as indicative only.

In a majority of the ten countries, the actors who appeared most prominently and frequently in the media during the pandemic represented the institutions responsible for managing the pandemic in each country. In several countries the responsible authorities were represented at the highest political level, such as by Chancellor (at the time) Sebastian Kurz in Austria, Prime Minister Giuseppe Conte in Italy, President Klaus Ioannis in Romania, Prime Minister Pedro Sánchez in Spain, Prime Minister Kyriakos Mitsotakis in Greece. In other countries the authorities were represented by government ministers, especially from the health and welfare sectors, such as the Minister of Health Marta Temido in Portugal and Minister of Health and Social Welfare, Lena Hallengren in Sweden. Various experts are also mentioned as spokespersons in several of the reports, but it is unclear to what extent they participated in media appearances. In Sweden, for example, Anders Tegnell, State Epidemiologist at the national Public Health Agency, was the most frequent representative of responsible authorities in the news media.

Large-scale information campaigns were commonly aimed at the general public, but targeted activities were also carried out for particularly vulnerable groups. An activity in all countries was the publication of pandemic vaccination information in several different languages aimed at ethnic/cultural minorities. Other vulnerable groups that were identified in many country reports, and presumably also highlighted in campaigns and media content, were elderly people (residents in elderly care, people with dementia, elderly with homecare), health care workers, and youngsters. The Belgium report also highlighted low-literate people; the Italian one caregivers of elderly people, women victims of domestic violence and pregnant women; the Greek migrant and refugees and individuals with disabilities; the Portuguese teleworking parents and Roma communities; and the Welsh one highlighted under-paid, self-employed, and unemployed people, people with learning disabilities and people working with charities. In summary, the same three major vulnerable groups recur in all countries, but otherwise the identified vulnerable groups partially reflect the demographic and socio-cultural composition of the population in each country.

From the information provided in the reports on general communications, targeted information campaigns, public announcements, etc. of the various countries, an attempt to derive knowledge about how media framed the pandemic can be made. Some themes recur in all reports. These emphasise health aspects, risk assessments, protective actions, including vaccinations, and society resilience. In addition, some reports indicate which issues/themes that have been particularly highlighted in the authorities' communications and narrations about the pandemic, and how these have been responded to in the public debate. For example, the Austrian report points out how public authorities engaged in self-praise and promoting their own capability in comparisons with other nations. The German report mentions focus on individual responsibility and self-discipline, and the

Swedish public discourse about the COVID-19 pandemic was based on scientific argumentation focusing statistics and mathematical probability calculations.

8.4.3 Findings from the Swedish case study

As a brief introduction to this part of the report, we would like to point out that Sweden adopted a different approach to mitigate COVID-10 infection than the rest of Europe and most other countries. The Swedish Public Health Authority was put in charge of handling the pandemic. Their strategy was not to stop transmission but to contain the spread of the virus. The means to do this was to collect facts, analyse them in a scientific way, and suggest measures based on the analysis (Johansson & Vigsö, 2021). In short, the Swedish strategy during 2020, designed and conducted by the Public Health Authority and supported by the Government, relied mainly on recommendations to take voluntary actions. No mandatory measures were taken to limit gatherings of crowds in public or private spaces, or to impose the use of face masks during the first nine months of the pandemic (Claeson & Hanson, 2021). Facemasks were introduced in care homes and health-care facilities in November 2020 and were recommended to be used in public transports during rush-hours as of January 2021. Also, a ban on sale of alcohol after 10 pm was introduced in November 2020, and later changed to 8 pm in December 2020. The main features of the Swedish strategies have been based on social distancing, to stay at home at the slightest sign of illness, to work from home, and after March 2021, to get vaccinated. Sweden never implemented any form of lockdown.

The following section describes how Swedish news media have reported on the corona pandemic, which pandemic-related issues that have been most prevalent on Swedish social media and how vulnerable groups have been portrayed in the media⁴¹.

Corona pandemic in Swedish news media

The Corona pandemic most likely is the biggest news event in Swedish media since the second world war. In 2020, the four largest print newspapers published a total of 37,202 articles, equivalent to 25 articles per day per newspaper over the 365 days of the year.

⁴¹ Large parts of this section are based on two publications on Swedish media content during the COVID-19 pandemic:

Ghersetti & Odén (2021) is based on content analysis of the two largest Swedish daily print newspapers, *Dagens Nyheter* and *Aftonbladet*, and the largest tv news program, *Rapport 19:30* in public service television, *Sveriges Television*. Analyzed time periods during 2020 have been: 24 February – 10 March, 31 March – 14 April, 2-18 June. During these three periods every second day of news reporting was analyzed, in total 1,319 news items.

Ghersetti (2021) is based on two different data sets of content analysis. The first presents data on how many news articles about the COVID-19 pandemic that was published in the four largest daily newspapers – *Aftonbladet*, *Dagens Nyheter*, *Expressen* and *Svenska Dagbladet* – between 1 January 2020 to 31 December 2020. The data were collected from the digital media archive *Retriver* by using the search terms *corona** and *covid**. The second data set consists of the two largest Swedish daily print newspapers, *Dagens Nyheter* and *Aftonbladet*, and the largest tv news program, *Rapport 19:30* in public service television, *Sveriges Television*. Analyzed time periods during 2020 have been: 24 February – 10 March, 31 March – 14 April, 2-18 June, and 16-30 September. During these four periods every second day of news reporting was analyzed, in total 1,473 news items.

Figure 61. Number of articles about the corona pandemic in Sweden’s four largest print newspapers, and number of covid-related deaths, per day during 2020.

The intensity of the reporting peaked in March and April, during the first pandemic wave, with an average of 49 articles per day per newspaper (Ghersetti, 2021). During the second wave of the pandemic, in November and December, media attention was significantly lower, with in average half as many articles per day (24 per newspaper per day). It is worth noticing that the number of deaths during the second wave exceeded the numbers in the first wave (4,912 and 4,301 respectively). The still declining news value of the pandemic suggests that it gradually normalized and became part of our everyday lives. The dramatic and sensational (and therefore newsworthy) elements of the pandemic faded as it evolved over the year. Another observation is that the media coverage was at its most intense about a month before the death toll peaked in April, i.e. when access to reliable data about the virus and its infectivity was scarce and the uncertainty about the future development of the pandemic was prevalent.

Unconfirmed information about the pandemic in the news media is probably also a contributing factor to the multiplication of Google searches for the word *corona* in March 2020 (Dahlgren, 2021a). We here identify a strong agenda setting effect, i.e., the exceptional focus of news media on the pandemic was reflected in the public’s searches for information on social media. A peak in the search statistics also occurred in November 2020, but it was not nearly as large as in the spring of the same year. Again, a parallel pattern may be detected between the intensity in new media reporting and the public’s corona-searches on Google. The search terms that Swedes mainly used to find information about the pandemic on Google encompassed three main areas of interest, (i) general information about the virus and its spread (*Sweden corona, corona in Sweden, corona statistics*) with reference to major news media (*corona Aftonbladet, corona SVT*), (ii) what the symptoms were and how to get tested (*COVID, symptoms, COVID tests, test COVID 19*), and (iii) information about protection through vaccination (*vaccination, vaccine COVID*) (ibid).

Not very surprisingly, there was a strong ethnocentric bias in the news about the corona pandemic to the extent that most of them reported on Swedish corona events or adopted a Swedish perspective on events from other countries (Ghersetti & Odén, 2021). During the first six months of the pandemic, 53 percent of all news described events occurring in Sweden, and 73 percent of all actors that were cited in the news reports represented Sweden or Swedish interests.

The topics that received the most attention in news media coverage were (i) *negative aspects of government and political action*, e.g. news about lack of political leadership, shortcomings in elderly care, unfavourable comparisons between Swedish and foreign strategies to combat the pandemic, (ii) *positive aspects of government and political action*, e.g. news about effective infection control, and measures to mitigate negative economic impact of the pandemic, (iii) *negative economic consequences of the infection*, e.g. news about negative effects on businesses' and individuals' finances, (iv) *closures and social constraints*, e.g. news about cancellation of events, visitor bans, closure of schools and universities, limited opening hours of bars and restaurants, and (v) *the spread of the infection* (sick and dead), e.g. news about the geographical spread of the pandemic and reports on the number of infected, dead and persons in intensive care in Sweden and abroad (Ghersetti, 2021). Four of the five topics framed the pandemic in a negative way.

Another study based on automated content analysis of 19 Swedish news sites and 700,000 articles about COVID-19 during the period of January 2020 to April 2021 identified two overarching themes concerning (i) how the virus should be handled politically and medically, and (ii) how citizens generally should act (Dahlgren, 2021a). The issue of vaccines and vaccination began to appear in the autumn of 2020 and steadily increased towards the turn of the year and early spring as vaccines were mass produced and delivered around the world. A word analysis of the dataset shows that the words *corona*, *infected*, *sick*, *elderly* and *quarantine* were particularly prevalent at the beginning of the pandemic while the words *vaccine*, *restrictions* and *facemasks* were most common later on.

Also, the news about the pandemic during 2020 had an alarmistic tone (Ghersetti, 2021). This means that the news emphasized negative and concerning aspects – such as the number of people affected, the risks and threats created by the crisis, and accounts of people behaving irrationally – rather than reassuring aspects, e.g., that society had the pandemic under control and that effective vaccine was on its way. Overall, the proportion of news articles reporting on alarmistic aspects of the pandemic was more than twice as large as the proportion reporting on reassuring aspects (51 percent and 23 percent, respectively).

The four most represented groups in the news during 2020 were politicians, businesses and enterprises, health care personnel, and the public (ibid). Together, these groups accounted for 54 percent of all actors appearing in the news and consequently, their views and framings of the pandemic were reflected in the reports. A study of public discourse in Swedish national newspapers during the first six months of the pandemic shows that Swedish political leadership and leading experts not only were the most prominent actors in the handling of the pandemic (the experts more than the politicians), but also that media coverage gave more echo than counterweight to response leaders' arguments (Baekkeskov et al., 2021). The newspapers repeated leadership justifications rather than moderated them, and arguments from inside the government ranks were favoured before arguments for credible alternatives.

The groups that received most support and praise in the news were representatives of health and social care, medical experts, and artists/athletes, in short those who nursed COVID-patients, those who explained the virus and its consequences, and professionals that suffered from implemented restrictions (Ghersetti, 2021). Those who were most criticized were the government, other Swedish politicians, and representatives of regional administration, i.e., those responsible for handling the pandemic, and for administering health service and elderly care.

The single most appearing public authority was the Swedish Public Health Authority, and the single most appearing individuals were the State Epidemiologist Anders Tegnell, Prime Minister Stefan Löfvén, and Lena Hallengren, Minister of Health and Social Welfare. Interesting, the single most mentioned foreign actor in the COVID-related news was President Donald Trump (Ghersetti & Odén, 2021, Dahlgren 2021a). Anders Tegnell usually headed the daily press conferences that were live broadcasted both in legacy and digital media, and that during most of 2020 became the pandemic bonfire where Swedes gathered at 2 pm for the latest news and updates about the spread of the disease (Dahlgren, 2021b). In very short time, Tegnell went from being almost unknown to becoming an icon, so much that he also appeared in entertaining media programs on radio and television, and that his face appeared on tattoos and baby garments. A study of Tegnell's appearances in Sweden's two major newspapers found that he usually contributed in the role of the *educator*, describing and explaining the spread of the infection (Ahlcrona & Granström, 2021). But he also appeared as a *guide*, giving advice and recommendations on how to endure the crisis, as a *defender* of the official covid-fighting strategy or of his own statements, and finally also as a *private person*, accounting for his life outside work.

The Corona pandemic in social media in Sweden

Widholm and Mårtensson (2021) have conducted an analysis of three major news media's (Aftonbladet, Dagens Nyheter, Rapport 19:30) publications on Facebook and Twitter between March and November 2020. Compared to print news, the news on social media were more framed towards human interest issues and conflict, which is consistent with results from previous studies of news framing in legacy media versus on social media (Rodin et al., 2018).

The social media news articles that generated most interactions were those presenting personal portraits of dead or infected people, of individuals otherwise affected by the pandemic, articles with a moral frame, e.g., issues concerning compliance with authorities' restrictions, and articles with conflict frames (Widholm & Mårtensson, 2021). In contrast, the news that generated low engagement in social media reported on vaccine development, societal and economic consequences, and on the restrictions imposed by the authorities.

Widholm and Mårtensson (2021) also observed that the public's interest in corona news faded as the pandemic went on. On a weekly basis, there was a strong correlation between high numbers of deaths and high levels of interactions in COVID-related news on social media. However, just as the intensity of news media reporting slowed down, also the public's interest in commenting, sharing, and reacting to corona news diminished during the second wave of the pandemic in autumn 2020.

Another type of social media that several Swedish news media launched on their websites during the corona pandemic was the news live-feed. In February 2020 the largest tabloid, Aftonbladet, opened its site for short news items interspersed with questions from the readers that were answered by the newspaper's journalists (Magnholt & Carlsson, 2021). The feed was continuously and frequently updated on a 24/7 basis. During the early days of the pandemic, most reader posts requested more data on the spread of the disease, protective measures etc., and the live feed enabled journalists to quickly, sometimes instantly, reach out with basic information. The newspaper almost came to serve as an emergency service centre, forwarding information from public authorities to the readers. However, as time went by, the readers' interest increasingly turned towards explanations of why and how things could have happened, including explanations about the newspapers' selection and evaluation of COVID-related issues.

Media representations of vulnerable groups in Sweden

Ghersetti and Odén's (2021) content analysis of news media in the first half of 2020 showed that the majority of COVID-reporting described the pandemic as a danger to the population as a whole. However, a small amount (8 percent) of the news items identified one or more societal groups as specifically vulnerable to the pandemic. These were people older than 70 years, people with cardiovascular diseases, asthmatics and people with critical respiratory conditions, people with obesity problems, pregnant women, smokers and people with diabetes.

Persons with migration background were not targeted by the news media as a specific vulnerable group during the first wave of the pandemic. However, at the end of June, a new medical study revealed that excess mortality during March to May 2020 among immigrants from Somalia, Syria and Iraq was significantly higher than among people born in Sweden, the EU, the Nordic countries or in North America (Hansson et al., 2020). During the summer and autumn, the media began to give more attention to this vulnerable group and question whether the authorities had taken measures aimed specifically at Swedish residents with foreign background e.g., COVID- information in foreign languages (Dagens Nyheter, 2021). Later in the pandemic, in spring 2021, the focus on persons with immigrant background shifted towards vaccination resistance, based on surveys showing that vaccination willingness was lower among foreign-born residents than among Swedish-born residents (PHA, 2021). People with a foreign background also received media attention in connection with the high mortality rate among elderly people in special housing or with home care services. Even before the pandemic, there was an over-representation of employees with foreign background in Swedish elderly care, as well as an over-representation of employees hired on an hourly basis (Kommunal, 2013). During the pandemic, weak Swedish language skills were raised as a possible contributor to the lack of use of protective equipment among employees in elderly care, and precarious employment conditions as a reason why employees did not always stay at home if they felt ill (Svenska Dagbladet, 2020).

After almost two years of the pandemic, it may seem obvious that the elderly have received much attention in the news. However, the elderly are a group in society that rarely reaches the Swedish news media, as are children, since media content mainly focuses on age groups that belong to the potential workforce (Edström, 2018). The news media's portrayal of the 65+ during the pandemic has been twofold. On the one hand, it has reinforced previous stereotypical images of elderly people as weak, sick, dependent and lonely. On the other hand, media have described persons older than 65 as bright, happy, healthy, innovative, positive, strong and self-reliant (Dahlgren & Kjellman, 2020). However, the more powerful and positive image derives from portraits of single individuals, often celebrities that were already known to the public.

In the case of health care workers, they were not really portrayed as a vulnerable group in Swedish media, but rather as professionals working long hours and under great pressure, at times under almost inhumane conditions. This was particularly the case of staff working in intensive care. Interestingly, an interview study conducted in the autumn of 2020 showed that many healthcare workers did not recognize themselves or their working conditions in the news reporting (Ekdahl, Morton & Starke, 2020). They found that intensive care was portrayed incorrectly, and that the focus in the reporting was misdirected. To many, the portrayal of health care workers was clichéd and too heroic. Also, there was too much focus on sensational cases of survival and recovery, and more essential aspects of their professional efforts were left out.

8.5 Discussion and recommendations

Given the exceptional attention that the COVID-19 pandemic received in the European news media, and the public's need for quick and reliable information when crises occur, a reasonable conclusion is that citizens across the EU27 largely used the news media to make sense of what was happening, and to take necessary action to protect themselves and others.

In line with theories of agenda setting (McCombs & Shaw, 1972) and framing (Entman, 1973; Tuchman, 1978) the COVID-related aspects highlighted by the news media, the vulnerable groups pointed out and the persons/institutions given prominence contributed to shape the public's perception of the pandemic and how it was mitigated. It also means that the groups highlighted in the media as particularly vulnerable were likely to be perceived as such by the public, regardless of whether these groups themselves felt vulnerable or not. Consequently, there was also a risk that the same groups were stigmatized through media exposure.

According to the country reports that form the basis of this summary, politicians and public authorities were responsible for managing the pandemic, and consequently most likely also were those that featured most frequently in the news media. We may therefore assume that in most countries, and at least during the acute phases of the pandemic, the news media assisted public authorities in conveying important messages to the public. Whether the public followed the authorities' advice and implemented restrictions varied both between and within countries and may depend on social factors such as media use, trust in authorities and in news media, ideology, political leaning, as well as the risk and crisis culture of individual countries (Dressel, 2015). And, of course, on how well those responsible for handling the pandemic succeeded in containing the infection and keeping the death rates down. Studies show that so-called rally-around-the-flag-effects occurred in many countries around the world during the initial stages of the pandemic, i.e., sudden and substantial approval of political and public leaders in response to the dramatical events (Blais et al., 2020, Esaiasson et al., 2021). One may assume that the recommendations and restrictions implemented during this phase of the pandemic to a large extent were adhered to by the public. However, these rally-effects tend to decline over time. According to Johansson et al. (2021) both ideology and perceptions of how the authorities had handled the pandemic were important independent drivers of declining rally-around-the-flag-effects. As the crisis became less salient, criticism against the management of the pandemic intensified, not at least in the news media, and accountability issues rose, political ideology become more important in explaining government support. Support decreased both among political opponents and political followers to the government, but less so among the followers.

In conclusion: the media's representations of the COVID-19 pandemic most likely have influenced how publics in different European countries have made sense of the crisis, how they have acted to protect themselves and others, how successful responsible authorities have been in mitigating the crisis, and in the long run, how the publics will evaluate the efforts implemented by their government and public authorities. Which in turn may have long term effects on the public's trust in public authorities and influence both the efficiency of crisis management and crisis communication in future crises.

9 Conclusions

This deliverable consists of seven research chapters, all aiming to shed light on a different aspect of the role of crisis communication during the pandemic. The first two chapters analyse visual data, namely (i) public health campaigns and (ii) memes related to the pandemic. The other five chapters analyse the following dimensions: good and bad practices of COVID-19 communication strategies (chapter 4), communication to influence behaviour change (chapter 5), digital communication and exclusion (chapter 6), fighting malinformation, disinformation and misinformation (chapter 7), and representation and justice in media (chapter 8). While the first two chapters are based on the primary analysis of visual data (public health campaigns, memes), the other five chapters use the desk research conducted in the context of T7.1 as a baseline.

The two overarching research questions outlined in D7.2 are:

- RQ1: How have different actors designed, delivered and evaluated inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation?
- RQ2: What impact have COVID-19 communication strategies and practices had on individuals from the majority population and vulnerable groups?

In the following, we will summarise the main insights, before presenting the next steps of empirical research in the context of WP7.

Chapter 2 presents the outcomes of an analysis of COVID-19 public health campaigns. A sample of 93 images was analysed through a content analysis, following the logic of Panofsky's (1962) iconographic-iconological method. In an explorative approach, themes and topics were coded inductively. The analysis identified two main topics of communication across all countries under analysis (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, UK): public health recommendations and hygiene guidelines, including both personal preventive measures and general advice, and (motivating) information about vaccines and the vaccination campaigns. A narrative of solidarity and unity was observable across countries, as well as a narrative about rebirth / restarting life through the vaccines. There was also a message regarding public health recommendations and hygiene guidelines observable. Further, we could identify a number of stylistic elements such as a simple and straightforward design, using text messages on a single-colour background. Also observable was the use of emotive strategies, aiming to evoke feelings of guilt and fear (in demonstrating the consequences of non-compliance), or hope. Particularly at a later stage of the pandemic, we can observe the use of humour, e.g. in the form of puns, rhymes, dialect words, or references to pop culture. A use of *joie de vivre*, particularly in combination with messages of rebirth or restarting life, accompanies some of the vaccination campaigns. Within the sample of public health campaigns analysed in this chapter, we could observe only sporadic campaigns tailoring messages to specific subgroups based on gender, age, regional, ethnic or cultural affiliations, as recommended by Bonell et al. (2020). Such tailored campaigns usually address either older persons or young persons, the former as the most vulnerable group, as well as the group prioritised for vaccinations, the latter as a group that has been impacted drastically and whose cooperation was needed to keep numbers low. We have also identified individual campaigns addressing migrants. In terms of their design, we can observe inclusive design in some campaigns regarding the representation of persons of different ages, gender, and ethnicity, yet we still can observe a focus on the (white) majority population. We have to point out, however, that certain campaigns, launched in languages other than the national language, were

not included in this analysis, according to the language capacities of partners located in the countries under research.

The third chapter focuses on the use of humour as a coping mechanism and presents outcomes of an explorative analysis of memes aiming to gain an understanding of how humour was used to cope with the events of the pandemic and communicate with others. A sample of 668 memes collected between the beginning of 2020 and autumn 2021 within the ten countries of analysis (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, UK) was coded inductively, creating categories through identifying themes within the data set. While the analysis focused mainly on the country-level, two categories or overarching themes were identified across all countries under research: a commentary on the measures on the one hand, and social criticism on the other hand. Measures are often commented as a coping mechanism, but we have also identified specific critique, for example, if measures seem too 'soft' to actually stop the spread of the virus, as well as when measures were perceived as exaggerated and restrictive. On the other hand, memes comment on the behaviour of people during the pandemic, including hoarding of goods (particularly toilet paper), non-compliance with measures (such as wearing masks), and the anti-vax movement. Overall, the majority of the memes analysed reflect or comment on the pandemic situation, sometimes in a critique of measures or politics.

Chapter 4 focuses on good and bad practices of COVID-19 communication in ten countries (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, and the UK), identifying several categories of relevance for good and bad communication practices. The analysis is based on the data collected for D7.1. Our findings show that each of the countries under research applied a country-specific communication approach in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. While the pandemic is still ongoing and this cannot be seen as a finished process, we have identified some good and bad practices. Good practices include the development of a strategy from the beginning, creating a collective feeling, as well as a feeling of responsibility of the individual, and a feeling of belonging. It is also relevant to acknowledge the effort of the population and provide examples of positive acts. The vulnerable population groups should be targeted; and multilingual, simple, and culturally sensitive information should be disseminated via different media channels. A multi-spokesperson strategy may be useful, in collaboration with private organisations. Messages need to be transparent, clear, open, timely, understandable, grammatically and lexically precise. Finally, a strategy to handle misinformation should be elaborated, allowing to react to rumours or misinformation in a swift manner. Bad practices include a failure to adapt strategies and a lack of openness to critique. Information should not only be provided by political leaders, and inconsistency may cause confusion, as well as a lack of expertise of spokespersons. A lack of involvement of experts from communication and/or behavioural sciences, as well as a delay in information release, are further bad practices. Finally, information overload as well as errors in the data should be avoided. As such, multiple factors need to be taken into consideration when planning such strategies and ultimately, all population groups must be addressed.

The fifth chapter focuses on communication to influence behaviour change, discussing communication strategies in eleven countries (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Romania, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, England, and Wales). Drawing on insights from *D2.1 Database containing different data sources* and *D7.1 Baseline report: Communication and information*, this chapter explores how (if at all) communication strategies encouraged people in undertaking protective public health behaviours, including mask-wearing and regular handwashing; physically distancing; avoiding mass gathering;

staying at home; working/schooling from home; public testing; and vaccinating. In general, compliance with government's measures was high in the majority of countries during the first lockdown. However, this allows no in-depth evaluation of the impact of government communication on behaviour change itself. Nonetheless, it gives an indication that government communicated in a way that enabled the majority of residents to follow their measures at least to some extent. Further research and evaluation are needed to understand the effectiveness of government communication on behaviour change, particularly in relation to diverse and vulnerable audiences. Further, as the pandemic is unfolding for almost two years now, communication and measures have changed and so has, most likely, the willingness or ability to comply to measures involving behaviour change. Here too, further research is needed. Investigating time dimensions would also allow for insightful comparisons. There is limited research assessing the effectiveness of the communication strategies of the eleven COVINFORM EU + UK countries as evaluations focus on compliance. As such, research on the effectiveness of communication strategies on behaviour change is needed.

In chapter six, we focus on digital communication and exclusion through an extensive literature review. An increase of all forms of digital media use, particularly of video conferencing tools, but also an increase in internet use, has had both positive and negative effects on people: staying connected via digital technologies may reduce feelings of isolation and loneliness; however, some groups within society may face challenges to meaningfully connect online. The digital divide is caused by four factors that increase digital inequality: technical means, the autonomy of use, social support networks, and experience. Research (Baum et al. 2014; Ragnedda 2017) has shown that lower socio-economic backgrounds impact the digital divide and thus amplify existing disadvantages. This existing effect has been worsened during the pandemic; the reliance on digital technologies in the crisis has reinforced and deepened existing societal inequalities related to factors like socioeconomic status, age, education, and health literacy (Beunoyer et al., 2020; van Deursen, 2020), and we have seen that health, societal, and economic impacts of the virus disproportionately affect these vulnerable and disadvantaged populations (Budd et al., 2020). Some vulnerable groups may be at increased risk of contracting the virus due to the digital divide and a subsequent lack of information on the virus, vaccines, and other public health aspects provided online: vulnerable groups such as older or chronically ill persons as well as those living in poverty, who are generally more digitally disconnected, are also at higher risk of the effects of the pandemic (Van Deursen 2020; Gabbiandini et al. 2020). For this reason, there is a need for policy change to mitigate digital inequalities, including the development of strategies to reduce the digital divide, offering affordable access to communication technologies, as well as more focused policies aiming to enhance people's health outcomes, such as encouraging people to engage with information and communication related to COVID-19 online.

In chapter seven, we focus on the measures taken in the countries under research (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, and the UK) to combat disinformation and misinformation. The COVID-19 pandemic has been accompanied by an overwhelming amount of information, including misinformation, in what the WHO titled an infodemic. Based on the information collected for D7.1, we have identified measures and initiatives to fight misinformation including: channelling information, individual targeting, targeting of vulnerable groups, information campaigns and awareness-raising campaigns, information hotlines, taskforces, community-based initiatives, training, strategic plans, fact-checking, legislation, and monitoring information. While all countries implemented some measures, the numbers of measures and initiatives as well as the measures and initiatives themselves differ substantially from country to country.

Chapter eight focuses on representation and justice in media, particularly in news media, which people use to make sense of the crisis. The chapter provides an analysis of the groups represented in media, as well as the way different concerns and threats are addressed. A cross-country analysis was conducted based on the information collected for D7.1 for ten EU+UK countries (Austria, Belgium, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Romania, Spain, Sweden, and the UK), as well as an additional case study conducted in the context of Sweden. It further analyses how certain fears and threat perceptions may be connected to prejudice, discrimination and hate speech. Those COVID-19-related aspects highlighted or addressed by news media shape the public's perception of the pandemic and how it is being mitigated. It further influences how the public in different European countries has acted to protect themselves and others, and how successful authorities have been in mitigating the crisis. Furthermore, while this means that the groups highlighted in the media as particularly vulnerable are likely to be perceived as such by the public, there is also a risk that the same groups are stigmatized through media exposure. All of these aspects may have long-term effects on the public's trust in public authorities, which in turn may influence both the efficiency of crisis management and crisis communication in future health crises.

Regarding RQ1, which aims to gain an understanding of how different actors have designed, delivered, and evaluated inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change, we have found that information campaigns have, at least initially, been addressed to the general public, before more targeted campaigns were launched. While there are some efforts to design campaigns inclusively, we could still observe a focus on the (white) majority population. We have further identified good and bad practices of COVID-19 crisis communication. With regards to addressing mis- and disinformation, we have found that while all countries under research have implemented some measures, they differ substantially between countries.

Regarding RQ2, *What impact have COVID-19 communication strategies and practices had on individuals from the majority population and vulnerable groups?*, we found that memes are a way to cope with the pandemic situation, particularly as a way to comment and critique measures, as well as the behaviour of members of society. Furthermore, the shift towards digital communication, as described in chapter 6, as well as the pre-existing digital divide, increased digital inequalities. This shift towards digital communicating unveiled a need to improve policies and access to digital media. Finally, we found that the way media provide information about the crisis influences how members of the public make sense of the pandemic, including which groups are perceived as vulnerable. It further influences trust in crisis management and crisis communication.

The analyses conducted for this deliverable unveiled some gaps that will be investigated further (see below). These include, on the one hand, the effect of information campaigns and media representation on residents, particularly on groups defined as vulnerable. On the other hand, the impact of COVID-19 communication on behaviour change needs to be explored further as well as what is considered to be good communication from a resident perspective.

9.1 Limitations

The research presented in this deliverable is explorative and thus does not claim representativity. Following a qualitative approach, the two chapters presenting the outcome of the analyses of visual data conducted empirically for this report explore and identify topics and themes of public health campaigns, as well as the way memes are used as a coping strategy during the ongoing pandemic. Due

to country-specific differences (culturally as well as due to the different national approaches to handling the pandemic situation), as well as variations in search strategies conducted by partners (caused by the country-specific differences of both public health campaigns and memes), we aimed for country analyses while still aiming to identify overarching themes. As such, both analyses provide highlights and inputs for the subsequent fieldwork, as well as stimulus material for interviews.

The other five chapters are based on data collected through desk research, covering a time span between March 2020 to March 2021. The data included public health campaigns, government statements, strategy papers, grey literature, academic publications, newspaper articles, and evaluations of social media posts. As such, it is not comprehensive but constitutes the openly available information in the presented timeframe.

With regards to the overarching RQs of WP7, we can provide only limited answers through this deliverable, particularly regarding the impact of COVID-19 communication on vulnerable groups. This will be the main focus of the empirical fieldwork, particularly the research with residents.

9.2 Outlook & next steps

During the empirical research, interviews will be conducted with residents as well as communication experts (either involved in COVID-19 communication and/or researchers) to gain more in-depth knowledge on the design of good and bad practices of communication strategies as well as the ways in which diverse groups of (vulnerable) residents perceived certain strategies and COVID-19 communication intended to change behaviour. The interviews will shed light on the lived experience of residents as well as the challenges of those in charge of implementing effective communication. More in-depth analysis of media discourses in each of the countries could be conducted in the second iteration of this deliverable to focus on issues identified in this deliverable. A focused search for the initiatives and measures found in the current report could be done to gain a more comprehensive picture of the fight of dis- and misinformation as the COVID-19 pandemic continues. Evaluation of dis- and misinformation strategies would be of great interest as these are still missing. These will be beyond the scope of this project. However, interviews with residents could give insights into the effectiveness of such initiatives. Based on the diligent literature review provided by MDI on the question of the digital divide, residents at risk of communication vulnerability, community organisations and communication experts could be interviewed to understand the challenges for those at risk as well as those developing communication strategies. Best practices examples could be derived and provided.

Furthermore, as described in chapter 2, we are aiming to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the public health campaigns once fieldwork with residents and communication experts has been conducted, thus synthesising results. Further, insights regarding behaviour change will be taken into account.

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Project deliverables

COVINFORM D2.1 Database containing different data sources.

COVINFORM D7.1 Baseline report: Communication and information.

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